

Chapter 1

SETTING THE SCENE¹

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Chapter 1

SETTING THE SCENE

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This IPBES assessment is a comprehensive and ambitious intergovernmental effort that aims to provide policy and solution-oriented approaches towards more sustainable use of wild species, recognizing the diversity of practices, uses and contexts. The core of this assessment is therefore not to evaluate the status of wild species worldwide, nor to exhaustively document the impacts of human uses on wild populations or the various biotic and abiotic components of the ecosystems that they inhabit, as unsustainable use of wild species has been extensively covered elsewhere. This assessment focuses on: (i) how sustainable use is conceptualized by different groups, (ii) the status and trends in use of wild species and its consequence for nature and nature's contributions to people, (iii) the main drivers of change, (iv) the various scenarios for the future and finally (v) the effectiveness of policies, governance systems and institutions for managing the use of wild species.

1 The use of wild species contributes directly to the well-being of billions of people globally. In some countries, wild foods contribute to food and nutrition security for one third to 100% of the nation's population or select populations within it. Plants, algae and fungi provide food, income and nutritional diversity for an estimated one in five people around the world, in particular women, children, landless farmers and others in vulnerable situations. Freshwater and marine fisheries are primary sources of animal protein, nutrients and income for hundreds of millions of people worldwide, while wild meat from terrestrial animals remains a major source of protein for some rural and urban populations. The use of wild species also provides non-material contributions by enriching people's physical and psychological experiences, including their religious and ceremonial lives.

2 Use of wild species is particularly important to people in vulnerable situations on both a day-to-day basis and in times of crisis. The viability of wild species as livelihood resources for all people, but especially individuals and communities in vulnerable situations, depends fundamentally on their sustainable use. In many cases, a single species may have multiple uses and contribute to human well-being in multiple ways.

3 For many indigenous peoples and local communities, the use of wild species is inextricably entwined in culture, identity and livelihoods. Globally, lands managed by indigenous peoples and local

communities display high biodiversity, including sustainable use of wild species grounded in indigenous and local knowledge systems. Unsustainable uses of wild species both contribute to and result from loss of culture and identity in indigenous and local communities. Thus, the answer to the question of how to ensure sustainable use of wild species has profound implications for the survival of indigenous peoples and local communities. Likewise, indigenous and local knowledge can play an important role in identifying and supporting existing sustainable uses of wild species and pathways to further sustainable use in the future.

4 Overexploitation of wild species is a key driver of biodiversity decline together with other factors, including (but not limited to) land use/land cover change, pollution, climate change and invasive alien species. This decline is substantial as, for instance, indicated by the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species, which classifies 28% of the species assessed to date as being threatened with extinction or by the IPBES Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services that documented an unprecedented species extinction rate over the past decades. The adverse consequences of species decline on human well-being are receiving increasing global attention, especially in relation to food security, human health, awareness of climate crisis and rights and livelihoods of indigenous peoples and local communities.

5 The results of human uses of wild species are not always and everywhere destructive. Indeed, much of the biodiversity people seek to protect owes its origins to long-term relationships between the biophysical environment and the practices of indigenous peoples and local communities, including their uses of wild species. Indigenous peoples manage fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting and other uses of wild species on more than 38 million km² of land in 87 countries. This area coincides with approximately 40% of terrestrial conserved areas, including many with high biodiversity value. Cases around the world provide examples of successful efforts to restore populations of overexploited wild species to assure their long-term sustainable use at scales from the local and national to the regional and international.

6 It is simultaneously true that: (a) unsustainable use of wild species contributes to accelerating biodiversity loss, and (b) sustainable use of wild species is an avenue for realizing conservation and development goals. This is not a contradiction. Rather, it is

an acknowledgement that the outcomes of the use of wild species depend on social and ecological factors. These include species ecology and the status and properties of the ecosystems that they inhabit. They also depend on the history, technology, and economics of use, as well as the governance systems through which they are managed. Each of these factors are embedded in conceptualizations of the relationship between people and nature. Biodiversity loss often results from the disruption or intensification of uses that previously had been sustainable.

7 Sustainable use of wild species may contribute in multiple ways to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, but these potential contributions are most often overlooked.

Sustainable use of wild species can support better quality of life for people in the most vulnerable situations and is also an essential component of good quality of life for all. However, these potential contributions are poorly reflected in targets and indicators of several Sustainable Development Goals. While the contributions of the sustainable use of wild species has been identified for Sustainable Development Goal 14 (life below water) and 15 (life on land), there is untapped potential for contributions to the rest of the Sustainable Development Goals. Further attention to ways in which the sustainable use of wild species can support good quality of life for people and the planet will contribute to realizing these global goals.

8 The use of wild species involves at least three components, which interact in a dynamic way. These are (i) the wild species being used, (ii) the practices undertaken by people when they use wild species and (iii) the uses for goods and services derived from wild species.

- **Wild species** refers to populations of any species that have not been domesticated through mutigenerational selection for particular traits, and which can survive independently of human intervention that may occur in any environment.
- **Practices** have been divided into extractive (fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, and logging) and non-extractive (observing) practices.
- **Uses** have been divided into nine categories, which are not mutually exclusive (aesthetic, construction, energy, food, learning, medicine, recreation, ritual and others).

These three components are affected by environmental, political, demographic, economic, cultural and technological drivers. The ways in which wild species, practices and uses are managed can determine whether outcomes are consistent with sustainable use.

9 Sustainable use is an outcome of social-ecological systems that aim to maintain biodiversity and

ecosystem functions in the long term while contributing to human well-being. It is a dynamic process as wild species, the ecosystems that support them and the social systems within which their uses occur, change over time and space.

10 The sustainable use of wild species will benefit from transformative change in the prevailing conceptualization of nature, shifting from the human-nature dualism deeply rooted in many (but not all) cultures, to a view that humanity is part of nature.

Views of the human-nature relationship that separate nature (understood as existing by itself) from culture (produced by humans) have a profound influence on perceptions of the functioning of the biosphere and the language used to understand and describe it. Although many cultures consider nature and humans to be indivisible, a conceptual separation between people and nature is pervasive and may be found in most national and international instruments and policies. This human-nature dualism fosters the illusion that humanity could exist apart from or in control of the rest of nature. Considering humanity to be part of nature (i.e., one member or citizen of nature among many others) would lay the foundation for a more respectful and sustainable relationship, as shown by indigenous peoples' and local communities' traditional practices and uses.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Rapid declines in biodiversity and degradation of ecosystem functions and global environmental commons, such as climate and water resources, heavily affect human well-being (IPBES, 2019a; Millenium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The nature and extent of this decline is well documented from an ecological/conservation perspective (IPBES, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2019a; IUCN, 2021b; WWF, 2018) due to strong and long-lasting efforts from several international bodies, the academic research community and environmental non-governmental organizations. This decline is substantial as, for instance, indicated by the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species, which classifies 28% of the species assessed to date as being threatened with extinction (IUCN, 2021b), or by the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019a), which documented an unprecedented rate of species extinction and its effect on human well-being over the past decades. These effects can be attributed to direct drivers, such as habitat destruction, biological invasions, climate change and overexploitation (IPBES, 2018e, 2019a; Román-Palacios & Wiens, 2020) or indirect drivers, that can alter ecosystem functioning and productivity (Casini *et al.*, 2012; Daskalov *et al.*, 2007; Palkovacs *et al.*, 2018). The adverse consequences of species decline on food security and nutrition (Golden *et al.*, 2016), human health (Sandifer *et*

et al., 2015), conservation and the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities (Sasaoka & Laumonier, 2012; Turner *et al.*, 2013) and other requirements for human well-being are receiving increasing global attention.

There is consistent and substantial evidence that use of wild species has in many cases occurred at unsustainable levels, exceeding the populations' capacities to recover (IPBES, 2019a; Vignieri, 2014). Declines in a wide range of taxa (both plants and animals), due to non-sustainable use of wild species, have been recorded across marine (FAO, 2020b; Lam & Sadovy de Mitcheson, 2011; Pacoureau *et al.*, 2021; Worm *et al.*, 2009), inland waters (Allan *et al.*, 2005; FAO, 2020b; Fluet-Chouinard *et al.*, 2018) and terrestrial ecosystems (Coad *et al.*, 2019; Fa *et al.*, 2006; FAO, 2018b). Direct exploitation by humans has been identified as the most serious driver of biodiversity loss in marine ecosystems and as the second most important driver in terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems (Coad *et al.*, 2019; IPBES, 2019, 2018a, 2018b; FAO, 2018a, 2018b; Vignieri, 2014; Fa *et al.*, 2006; Allan *et al.*, 2005; Fluet-Chouinard *et al.*, 2018). The extent of decline has clearly shown that many current policies are inadequate and/or their implementation is ineffective. This has increased the urgency to identify ongoing policies that work and scale them up, or find alternative approaches when ongoing policies have been unsuccessful (IPBES, 2019a).

The decline in biodiversity also affects human communities who directly or indirectly depend on the use of wild species. Regular use of wild foods is an important component of global food and nutrition security. Although more data are needed to establish a complete picture of the contributions of wild foods to people around the world, some countries report that between one third and 100% of their national or subnational populations may use wild foods at certain times (FAO, 2019). Wild marine and freshwater species (mostly fish, crustaceans and mollusks) provide 54% of the world's seafood production which accounted, in 2017, for 17% of the global population's intake of animal proteins and 7% of all proteins consumed (FAO, 2020b). Wild meat from terrestrial animals is also a major source of protein for rural and urban populations (Coad *et al.*, 2019). A wide range of wild-harvested plants, fungi and lichens are used and traded, including 30,000 plant species for medicinal or aromatic uses, an estimated 60-90% of which are gathered in the wild (Jenkins *et al.*, 2018). Wild forests (often referred to as natural forests) provide a significant proportion of wood for material and construction, energy (fuelwood or charcoal) and food to people, particularly in developing countries (FAO, 2018b). An estimated 5% to 8% of current global crop production depends on wild animal pollination, which corresponds to an annual market value of US\$235 billion to US\$577 billion (IPBES, 2016). People in vulnerable situations are often most reliant on wild species and are most likely to benefit from more sustainable

forms of use of wild species to secure their livelihoods (FAO, 2018b). Biodiversity decline nevertheless also affects the economies of developed countries, especially those depending on the use of wild species, such as fisheries, the logging industry, the medicinal plant industry or tourism (see Chapters 3 and 4). Further, the use of wild species provides non-material contributions by enriching people's physical and psychological experiences, including their religious and ceremonial lives (Anthony & Bellinger, 2007; Russell *et al.*, 2013). Determining and enhancing the sustainability of uses of wild species is thus a critical issue for conserving biodiversity and contributing to human well-being.

Although overexploitation of wild species is well documented, there are many examples of success in maintaining or restoring populations for long-term use (Cromsigt *et al.*, 2018; Lichtenstein & Vilá, 2003; Mahoney, 2019). Finding ways to prevent the ongoing loss of species and mitigate the concomitant impacts on human well-being remains a major challenge. Human societies have grappled for millennia with profound questions relating to the harvest of wild species to meet their needs, the balance required for those same species to thrive, and the distribution of benefits derived from wild species. The knowledge, customary institutions and practices of many indigenous peoples and local communities ensure sustainable use of the species and environments on which they rely (Berkes, 2018; Comberti *et al.*, 2015; Minnis & Elisens, 2000). However, local and global changes in the environment, consumption patterns and the rapid growth in human population have greatly altered the context in which wild species are used and managed. Complex social-ecological dynamics operating from local to global scales underlie the use of wild species (Brashares & Gaynor, 2017; Ostrom, 2009) and influence the likely outcomes of policies and practices aimed to maintain and restore them.

There have been numerous national, bilateral and multilateral initiatives to find policy and management solutions favoring the sustainable use of wild species. National policies and regulations relating to the use of wild species date back more than 2000 years in China (Schäfer *et al.*, 2018; Yi-Ming *et al.*, 2000) and at least to the 13th century in Europe (Bazeley, 1921; R. C. Hoffmann, 2005). Over the past century, many agreements for the use of wild species have been developed and refined (Gulbrandsen & Humphreys, 2006; McDermott *et al.*, 2007; Rice, 2014, see Chapter 2). These include specific agreements on whales, fishing, logging, and hunting that have been set at national levels or through specific international management bodies, such as the International Whaling Commission, regional fisheries management organisations, and the International Tropical Timber Organization, which all aim to ensure more sustainable harvest of wild species. They also include more general instruments, such as the Addis Ababa Principles and Guidelines for the Sustainable Use of Biodiversity adopted under the Convention on Biological Diversity (see:

<https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-07/cop-07-dec-12-en.pdf>). Various global targets for sustainable use have been developed, such as the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation, the Aichi Biodiversity Targets of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and the Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the United Nations. However, these are non-binding policy instruments and the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation and Aichi Biodiversity Targets failed to achieve sustainable use (IPBES, 2019a). It will remain a challenge to achieve the targets under the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030 and it is therefore important to understand how sustainable use of wild species contributes to the Sustainable Development Goals and what can be done to achieve sustainable outcomes.

Sustainable use of wild species features prominently in several international assessments, such as those done by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) on fisheries and forestry (FAO, 2018b, 2018c, 2020b, 2020a), the Center for International Forestry Research on terrestrial wildlife (Coad *et al.*, 2019) and IPBES on biodiversity at global (IPBES, 2019a) and regional levels (IPBES, 2018d, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c). These assessments provide a strong background on the status and trends of wild species and problems relating to use of wild species (see section 1.5). Nevertheless, the status of many species remains unassessed because of a lack of monitoring, technical limitations, unreported illegal practices and trade, lack of appropriate experts or simply lack of recognition of existing practices and sources of knowledge (e.g., indigenous and local knowledge, see Chapters 3 and 4). Governance systems in place are also often undocumented, particularly those of indigenous peoples and local communities. Further, the nature and extent of human uses, harvesting rates and traditional management practices remain poorly documented, especially for uses that are not subject to trade. Despite general approaches, such as those identified by the precautionary approach (Garcia, 1996), uncertainty and lack of consensus regarding scientific advice (e.g., about the way to model population dynamics under use) have resulted in often divergent views on which policies to support and sometimes led to heated controversies, such as on whaling, fisheries or trophy hunting (e.g., Fromentin *et al.*, 2014; Mkono, 2019; Peace, 2010). This can lead to policy inertia or policies being maintained that are ineffective or, worse, that provide perverse incentives resulting in further loss of biodiversity and human well-being. It is also crucial to clearly understand and define people's needs (Singh *et al.*, 2021) and to assess with them potential solutions to optimize the social acceptability of various policy instruments put in place to regulate the use of wild species (see also Chapters 4 and 6).

The IPBES thematic assessment of the sustainable use of wild species (hereafter “the sustainable use assessment”) is a comprehensive and ambitious intergovernmental effort

that aims to build on previous assessments and address the challenges faced by policymakers. According to the scoping report set out in annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1, the objective of this thematic assessment is: “to consider various approaches to the enhancement of the sustainability of the use of wild species and to strengthen related practices, measures, capacities and tools for their conservation through such use”. In other words, the aim of this assessment is not to evaluate the status of wild species worldwide, nor to exhaustively document the impacts of human uses on wild populations or the various biotic and abiotic components of the ecosystems that they inhabit, as this has already been done by the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019a) or by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (2020). Instead, the core of this assessment is to evaluate sustainability through the lens of different practices and uses by:

- Reflecting on how sustainable use is conceptualized by different groups (stakeholders, scientists, indigenous people, local communities);
- Assessing the status and trends in the use of wild species and consequences for nature and nature's contributions to people;
- Understanding and assessing the main drivers of change;
- Examining scenarios for the future;
- Assessing the effectiveness of policies, governance systems and institutions for managing the sustainable use of wild species;
- Identifying the main gaps in knowledge and data as well as the main challenges and opportunities associated with the sustainable use of wild species;
- Addressing uncertainties regarding the outcomes of policies and actions; and
- Providing an objective assessment of disputed facts and statistics.

1.1.1 Diverse uses of wild species by people and practices associated with them

All uses of wild species are embedded in social-ecological systems, defined as complex adaptive systems that include social (human) and ecological (biophysical) subsystems in a two-way feedback relationship (Berkes, 2011; Chapin *et al.*, 2009). Because the social and ecological subsystems function as a coupled, interdependent and co-evolutionary system (Berkes & Folke, 1998), social-ecological systems

constitute natural units of analysis of the sustainability of wild species use. An analytical framework proposed by Ostrom (2009) distinguishes four interacting subsystems which comprise the resource units (e.g., fish), the resource systems (e.g., coastal fishery), the users (fishers) and the governance systems (organizations and rules that govern fishing on that coast). These components interact to produce outcomes at the system level, which are also influenced by external drivers (see Figure 1.1). For the purpose of this assessment, drivers are recognized as all the factors that directly or indirectly influence the use of wild species, such as environmental, economic or cultural drivers (see Chapter 4).

A first step for undertaking an assessment of the sustainable use of wild species is to recognize the diverse ways in which people use wild species. This diversity results from the intersection of several dimensions (Figure 1.1), primarily: (i) the wild species used by people, which encompass all main species groups, including algae, animals, fungi and plants, from freshwater, marine and terrestrial habitats; (ii) the goods and services derived from those species, referred to in this assessment as “uses”, including food, energy, materials, medicine or recreation (see section 1.3.4); (iii) the means or practices used to obtain benefits from wild species, including extractive and non-extractive practices; (iv) the destination and distribution of benefits

derived from wild species, ranging from personal/family use or consumption to products sold in local informal markets, to those traded as global commodities in the international market; and (v) the statutory, customary and informal institutions, access regimes and rules that regulate uses and practices. The intensity of use of wild species and the scale of the operations involved vary enormously and are the main factors in evaluating sustainability and suitable forms of regulation. Furthermore, the components are affected by various drivers and the way they are managed can determine whether the outcomes of such complex social-ecological systems are consistent with sustainable use.

The use of wild species involves various practices associated with their harvest and/or other kinds of interactions with them. For the purpose of the assessment, these practices have been classified into five categories, which are generally associated with the species in use, i.e., fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging and non-extractive practices. While most practices used to obtain benefits from wild species clearly fit within one of these five categories, there are some that are not so obviously classified. To avoid ambiguity, a working definition of the five practices for use across all chapters is developed in Section 1.3.4. Within each practice, uses may be characterized by the users, the wild species and

Figure 1.1 A diagrammatic representation of the interactions between the end use of wild species, the practices associated with use, and the populations under use within the context of the drivers and responses that may influence sustainability.

ecosystems used, their interactions and the context within which uses occur.

The wide diversity of uses within each practice needs to be considered in order to provide a balanced and representative assessment of the sustainable use of wild species, as well as a suitable analysis of possible pathways to further sustainability. For example, a discussion of policy measures that may be effective at achieving sustainable fishing needs to consider the full spectrum of tools and institutions, but also the different types of fishing categories and operations, as well as the local context. What may work for large, industrial fisheries from regions with strong management capacity and resources tends not to be suitable for the management of small-scale artisanal fisheries, especially in resource and capacity-limited situations (FAO, 2020b; Hilborn *et al.*, 2020). This lack of singular solutions and the dependency of most suitable forms of governance and tools on the attributes of the social-ecological system involved and the operational scale and intensity of wild species use is common to all the practices.

The operational scales of extractive practices cover the full spectrum, ranging from manual gathering of a few grams of biomass to highly technological and capital-intensive harvesting methods that remove tons. While the total quantity extracted relative to the total population biomass or abundance (i.e., the harvest rate) has direct implications for the impact and sustainability of extraction, the operational scale of an extractive activity also has implications for the types of regulations and regulatory schemes that may be most effective to achieve sustainability (Kurien & Willmann, 2009; Parma *et al.*, 2006). For example, depending on the intensity of use, the population impact of a small-scale artisanal extraction is not necessarily lower than that of an industrial operation; however, the suitable means for keeping harvest rates within sustainable levels will likely be very different (see Table 6.5 in Chapter 6, section 6.4.4.5). Similarly, non-extractive uses include a wide range of operational scales which have different regulatory implications, from individual experiences of watching wild species for recreation and inspiration to the high-end tourist industry built around whale watching, diving or game watching. Especially at the large-scale end of the spectrum, non-extractive recreational uses supporting the tourist industry can have negative impacts on wild species and the ecosystems they inhabit if not properly conducted; hence the need for guidelines and regulations (e.g., Parsons & Brown, 2017; Tapper, 2006, see also Chapter 4).

When the complex social-ecological systems of wild species uses are managed to maintain and/or enhance nature's contributions to people while ensuring the productivity of the species (or population) used and the integrity and functioning of the ecosystems in which they occur are preserved to meet current and future human needs, sustainable use

is one possible outcome. However, outcomes may be highly heterogeneous across the different dimensions of the social-ecological system, and specific management interventions may be focused on strengthening sustainability of the resource system (e.g., reduce harvest rate to improve population status), the users (e.g., build users capacity) or the governance system (improve institutional arrangements) (Leslie *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, these complex interactive systems can be managed to produce wider ecosystem outcomes linked to sustainable use, beyond sustaining the wild species used and the direct benefits derived from them, such as to incentivise habitat and biodiversity conservation (Abensperg-Traun, 2009; Allen & Edwards, 1995) or to improve human well-being and achieve sustainable development goals (Mahapatra & Mitchell, 1997; Pullanikkatil & Shackleton, 2019).

1.1.2 Placing the assessment within the IPBES conceptual framework and nature's contributions to people

The IPBES conceptual framework provides a simplified model of the interactions between people and the natural world (Díaz, *et al.*, 2015a; Díaz *et al.*, 2018), which serves as a tool for assessing issues relevant to nature's contributions to people and good quality of life. Since its approval by the IPBES Plenary in 2013, the conceptual framework underpins all IPBES deliberations and provides a consistent structure and terminology to IPBES products across spatial scales, themes, and regions. The conceptual framework includes six primary interlinked elements that operate across different spatial and temporal scales:

- Nature;
- Nature's contributions to people;
- Anthropogenic assets;
- Institutions and governance systems and other indirect drivers of change;
- Direct drivers of change; and
- Good quality of life.

These elements have been conceived as broad, inclusive categories intended to be meaningful to a wide range of stakeholders while being flexible and amenable to interpretation as the conceptual framework is applied to particular topics of interest to the members and stakeholders. Sustainable use of wild species is a case in point. Previous IPBES assessments have quite reasonably treated "use" as one driver of change in natural systems, among many. In contrast, use of wild species is the

central focus of this assessment. The flexibility of the IPBES conceptual framework enables its application to the assessment of the sustainable use of wild species. In the section that follows, this assessment shows how sustainable use can be mapped onto the conceptual framework (Figure 1.2), highlighting some concepts that are particularly germane to this assessment.

For the core concepts in the framework, definitions here draw on those from Díaz *et al.*, 2015a. Elements of special importance to sustainable use of wild species are put forward, with the benefit of insights that emerged from a participatory process intended, among other things, to ensure that understandings of the conceptual framework elements would be meaningful and relevant to all stakeholders.

The current assessment engaged indigenous peoples and local communities following the IPBES approach to recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge

systems and seeks to include their perspective and insights for the sustainable use of wild species (see section 1.4). Through this process, participants suggested the phrase “people’s contributions to nature” would better capture the multiple ways humans engage with, maintain, and, to varying degrees, produce nature (IPBES, 2019b, 2019c). In proposing the language of people’s contributions to nature, participants in indigenous and local knowledge dialogues explicitly insisted on the importance of conceptual symmetry between nature’s contributions to people and an expanded understanding of what is taken into account as direct and indirect anthropogenic drivers. In particular, their worldviews and experience suggested a need to re-examine the notion of human impacts as acting upon a separate pre-existing nature (see 2.2.4). Workshop participants were concerned that a language of “drivers” alone could not easily include concepts, such as caring for, nurturing, or stewarding nature, as well as broader concepts such as responsibility and reciprocity relative to the complex interactions between the natural

Figure 1.2 The sustainable use of wild species in the IPBES conceptual framework.

The boxes and arrows of the central panel, delimited in grey, denote the elements of nature and society that are at the main focus of IPBES. In each box, the headlines in black are inclusive categories for stakeholders involved in IPBES and embrace the categories of science (in green) and equivalent categories according to other knowledge systems (in blue) (IPBES, 2019a). This assessment foregrounds wild species uses as anthropogenic drivers and notes that many indigenous and local knowledge systems view such uses through a lens of people’s contributions to nature. Modified from Díaz *et al.*, 2015b under license CC-BY 4.0.

world and human societies. The definitions below, as well as inclusive text added to the direct drivers box in **Figure 1.2** endeavor to honor this input while following the definitions, approved by the IPBES Plenary, for the main elements of the IPBES conceptual framework (IPBES, 2019a). The following text reproduces partially or in full these definitions and provides additional insights compatible with the IPBES commitment to understand elements of the framework in an inclusive manner in the context of the current assessment.

- **Nature** encompasses the nonhuman world, with particular emphasis on living organisms, their diversity, their interactions among themselves but also with their abiotic environment. The current assessment is particularly attentive to the abundance, distribution, and traits of wild species that are used by people as well as the entanglements of nature and society that those uses imply. The inclusivity of this element is manifest in the multiple ways nature can be understood and engaged. Within the framing of the natural sciences, for example, nature includes all dimensions of biodiversity, from the genes to the ecosystems, including species and communities and their associated ecological, evolutionary and biogeochemical processes. Within the framework of ecological economics, it includes disciplinarily specific categories such as biotic natural resources, natural capital and natural assets. In the context of other social sciences and humanities disciplines, as well as interdisciplinary environmental sciences, nature is referred to with categories such as natural heritage, living environment, or the nonhuman. Finally, within the framing of a wide range of knowledge systems grounded outside science, nature includes categories such as Mother Earth (shared by many indigenous peoples and local communities around the world), Pachamama (South American Andes), sēnluo'-wa'nxia'ng and tien-ti (East Asia), Country (Australia), fonua/vanua/whenua/ples (South Pacific Islands), Iwigara (northern Mexico), Ixofijmogen (southern Argentina and Chile), among many others (see Díaz *et al.*, 2015b for references). Across different knowledge systems, both scientific and non-scientific, the degree to which humans are considered part of nature varies considerably.
- **Nature's contributions to people** are all the contributions of nature to the quality of life of humans, as individuals, societies or humanity as a whole that emerge from the interactions of nature with anthropogenic assets, institutions, and governance. In particular, the use of wild species makes possible a wide range of direct and tangible contributions to people that include food, energy, medicine, materials, physical and psychological experiences, learning and inspiration, and identity. In some knowledge systems such contributions may be understood as, for example, "ecosystem goods and services," while in others they may better be seen as

"nature's gifts." Furthermore, nature's *contributions* to people have replaced nature's *benefits* to people (found in earlier versions of the conceptual framework) to not only accommodate the multiple ways nature's contributions to people are understood and enacted, but also to better reflect the fact that contributions may have detrimental or beneficial consequences for people's quality of life.

- **Good quality of life** is the achievement of a fulfilled human life. Visions, concepts and indicators of good quality of life are highly diverse, both in cultural roots and in geographical application. Approaches applied internationally can be based solely on the economic aspects of social systems (e.g., gross domestic product per capita), be more inclusive in the social factors considered (e.g., human development index, inclusive wealth) or holistic framings (e.g., living in harmony, gross national happiness index). Other more culturally specific and place-based approaches include Sumak Kawsay/ Buen vivir (Central Andes), teko porã (Paraguay), vida plena (Amazonian basin), or shizen kyosei shakai (Japan) (Díaz *et al.*, 2015b). Within the context of a wide range of good quality of life conceptualizations, wild species are vitally important as sources of food, energy, medicine and other materials; a current and potential source of livelihoods; and a key contributor to rich and meaningful cultural and spiritual lives. A society's quality of life and the vision of what constitutes a good quality of life strongly influence all other elements in the conceptual framework. For the purposes of this assessment, people's quality of life is regarded not just as an outcome of nature's contributions to people, but also as influencing direct anthropogenic drivers that impact and shape nature.
- **Direct drivers** refer to natural and anthropogenic factors that act directly on nature. Natural drivers are abiotic forces that have generally been regarded as beyond human control, such as disturbances caused by earthquakes or extreme climate events, although the concept of the anthropocene calls attention to the increasing degree to which human actions may influence these systems (see, for example, Steffen *et al.*, 2011, 2018). In contrast, direct anthropogenic drivers comprise factors that are under human control. This assessment focuses on the practices related to the use of wild species (i.e., fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices) as direct drivers (see Chapter 3). In scientific knowledge systems, direct anthropogenic drivers often are conceived as external factors that change or transform a pre-existing nature. In other knowledge systems, including much indigenous and local knowledge, humans are considered part of nature. Indeed, nature itself is co-produced through interactions between humans and nonhumans, with both playing an active role. Ideally, but far from always,

this process of co-production is characterized by mutual caring and responsibility. However, just as nature's contributions to people may be beneficial or adverse, people's contributions to nature can include positive and negative outcomes. For example, the age and sex classes targeted by some hunters may disrupt breeding success or increase population productivity. This perspective explicitly contains conceptual room for a range of actual and potential human "contributions" to nature and can facilitate identification of and support for existing sustainable uses of wild species.

➤ **Institutions and governance systems and other indirect drivers** include human actions and decisions that indirectly affect nature by altering and influencing human practices relating to the use of wild species. Along with good quality of life, they influence and mediate direct anthropogenic drivers that affect nature both positively and negatively. Indirect drivers include economic, demographic, institutional, technological and cultural processes (see Chapters 2, 4 and 5). Special attention is given, among indirect drivers, to the role of institutions and governance systems, including formal and customary systems of access to land and property rights as well as those emerging from indigenous and local knowledge systems (see Chapter 6). Indirect drivers include, for example, socially shared rules, legislative arrangements, international regimes such as agreements for the protection of endangered species, and economic policies. It is important to note that this assessment does not deal separately with direct and indirect drivers, which are dealt with collectively in Chapter 4. The reason for this approach is that sustainable use is an outcome of a system that includes nature, and the drivers acting on it, as well as the institutions and governance systems that act as drivers of uses and practices (as depicted in **Figure 1.1**). Sustainable use is therefore affected by multiple interacting drivers comprising both direct and indirect drivers.

➤ **Anthropogenic assets** refer to knowledge (including indigenous and local knowledge and technical or scientific knowledge), technology (both physical objects and procedures), labor, financial assets, and built infrastructure. These are closely tied to institutions, governance and other indirect drivers as indicated by the line linking them in the conceptual framework figure (**Figure 1.2**), which suggests that accumulated assets and systems of decision-making work together to influence and shape interactions between nature and human society. While such interactions clearly emerge as nature's contributions to people, they also are integral to those practices and uses that directly produce nature. Thus, anthropogenic assets may contribute as much to people's contribution to nature as they do to nature's contributions to people.

1.2 ASSESSING SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES: A ROADMAP TO THE CHAPTERS

The sustainable use assessment is a critical evaluation of the state of knowledge carried out under the principles of relevance, legitimacy and credibility. The sustainable use assessment has not undertaken new primary research, but analyzed, synthesized and critically evaluated available information and data previously published or otherwise made available in the public domain in a traceable way.

1.2.1 Overarching questions

The sustainable use assessment is structured according to ten overarching questions defined in the scoping report (annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1). They provide a framework for evaluating and integrating evidence from local to global levels, spanning past and future:

1. How can the sustainable use of wild species be appropriately conceptualized and operationalized? (Chapter 1 and Chapter 2)
2. What methods and tools exist for assessing, measuring and managing the sustainable use of wild species? (Chapter 2)
3. What are the positive and negative impacts of various uses of wild species and other direct drivers on nature and nature's contributions to people? (Chapter 3)
4. Who are likely to be the main beneficiaries of the sustainable use of wild species? (Chapter 3)
5. What are the drivers that affect the sustainability of the use of wild species, including systemic obstacles and perverse incentives preventing sustainable use? (Chapter 4)
6. What are the different scenarios related to the sustainable use of wild species? (Chapter 5)
7. What policy options and governance pathways relating to various scenarios of the use of wild species, including socioeconomic and ecological considerations, can lead to the achievement of sustainability of the use of wild species in the ecosystems they inhabit? (Chapter 5)
8. What policy responses and methods and tools for assessing, measuring and managing sustainable use of wild species have proved to be appropriate and effective, in which contexts and over what time

frames? To what extent can they be replicated in other contexts? (Chapter 6)

9. What gaps in data and knowledge regarding status, drivers, impacts, policy responses and policy support tools and methods need to be addressed in order to better understand and implement the variety of options and opportunities for enhancing conservation through the sustainable use of wild species? (All chapters)
10. What opportunities does the sustainable use of wild species offer with regard to alternative land uses (for example, replacing less sustainable land use activities)? (All chapters)

1.2.2 Outline of chapters

The assessment is organized into six chapters, comprising this introduction followed by five chapters that form the core of the assessment. The broad areas covered by the chapters are summarized below.

Chapter 1 provides the conceptual framework, organizing structure, terminology and definitions that apply to all chapters. It emphasizes the relationship to the IPBES conceptual framework and shows how this assessment both builds on and differs from other recent assessments of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

Chapter 2 focuses on the question of conceptualizing and operationalizing sustainable use. It provides a history and lays out the main features of diverse conceptualizations of sustainable use. It also identifies considerations that influence the ability to achieve sustainability, as well as methods and tools needed to assess and measure sustainable use of wild species.

Chapter 3 assesses the status and trends in the use of wild species and effects on their conservation. It examines what levels of use could be sustainable and when management is required in order for species to recover in relation to international instruments (Sustainable Development Goals, Convention on Biological Diversity, Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, etc.). The implications of use with regard to nature's contributions to people and good quality of life are also investigated in this chapter.

Chapter 4 provides an assessment of the drivers affecting sustainable use. It identifies the main drivers (environmental, political, social, economic, cultural, scientific and technological) that positively or negatively impact the sustainable use of wild species, including the effects of international agreements and commitments (e.g., Convention on Biological Diversity, Convention on

International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora).

Chapter 5 assesses scenarios and how future trajectories may be affected by different policies and approaches. It examines plausible futures for the use of wild species, using a range of scenarios. This chapter also addresses pathways to transformative change in sustainable use of wild species to achieve targets under the Sustainable Development Goals and the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Chapter 6 assesses the effectiveness of policy responses with regard to the sustainable use of wild species, including regulatory, economic, social and rights-based instruments, and best practices. It explores the enabling conditions for effective policy options, summarizes the lessons learned and suggests solutions for ensuring success of sustainable use of wild species.

1.3 SCOPE AND ORGANIZING STRUCTURE FOR ASSESSING THE SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES

The scoping document for the assessment of the sustainable use of wild species, as accepted by the IPBES Plenary, provides the broad framework for the work presented here. The main components outlined in the scoping report (annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1) have been interpreted and defined in the following ways for the purposes of this assessment.

- **Wild species** refers to populations of any species that have not been domesticated through multigenerational selection for particular traits, and which can survive independently of human intervention that may occur in any environment. This does not imply a complete absence of human management and recognizes various intermediate states between wild and domesticated (see section 1.3.2). For the sustainable use assessment, the scope mostly excludes feral and introduced populations although these may satisfy the general definition of wild and they may be included in some aspects of the assessment. The rationale for this definition and the scope of the assessment is provided in section 1.3.2.
- **Sustainable use** is an outcome of social-ecological systems that aim to maintain biodiversity and ecosystem functions in the long-term, while contributing to human well-being. It is a dynamic process as wild species, the ecosystems that support them, and the social systems within which uses occur, change over time and space.
- **Use of wild species** is interpreted in a narrow sense as applying only to the direct use of species through the practices of fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting, logging, and non-extractive practices. These practices are explained in greater detail in section 1.3.4. The rationale for this narrow focus is: (i) that it is consistent with the policy issues raised in the scoping report; (ii) past global, regional and thematic IPBES assessments have already assessed other ecosystem services and nature's contributions to people; and (iii) the concepts, principles and evidence relating to the direct use of wild species represent a significant issue that needs to be assessed in its own right.

This means that the interpretation of this assessment is aligned with the concept of nature's material contributions. The scope does not include the contribution of wild species to nature's regulating contributions (e.g., pollination, carbon sequestration) nor to contributions to people through indirect uses such as grazing for livestock. In the case of

non-extractive practices, it is often difficult to separate practices that are directly related to wild species (e.g., wildlife watching) from those that relate more generally to nature or wild spaces (e.g., sacred groves). The intention of the assessment of the sustainable use of wild species is to focus primarily on those practices that involve interactions with wild species. There are also emerging initiatives that explore financing mechanisms for conservation based on the existence values of iconic species. These are largely regarded as beyond the scope of the assessment but this assessment acknowledges that initiatives based on existence values may interact with other practices involving direct use. This is noted in later chapters although there is currently very little evidence available to assess their impact on other uses of wild species.

- **Extractive and non-extractive practices.** The scoping report outlined the need to consider consumptive and non-consumptive uses. The preferred terminology used in the sustainable use assessment is extractive and non-extractive practices. Extractive practices result in the temporary or permanent extraction of individuals or harvest of biomass, which may or may not result in the death of the individual organism (e.g., hunting of big horn sheep *versus* shearing and releasing of vicuña). Non-extractive practices do not involve extraction or removal of biomass (e.g., wildlife watching).

This section further refines the focus of the assessment and provides a consistent structure and terminology that is used throughout the assessment. The structure is intended to:

- Clarify what is included in the assessment;
- Achieve consistency and coherence among categories, terms and definitions throughout the assessment;
- Ensure adequate coverage across uses, species, biomes, and geopolitical regions;
- Maintain focus on sustainable uses, and;
- Present the document in a way that enables distillation of policy relevant findings and messages from the detailed analyses.

1.3.1 Defining sustainable use

The conceptualization of sustainable use of wild species in international policy can be traced at least back to the Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment in 1972. Principles 2, 3 and 4 arising from this conference are particularly relevant:

Principle 2: The natural resources of the earth, including the air, water, land, flora and fauna and especially representative samples of natural ecosystems, must be safeguarded for the benefit of present and future generations through careful planning or management, as appropriate.

Principle 3: The capacity of the earth to produce vital renewable resources must be maintained and, wherever practicable, restored or improved.

Principle 4: Man has a special responsibility to safeguard and wisely manage the heritage of wildlife and its habitat, which are now gravely imperilled by a combination of adverse factors. Nature conservation, including wildlife, must therefore receive importance in planning for economic development.

Likewise, the World Charter for Nature adopted by the United Nations in 1982 reaffirms that “man must acquire the knowledge necessary to maintain and enhance his ability to use natural resources in a manner which ensures the preservation of the species and ecosystems for the benefit of present and future generations.”

Sustainable use is a concept that is now widely applied in various sectors, including natural living resources (e.g., wild animals or wild plants), natural non-living resources (e.g., water, air and soil), and human products (e.g., agricultural products, pesticides, other goods) (Cooney, 2007). Using the term “sustainable use” in such different contexts leads to different meanings. The sustainable use assessment’s definition is restricted to the context of wild species (or wild living resources).

For the Convention on Biological Diversity since 1992, sustainable use is mostly defined according to the target resource (see **Figure 1.3**): “the use of the components of biodiversity in a way and at a rate that does not lead to the long-term decline of biological diversity, thereby maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of present and future generations”. As such, sustainable use is defined using primarily ecological criteria, but within a framework of human needs. Some other international organizations have adopted the CBD definition, but included further considerations in policy positions, e.g., the International Union for Conservation of Nature states that it is ‘committed to ensure that any use of wild species is equitable and ecologically sustainable’ (IUCN Resolution 2.29, 2000). Other formulations, e.g., the White Oak principles, include a clearly articulated social dimension as well: “a dynamic process toward which one strives in order to maintain biodiversity and enhance ecological and socio-economic services, recognizing that the greater the equity and degree of participation in governance, the greater the likelihood of achieving these objectives for present and future generations”. The sustainable use assessment’s definition

of sustainable use considers both the ecological and social dimensions and should be understood as applying to multiple aspects of human-ecological interactions around use (see below and **Figure 1.3**).

Indigenous and local knowledge offer additional perspectives on sustainable use. Many indigenous peoples regard humans and wild species as relatives, existing in relationships like those of the members of a family, in which each has an essential role to play (IPBES, 2019a, 2019b; Muir *et al.*, 2020). In this worldview, the social and ecological dimensions of the use of wild species are inseparable (Nadasdy, 2007; Polfus *et al.*, 2016; Robinson & Raven, 2019). To be sustainable, the use of wild species should ensure the well-being of both humans and other species (Sangha *et al.*, 2015). Seen through this lens, to choose between human well-being and that of wild species is both unethical and untenable.

In defining sustainable use, the following aspects, which are discussed thoroughly in Chapter 2, are critical to this assessment:

- Sustainable use is an outcome of social-ecological systems, in which nature’s contributions to people derived from extractive or non-extractive uses of wild species are managed to meet current human needs while maintaining or co-creating natural systems that promote the continued survival of the species being used and the ongoing provision of nature’s contributions to people. It is not, and cannot be, a static endpoint because the target species, the ecosystems that support them, and the social systems within which uses occur are dynamic and change over time and space. Consequently, the sustainability of use is an ongoing adaptive process, which may be depicted as follows: (i) assess status and trends in wild species under use, (ii) identify drivers of (un)sustainability, (iii) adapt uses and management (which may include, if necessary, stopping use for a period of time), (iv) re-assess after a given time interval and re-adapt use and management if needed.
- Sustainable use has a narrower and more specific meaning than sustainable development or sustainable management and these should not be used as synonyms. Sustainable development has a clear economic basis and can be seen as a quest to reconcile economic growth with social and ecological challenges and problems (often conceptualized through the three-pillars, social-economic-environmental, diagram, see Purvis *et al.* (2019)). Sustainable management also encompasses a broader array of actions related to the reduction of environmental, and social (including economic) impacts associated with any activity, not only use (Cooney, 2007).

- Sustainable use emerges from social-ecological systems that meet human needs without compromising ecosystem health. Sustainable use is thus not limited to anthropocentric considerations (i.e., the sustainability of the use for the benefit of people) or to ecological/environmental considerations (i.e., the conservation of the target resource from an ecosystem perspective). Rather, it encompasses both social and ecological considerations as well as the multiple aspects of their interactions.
- Human views on sustainable use are diverse, resulting from local, indigenous and scientific knowledge that should each be appreciated as relevant experiments in sustainable use from which people can learn.
- For practical purposes, especially for an assessment of this nature, the definition of sustainable use or what is assessed as being sustainable, needs to be precise enough that assessors can determine whether or not use is sustainable.
- Sustainability should therefore be clearly defined through a set of specific targets or indicators in the social and ecological domains. Ideally, this set of indicators should be developed jointly by all the actors of the social-ecological system.
- Animal welfare and animal protection are important considerations receiving increasing social, ethical and legal consideration worldwide (see the Global

Figure 1 3 **Different conceptions of the sustainable use of wild species, illustrating the increasing degree of complexity associated with them as well as the availability of methods and indicators to evaluate sustainable use.**

Most international organizations consider only the “single species” dimension when evaluating sustainable use and managing human uses of wild species, others have introduced the “multi-species” dimension, while some seek to use an ecosystem approach (for example, taking into account the impacts on the functioning of ecosystems and habitats). Economic and social dimensions are more rarely taken into account by international organizations. The indigenous and local knowledge approach is often more integrative and considers the socio-economic and ecological dimensions as inseparable. The availability of indicators and methods by dimensions is approximated by the color level and is inversely proportional to the complexity or the number of dimensions, illustrating the more comprehensive development of indicators at the species level and the general lack of indicators for higher level ecological dimensions or social dimensions.

Sustainable Development Report 2019 by the Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General). Animal welfare is increasingly incorporated into the concepts of sustainable use of wild species, but it was not identified in the scoping report for the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species (annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1). Therefore, animal welfare was not addressed in this assessment.

1.3.2 Unpacking the definition of wild species

The scoping report for the sustainable use assessment (annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1) identified the need for a general definition of wild species that could be applied in different assessments and across conventions. Despite the widespread reference to specimens from the wild, or wild species, in both the academic literature and policy documents (see Chapter 2), there is no universally accepted definition and the majority of papers do not refer to a clear definition for wild species.

The definition of wild species adopted for the sustainable use assessment (1.3) clarifies two aspects that are relevant to this assessment. First, the definition focuses attention on wild populations and not on the species as an entirety. This is because populations of the same species can span a continuum from those that do not experience any human intervention to being fully domesticated. The naming of domesticated taxa in relation to their wild progenitors, linked to debates about whether domesticated forms should be recognized as distinct species, has been extensively discussed in terms of both the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (Gentry *et al.*, 2004) and the International Code of Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi and Plants (Spooner *et al.*, 2003). As noted by Gentry *et al.* (2004) for animals, some domesticated forms have scientific names which are distinct from those applied to their wild ancestors, but the majority of wild progenitor species and their domestic derivatives are considered to be the same species and this is also true for plants, algae and fungi. Some examples include *Coffea arabica* for wild and domesticated coffee (Wiersum *et al.*, 2008), *Salmo salar* for wild and cultured Atlantic Salmon (Teletchea & Fontaine, 2014), *Agaricus bisporus* (button mushrooms) and *Struthio camelus* for wild and domesticated forms of ostrich (Spinu *et al.*, 1999). For precision, the assessment should refer consistently to wild populations of particular species but this is often not practical and any reference to wild species should be read as an abbreviation for wild populations of a species.

The second clarification relates to the term 'wild' which, although commonly used, is open to different interpretations and needs to be more precisely defined in this assessment.

A common starting point is to distinguish wild forms from domesticated ones. For example, the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List defines wildlife as living things that are neither human nor domesticated (IUCN, 2021a). The Convention on Biological Diversity does not define wild but, instead, defines domesticated to mean species in which the evolutionary process has been influenced to meet human needs. By implication, wild populations are those that do not fit the definition of domesticated.

It is *well established* in both scientific and indigenous and local knowledge systems that a binary separation between 'wild' and 'domesticated' populations does not exist. Scientific analyses of use systems for plants (Muir *et al.*, 2020), terrestrial animals (Child *et al.*, 2019) and aquatic organisms (Bell *et al.*, 2006; Hilborn & Hilborn, 2019) recognize intermediate stages between wild and domesticated. At one extreme, wild populations are identified as those that retain the capacity to evolve autonomously under conditions where genetic diversity enables natural selection to produce adaptation (Redford *et al.*, 2011; Mallon and Stanley Price, 2013). Along the continuum towards domestication, populations may be managed by people, to a greater or lesser extent, to increase accessibility and productivity or to promote the forms with traits most sought after by the people concerned. In this transition, the population may increasingly depend on human intervention to survive one or more life history stage, till finally at the other extreme the population is selectively bred over multiple generations to serve human needs (Vigne, 2011). Typically, the path to domestication is characterized by intensification of the relationship between forms derived from wild progenitors and human societies (Vigne, 2011), is accompanied by changes in phenotype and has been defined as a distinctive coevolutionary, mutualistic relationship between domesticator and domesticate (Zeder, 2015).

A commonly accepted definition for wild animals, accepted by the Collaborative Partnership on Sustainable Wildlife Management (IUFRO, 2018), applies to animals that have a phenotype unaffected by human selection and can live independently of direct human supervision or control. There may be a continuum from truly wild, where animal populations are self-sustaining and exist without human intervention, through various levels of confinement and intervention (such as feeding), to domestication. Similarly, wild products from plants have been described as those derived from untended wild resources (Muir *et al.*, 2020). Domestication is not just a state of being, but a process that results in genetic adaptation to the extent that animals will breed readily in captivity, their owner has some control over reproduction, and it results in detectable differences between the domestic populations and their wild progenitors.

The scientific literature and indigenous and local knowledge literature are also quite clear that there is no single dimensional point that can be used to distinguish wild from not wild (Child *et al.*, 2019; Cruz-Garcia, 2017; Redford *et al.*, 2011). Biologists have proposed various ways to categorise wild populations which may vary depending on the purpose of the categorization. These include a five-node system for evaluating self-sustaining sub-populations (Redford *et al.*, 2011) focusing on reintroducing captive animals into the wild; a timebound system, also focusing on reintroductions, where populations that can survive longer than ten years in the absence of human intervention would be wild (Hayward *et al.*, 2015; IUCN Standards and Petitions Committee, 2019); a composite score based on the existence of certain management interventions (Child *et al.*, 2019); and a five-stages process from wild to domesticated for fish (Teletchea & Fontaine, 2014). Indigenous peoples and local communities have developed their own classification systems based on different criteria to define wildness. For example, some communities in the Amazon categorize 'wild' plants into six different groups based on how they are used and managed (Cruz-Garcia, 2017) and indigenous peoples and local communities in Peru distinguish between domesticated and two types of wild animals on the basis of their interactions with humans and domesticated animals.

The relationship between wild, introduced, feral, domesticated and captive can be mapped using three axes linked to human interventions (Figure 1.4). These are (i) the extent of human intervention in reproduction and survival; (ii) multigenerational selection for traits by people to suit human needs; and (iii) the extent to which populations are dispersed through human intervention. In interpreting the scope of this assessment, the emphasis is on those populations that are situated on the lower end of these three axes, i.e., those that still occur in their natural range, have not undergone multigenerational selection for traits and can survive without human intervention. Nevertheless, some of the intermediate conditions along the continuum from wild to domesticated can be important for any assessment of sustainable use and are included in the assessment when appropriate (see Box 1.1). The terminology for the intermediate states between wild and domesticated varies between taxa (e.g., animals and plants), practices (e.g., fishing or gathering) and purpose (e.g., conservation versus use) (Bell *et al.*, 2006; Child *et al.*, 2019; Lorenzen *et al.*, 2000; Muir *et al.*, 2020). For the purposes of this assessment, the typology of wild, wild managed, farmed and domesticated provides a sufficient framework for analysis (see Table 1.1).

Figure 1.4 A diagrammatic presentation of the multiple dimensions that may be used to define the continuum between 'wild' and domesticated.

The bubbles represent various examples of states that can exist between the extremes of wild populations occurring freely within their original habitat and those that are fully domesticated. This is not a complete list of possible states.

Table 1.1 **Categorisation of intermediate states between wild and domesticated, comprising wild, wild-managed, farmed and domesticated populations and showing how these intermediate states correspond to similar typologies used in other contexts.**

Wild	Wild managed	Farmed	Domesticated	Application & references
Wild capture fisheries	Enhanced capture fisheries (limited technological interventions in the life cycle of aquatic resources)	Aquaculture	Domesticated	Fishing (Bell <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Lorenzen <i>et al.</i> , 2000)
Wild (untended wild plant populations)	Semi-wild algae, fungi and plants (biological resources that are subject to some form of human intervention to increase productivity)	Cultivated, Artificially propagated, farmed	Domesticated	Mostly for algae, fungi and plants (Muir <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Wild	Wild managed (animal populations where some level of supplementary feeding, watering or veterinary care is provided to increase productivity)	Captive bred, ranched (animal populations where space, supplementary feeding, watering, breeding and veterinary care are managed to increase productivity)	Domesticated	Terrestrial animal populations (Child <i>et al.</i> , 2019)

Scope of the sustainable use assessment in relation to wild species

The scope of the sustainable use assessment is guided by the requirements of the scoping report (annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1). A primary concern for the public and policy makers is that unsustainable use of wild populations is leading to their decline and collapse (1.1). To address this aspect of the assessment, the focus should be consistent with populations that are included in the indicators used to measure decline and collapse. The International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species and other similar metrics use criteria to evaluate the ability of species to survive as self-sustaining entities, mostly within their original distribution range (e.g., Traill *et al.*, 2007). This would include their capacity to evolve autonomously under conditions where genetic diversity enables natural selection to produce adaptation (Redford *et al.*, 2011; Mallon and Stanley Price, 2013). Hence the emphasis on populations that meet these criteria.

A second factor for policymakers is the link between the use of wild species and the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the United Nations (see also section 1.6). In this context, the use of wild species may present different opportunities and risks for development when compared to the use of completely domesticated species. As a result, the definition applied in this assessment should differentiate between species that have been selected for traits that suit human needs, and where production is under human control, versus wild species that are self-sustaining and express traits that have evolved in response to environmental pressures. Some indigenous

peoples and local communities' terminology refers to wild species as 'gifts' and this reflects the essence of what is meant perhaps more effectively than scientific definitions.

The sustainable use assessment does not focus specifically on feral populations, or populations that have been introduced by humans to outside their native range (Figure 1.4). These species may be included in aspects of the assessment, for example where invasive species offer alternative resources for use, but they are not the primary focus of this assessment. Many non-domesticated species have been introduced to outside their original distribution range through human-mediated dispersal. Their release into novel habitats can result in significant changes to these habitats and such biological invasions have been identified as one of the main drivers of decline in biodiversity in certain ecosystems (IPBES, 2019a). Depending on societal values, scientific interpretation and the perceived utility of alien and invasive species, they have been considered as a natural part of emerging novel ecosystems (wild) (e.g., Hoffmann & Courchamp, 2016), they may be considered as part of the wild population under special circumstances (e.g., IUCN Standards and Petitions Committee, 2019) or they can be regarded as an unintended negative consequence of human activities and therefore need to be managed and controlled (IPBES 2019). There are numerous instances of the use of introduced species, including by indigenous peoples and local communities (Bhattacharyya & Larson, 2014; Tebboth *et al.*, 2020) but this is not a primary focus of this assessment since the main policy concern relates to the status of species within their original distribution range.

Similarly, populations that were introduced as domesticates, but then escaped and established in the wild as feral populations also fulfil some of the criteria relating to wild populations (Figure 1.4). These, too, are frequently used by people either to replace or complement use of other species, but they are not a main focus for this assessment.

In adopting this approach, the sustainable use assessment acknowledges the rich body of work dealing with the biological, social and philosophical complexities of defining the meaning of wild (Haraway, 2003; Latour, 1993, 2004; Maris, 2018; Palmer, 2011). The IPBES conceptual framework (Díaz *et al.*, 2015a) emphasizes the unity of nature and humanity, which recognizes the ongoing interaction between environmental and social processes. This is consistent with a conceptualization of wild which is not in opposition to that belonging to the human or cultural sphere. The concept of wild has received much scrutiny in the humanities and social sciences during the past decades, notably in relation to the issues of wilderness and the social construction of nature (Comberti *et al.*, 2015; Nelson & Callicott, 2008; Neumann, 1998). Although 'wild' and 'wilderness' should not be confused, they are related in the way that nature is conceptualized. Early criticisms of the separation of people and nature in the conceptual and regulatory framework of areas designated as wilderness came from indigenous peoples and local communities and the issue has been problematized and debated since at least the 1960s. One of the key issues in this debate is the consequences of the western notion of wilderness as a pristine, idealized and distant nature devoid of human activity that, by extension, discounts the value of the environment in which people live and fails to provide an environmental ethic that will tell as much about using nature as not using it (Cronon, 1996; Fletcher *et al.*, 2021; Glacken, 1976; Leopold, 1949).

The concept of the Anthropocene has further problematized the idea of nature as a pure and timeless place characterized by the absence of humans (Lorimer, 2015). There is growing recognition that in the current era, few environments are unaffected by human activity (Cookson, 2011), and even conservation efforts might transform the characteristics, composition and distribution of biodiversity (Stokland, 2020). However, co-production of nature by humans and non-humans did not commence with the Anthropocene. Humans have played active roles in shaping life on land for millennia (Ellis *et al.*, 2021). Scholars of biocultural diversity have noted strong correlations between cultural diversity and biological diversity globally (Gorenflo *et al.*, 2012; IPBES, 2018e; Maffi, 2005; Pretty *et al.*, 2009; Sterling *et al.*, 2017). Their work indicates that many ecosystems that are regarded as natural or wild and evincing little human influence are, in fact, the result of long-term interactions between indigenous peoples and local communities and their biophysical environments

(Levis *et al.*, 2017). Likewise, the species composition in these areas reflects varying intensities of management by indigenous peoples and local communities. For example, Peacock and Turner (2000) and Anderson (2013) note that indigenous peoples of northwestern North America managed the land on which they lived at scales from the individual plant (e.g., through practices such as pruning and weeding) to the landscape (see also, Deur & Turner, 2005; N. J. Turner, 2014). The area managed by indigenous peoples coincides with approximately 40% of terrestrial conserved areas, including those with high biodiversity (Garnett *et al.*, 2018). In many cases, loss of indigenous and local knowledge and practices results in reduced species population size and distribution (see, for example, the case of camas bulbs *Camassia* spp., (N. J. Turner & Turner, 2008)). This perspective suggests that the defining characteristics of 'wild' cannot be represented as a simple dichotomy between management and no management by humans and that excluding all human management from the concept of wild species is problematic (Lepofsky & Caldwell, 2013; Mathews & Turner, 2017; McGregor *et al.*, 2003; Mueller-Dombois, 2007; Mueller-Dombois & Wirawan, 2005; N. Turner *et al.*, 2013; Posey, 1985; Zeder, 2015). Rather, wild is located on a continuum somewhere between instances in which humans have no current or remembered historical contact with a location and the species in it and intensive interventions with landscapes and the species in them (Ford, 1985).

Indigenous peoples and local communities' world views and concepts of nature offer an additional perspective on definitions of wild in relationship to animals, fungi and plants. Indigenous peoples and local communities' definitions of wild species arise from worldviews that emphasize material and spiritual relationships between humans and other beings (IPBES, 2019c). While the defining characteristics of wild vary between cultures (where the concept exists), commonalities and differences between them offer insights into how indigenous peoples and local communities' definitions of wild species are intertwined with notions of sustainable use (see section 1.4.1). Some cultures do not identify a sharp boundary between wild and domesticated species. However, many indigenous peoples and local communities recognize distinct types of animals and plants based on the level of care they need from humans to reproduce and thrive. This distinction may be further expressed in terms of the realm or power with which a species is associated or the degree of freedom it can exercise. For example, the Mixtec peoples of Mexico conceptualize wild as something that grows by itself, without need for external help. In Russia and other eastern European countries, wild species often are described as gifts of the forest while Native Hawaiian, many Andean, and other cultures regard wild species as belonging to or associated with gods. Thus, relationships between humans and these species also entail relationships with these other

Box 1 Case study on challenges with operationalizing the concept of wild species.

In South Africa, a dramatic surge in the conversion of land use from livestock to wild species ranches resulted in an increase of wild species numbers from 0.5 million head of game in the 1960s to 16-20 million in 2014 (Carruthers, 2008; Taylor *et al.*, 2015). As a result, Southern Africa is the only region on the African continent where mammal populations, on aggregate, are not in decline (Craigie *et al.*, 2010), and private landowners have played a major role in reversing the trend. This rewilding has been viewed as a successful model for sustainable use of wild species (Cromsigt *et al.*, 2018), but the process has also highlighted the need to avoid a shifting baseline for what is meant by “wildness” (Child *et al.*, 2016).

Management interventions on wild species ranches may include artificially increasing the abundance of a population through supplementary resources, veterinary care or controlling which individuals breed with each other to enhance an economically valuable trait. This negates natural selection and may hinder adaptation to changing environments. Thus, population abundance does not necessarily equate to an ecologically functioning population if those animals are disconnected from the

surrounding landscape and cut off from evolutionary trajectories. Metrics based on numbers alone may mask a gradual shifting baseline in what it means to successfully conserve wild species (Redford *et al.*, 2011).

Child *et al.* (2019) produced a framework to quantify the wildness of a managed population by mapping management thresholds between wildness ‘nodes’, using attributes such as available space, food and water provision, breeding freedom, and disease resistance, which have been demonstrated to influence the ecological and evolutionary attributes of a species. They found that population abundance did not correlate with wildness but that the area available to a population was a strong predictor of wildness whereas the frequency of supplementary feeding, density of artificial water-points and the degree of veterinary care provided were predictors of shifts away from wildness.

One of the key policy challenges is how to unlock economic opportunities associated with wild species without creating perverse incentives that may affect the wildness of managed populations (Turpie & Letley, 2018; Wanger *et al.*, 2017).

entities, with all the significance and consequences that this may imply (IPBES, 2019c, 2019b). These concepts are examined in greater detail in section 2.2.4.

Philosophers have identified three constituents of wildness (or wild), namely locational, dispositional and constitutional (Palmer, 2011). These constituents provide a qualitative framework for assessing wildness. Locational wildness refers to existence in an area free of human management; dispositional wildness relates to the state and behaviour of the organism; whereas constitutional wildness refers to an organism that has not been domesticated.

1.3.3 Impacts of nature conceptualizations on the uses of wild species

The traditional “western” view of human-nature relationship tends to separate nature (what exists by itself) from culture (what has been produced by humans). This human-nature dualism is deeply rooted in people’s perception of the functioning of the biosphere as well as in their common language. It is pervasive and may be found in most national and international agreements and policies related to the conservation of biodiversity or the regulation of use of wild species. IPBES is not an exception in this regard. The IPBES conceptual framework presented above (see section 1.2) indeed defines nature as the entity that “encompasses the nonhuman world, with particular emphasis on living organisms, their diversity, their interactions among

themselves but also with their abiotic environment”. This influence can be subtle, such as in the definition of natural environment given by the Convention for Biological Diversity: “the natural environment comprises all living and non-living things that occur naturally on Earth. In its purest sense, it is thus an environment that is not the result of human activity or intervention” (CBD, 2008).

Traces of this human-nature dualism can already be found in Antiquity, notably among the Greek philosophers of the 7th and 6th centuries BC (Bouchard, 2020) and in the Bible as well, especially Genesis (chapter 1, 27-30):

(27) “God created mankind in his own image; in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.”

(28) “God blessed them and said to them, “Be fruitful and increase in number; fill the Earth and subdue it. Rule over the fish in the sea and the birds in the sky and over every living creature that moves on the ground.”

(29) “I give you every seed-bearing plant on the face of the whole Earth and every tree that has fruit with seed in it. They will be yours for food.”

(30) “And to all the beasts of the Earth and all the birds in the sky and all the creatures that move along the ground, everything that has the breath of life in it, I give every green plant for food.” And it was so.

In Europe and the Mediterranean area, this human-nature dualism continued to develop during the Middle Ages with Christianity, according to which all creation proceeds from God, including humans who are the center of this creation and have the divine mission to control it (see Genesis citations above). God has thus bestowed strong power on humans and it is God's intention that humanity multiplies itself, spreads out over the Earth, exerting dominion over all of creation (Glacken, 1976). If humanity is clearly distinct from and positioned over the other living organisms in a hierarchy of creation, various passages from the old and new testaments also attest to the love and pleasure of humans for nature as a manifestation of God's work (Glacken, 1976).

This dichotomy between humankind and nature has permeated western thought over two millennia and is evidenced in the arts, philosophy and science. In 1637, Descartes in the *Discours de la Méthode* went a step further in this conceptualization of human-nature relationship through his famous quote: “to know the laws which govern nature to become masters and owners of nature”. For Descartes, this expressed a dream of liberating humanity from the grip of magical explanations of nature through technique. Descartes wanted to demystify nature and understand its laws, so that humans can have control over their environment and no longer simply endure it. In this conceptualization, nature is, however, seen as an object that humans can or must take advantage of. Descartes' philosophy was later seen as the manifesto of human excess, of an anthropocentric conceptualization based on the sciences and techniques, which will be disputed by several philosophers of the 20th century, among which Plumwood (2002).

This mechanistic view of nature, in which the role of humans is to discover the underlying laws of nature, has pervaded the development of modern science since the 17th century and greatly contributed to its extraordinary success in e.g., astronomy, biology, chemistry, medicine or physics. Following a series of epistemological debates in Germany and North America at the end of the 19th century, this human-nature dualism finally led to the distinction of two broad scientific categories: the natural sciences and the cultural sciences, or simply the humanities, which still strongly structures the scientific fields of today (Bouchard, 2020).

Darwin's ground-breaking publication on the origins of species (1859) was the first scientific study (with Wallace's study published in 1855) challenging the divine creation of humans and so, the foundation of this separation between humankind and nature. This publication is considered to be the founding text of the scientific theory of evolution, according to which all current living species, including humans, have evolved from extinct ancestral species, by

means of natural selection. The theory of evolution has been refined considerably since Darwin. It has in particular been enhanced by the contributions of genetics and it is today the unifying paradigm in life sciences (see e.g., Richerson *et al.*, 2021; Scheiner & Mindell, 2020 for a recent review on the scientific theory of evolution).

The theory of evolution challenged the Judeo-Christian view of the human-nature relationship in western culture, as, from an evolutionary perspective, humankind belongs to the long chain of living organisms on Earth and is thus part of it. This new paradigm has also fed other scientific fields, such as ecology, which defines the ecosystem as the largest functional unit that includes both living organisms and the abiotic environment, with each influencing the properties of the other, and the two being necessary to maintain life as it exists on Earth (Odum, 1953). There is a general consensus within the scientific community that humans are a part of ecosystems, as reflected in the World Charter for Nature adopted by the United Nations (1982), which declares that “mankind is part of nature and life depends on the uninterrupted functioning of natural systems which ensure the supply of energy and nutrients” and that “civilization is rooted in nature, which has shaped human culture and influenced all artistic and scientific achievement”.

As demonstrated in this assessment and other works (e.g., through the “One Health” approach, see IPBES, 2020b), humans are indeed intimately connected to their environment and to the other living micro- and macro-organisms on which they rely for their food, their health, their shelter and the energy necessary for their activities. Humans are also strongly impacted by various processes linked to the functioning of ecosystems, and more generally of the whole planet, such as droughts, floods, storms, fires, desertification and zoonotic diseases. While most of these phenomena are intrinsic to the functioning of ecosystems, they have become more intense as a result of the degradation of the integrity and functioning of most terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems due to human activities (Crutzen & Stoermer, 2000; IPBES, 2019a).

This conceptualization which assumes that humanity is part of nature, however still remains marginal in western culture, even while it echoes the much older concept of “Mother Nature” or “Mother Earth” for which nature and humankind are indivisible, such as in many indigenous cultures (see section 1.4) and Taoism (Ma *et al.*, 2021). It also echoes American philosophers from the 19th and early 20th centuries, such as Emerson, Thoreau and, especially, Leopold. In his famous book *A Sand County Almanac* (1949), Leopold presents the basis of an ecological ethics, which can be summed up as an ethics of the earth which should not prohibit the use of its resources, but affirms the right of the living organisms of the earth to continue to exist in a natural state. The human thus

passes from the role of conqueror of nature, inherited from Judeo-Christian theology, to that of member and citizen of the earth community. This conception leads to respect for other members and the community as a whole and reduces anthropocentrism, without sanctifying a static nature, which is, in fact, constantly evolving. The human-nature relationship therefore implies a continuous coordination of the interests of the different members of the earth community.

In contrast, human-nature dualism has fostered the illusion that humanity could exist apart from the rest of nature, to such an extent that humans' use of nature *ad libitum* ultimately led to major environmental crises (Ma *et al.*, 2021; Plumwood, 2002). An observation that is shared by the scientific community, which has pointed out the direct responsibility of human activity in climate change (IPCC, 2019b, 2019a), biodiversity decline (IPBES, 2019a) and the modification of the main planetary natural processes, ushering in a new geological era known as the Anthropocene (Zalasiewicz *et al.*, 2018).

Human-nature dualism also engendered the notion of wilderness (or pristine nature). This notion is mostly a western cultural construction, notably arising from Europeans and North Americans during the 18th and 19th centuries. "Wilderness" idealizes nature as a sublime, primitive and virginal natural space where the human has no place, except as a contemplative traveller (see section 1.3.2, Cronon, 1996). Such cultural construction of wilderness is problematic in general and particularly for the purpose of this assessment because (i) it ignores past and current scientific evidence according to which nearly three quarters of terrestrial nature (including landscapes and biodiversity) have been shaped over several millennia by diverse histories of human habitation and use by indigenous peoples and local communities (Ellis *et al.*, 2021), (ii) it tends to sanctify the notion of pristine landscapes in conservation practices and policies, which in turn denies the agency, access rights and knowledge of indigenous peoples and local communities in the maintenance of their territories and traditional uses of wild species (Fletcher *et al.*, 2021), and (iii) it does not allow the possibility for humanity to find an ethical and sustainable place in nature (Cronon, 1996).

Considering humans as part of nature (as in the earth community of Leopold) reframes the relationship of humans with other living organisms and the abiotic environment and could make this relationship more respectful and more sustainable, as demonstrated by indigenous peoples and local communities' traditional practices and uses (Barthel *et al.*, 2013). Indigenous peoples and local communities indeed offer a diversity of alternative worldviews, human-nature relationships, cosmologies and philosophies, which, in general, include a lack of division between nature and culture and respectful

relations of kinship and reciprocity between humans and non-humans (Brondízio *et al.*, 2021). Such considerations have large implications for this assessment, as sustainable use of wild species would imply a transformative change in people's conceptualization of nature, shifting from still deeply rooted western human-nature dualism to a more systemic view, in which humanity is a member and one among many citizens of nature.

1.3.4 Organizing structure

As set out in Section 1.1.2, the core factors to consider in the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species are the components of nature that are affected (wild species), the practices associated with the use of wild species, and their end uses, i.e., nature's contributions to people. These take place within particular cultures, economies, governance systems, and technological developments. To ensure consistency across the assessment, and to facilitate the distillation of key findings, a common organizing structure has been used throughout and is summarized in **Figure 1.5**. Categories within each system for the use of wild species are presented in diagram form below with narrative explanations in the subsequent paragraphs. They are not presented as a hierarchy but rather as interacting elements of the social-ecological systems of the use of wild species.

It is worth noting that many categories are not mutually exclusive, a point essential to understanding wild species, their uses, and benefits to people. For example, many species occur in multiple ecosystems over the course of their lifecycle. Wild anadromous fish, such as salmonids are a case in point, as their lifecycle includes time spent in both freshwater and marine environments. Similarly, a single species may support multiple uses. For example, wild rice (*Zizania palustris* L.) is both a food and a ceremonial resource (see **Box 1.2**), while the white gum tree or gum Arabic (*Acacia senegal*) is widely used as a food additive and in the pharmaceutical industry for medical purposes (Catarino *et al.*, 2019). Also, a single species may be the focus of more than one practice, sometimes in the same location. In several African countries, large terrestrial animals are subject to non-extractive practices (wildlife watching) and trophy hunting (terrestrial animal harvesting).

The wild species panel

Species Groups. The sustainable use assessment used the following higher level categories of four species groups: (i) aquatic animals, (ii) plants (excluding trees), fungi and algae, (iii) trees and (iv) terrestrial animals because there are differences in the status of use and practices of these groups as well as in the policy options for managing their uses (**Figure 1.6**).

Figure 1.5 Common organizing structure of the sustainable use assessment.

Biomes, ecoregions and ecosystems. Each population of a given group of species lives in a given ecosystem or ecoregion of a given biome. To avoid a level of detail that will obscure identification of key points for policy makers, some information may be analysed according to ecological biomes (terrestrial, marine and freshwater). These have been defined at a fairly high level using the typology adopted by the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, which is more aggregated than most biological typologies. Elements that are relevant to this assessment are:

- Freshwater biomes are classified as: (i) wetlands and (ii) inland waters.
- Marine biomes are classified as: (i) coastal systems, (ii) shelf systems and (iii) open and deep seas.
- Terrestrial biomes are classified as: (i) grasslands-steppes-savannas, (ii) forests (iii) deserts and (iv) mountains. Where appropriate, ‘anthropogenic biomes’ are also included, namely urban areas and cultivated areas.

The practices panel

For the purposes of this assessment, use of wild species involves both the practices associated with harvest or other direct interactions with wild species, as well as the end purpose for which the species is used (e.g., for food or medicine). Although the sustainable use of wild species has been discussed in academic and policy documents for more than 40 years, there is no single or accepted set of definitions for the practices associated with the use of wild species. Here the practices are defined to show how they have been applied in the assessment.

The scoping report directs the assessment to consider consumptive and non-consumptive activities, or practices (Annex IV to decision IPBES-5/1, 2018). These terms have been in use for a long time, referring mostly to the use of wild animals (FAO, 1995). However, they can be confusing due to various possible interpretations of consumption, particularly when one is looking for a term that can be used for both plants and animals. Following the FAO, this assessment uses the alternative terms of extractive (consumptive) versus non-extractive (non-consumptive) practices. Extractive practices involve temporary or permanent removal of organisms, part of them or materials derived from them from their habitat, and may result in

mortality of the individual to be used (e.g., hunting or whole plant harvest), but does not necessarily do so (e.g., limited collection of plant propagules or wild honey, or shearing and releasing of vicuña). Non-extractive use does not directly entail removal of materials from wild populations (e.g., wildlife photography) but may result in inadvertent mortality as a result of, for example, disease transmission at artificial feeders.

For clarity, the sustainable use assessment then mapped different types and modalities of practices against the main taxonomic groups (Figure 1.6). It started first by categorising the nature of different practices based on whether they were extractive or not, then on additional characteristics of the practices, such as whether it involved the entire organism or only a part or product of the organism. This mapping exercise showed that certain terms in common use were typically associated with a set of practices mostly aimed at one higher taxonomic group,

e.g., fishing incorporates several practices relating to the extractive use of aquatic animals. In order to align with common understandings, the sustainable use assessment employed the terms fishing, gathering, and logging to cover the practices set out in Figure 1.6. The one deviation from this approach was for hunting. Whereas fishing is understood as almost any practice relating to the harvest of aquatic animals, and can even be applied to harvest of animals in captivity, hunting generally applies only to activities that result in the death of the target animals and is not commonly applied when there is no direct, intentional mortality, again, as in the example of vicuña shearing and release. As a result, terrestrial animal harvesting has been adopted as the generic term for the extractive practice focused on terrestrial animals (see below for a full definition).

Extractive practices. Extractive practices are broken down into the five following categories.

PRACTICE		ALGAE, FUNGI AND PLANTS	TREES	TERRESTRIAL ANIMALS	AQUATIC ANIMALS
EXTRACTIVE PRACTICES	Harvest entire organism with mortality	GATHERING <i>(e.g., whole plant harvest)</i>	LOGGING <i>(e.g., sawn wood)</i>	HUNTING <i>(e.g., subsistence hunting)</i>	FISHING <i>(e.g., commercial fisheries)</i>
	Harvest part of organism with mortality	GATHERING <i>(e.g., excessive root harvest)</i>	LOGGING <i>(e.g., excessive branch removal)</i>	HUNTING <i>(e.g., amphibian's secretions)</i>	FISHING <i>(e.g., shark finning, fish roe)</i>
	Harvest entire organism with without intended mortality	GATHERING <i>(e.g., landscaping materials)</i>	LOGGING <i>(e.g., landscaping materials)</i>	"NON-LETHAL" TERRESTRIAL ANIMAL HARVESTING <i>(e.g., pet trade, green hunting)</i>	"NON-LETHAL" FISHING <i>(e.g., aquarium fish, catch and release)</i>
	Harvest parts or products of organism without mortality	GATHERING <i>(e.g., leaves, nectar, resin, latex, berries)</i>	LOGGING <i>(e.g., coppicing)</i> GATHERING <i>(e.g., leaves, fruits, bark)</i>	"NON-LETHAL" TERRESTRIAL ANIMAL HARVESTING <i>(e.g., wild honey, vicuña fiber, bird eggs)</i>	"NON-LETHAL" FISHING <i>(e.g., horseshoe crab's blood)</i>
NON-EXTRACTIVE PRACTICES	Direct interaction with organism	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., touching, smelling plants)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., touching trees)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., bird feeding)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., shark feeding)</i>
	No direct interaction with organism	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., photography, wild species watching)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., photography, wild species watching)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., photography, wild species watching)</i>	OBSERVING <i>(e.g., diving and scuba without contact)</i>

Figure 1.6 Wild species versus different types of practices.

Note: The definitions of practices are not intended to reflect on their impact. That is the role of the assessments that follow in Chapters 2-6. As a result, the definitions of non-lethal fishing and terrestrial animal harvesting should not be read as implying that these practices necessarily have less impact than lethal practices.

- **Fishing.** Fishing is defined as the removal from their habitats of aquatic animals (vertebrates and invertebrates) that spend their full life cycle in water (e.g., fish, some marine mammals, shellfish, shrimps, squids, corals). Fishing most often results in the death of the aquatic animal, but it may not in some cases. To reflect both situations, fishing has been sub-divided into a lethal and “non-lethal” category. Lethal fishing is defined as the general and more usual meaning of fishing that leads to the killing of the animal, such as in traditional commercial fisheries (Figure 1.6). “Non-lethal” fishing is defined as the temporary or permanent capture of live animals from their habitat without intended mortality, such as in the aquarium fish trade or catch and release (Figure 1.6). However, unintended mortality may occur in “non-lethal” fishing and the term “non-lethal” is therefore put in quotes. The killing of species that spend part of their life cycle in terrestrial environments (e.g., walrus, sea turtles) is encompassed by the definition of hunting.
- **Gathering.** Gathering is defined as the removal of terrestrial and aquatic algae, fungi, and plants (other than trees) or parts thereof from their habitats (Figure 1.6). Gathering may, but often does not, result in the death of the organism. Gathering includes whole plant harvest and removal of above and below ground plant parts, as well as the fruiting bodies of macrofungi. It also includes removal of non-woody portions of trees (e.g., leaves, propagules, and bark). Where removal of propagules or death of an individual plant occurs (e.g., whole plant and root removal) effects on population sustainability are contingent upon factors including timing, frequency, and intensity of harvest (Figure 1.6). The harvest of wood and woody parts of trees is encompassed by the definition of logging.
- **Logging.** Logging is defined as the removal of whole trees or woody parts of trees from their habitat (Figure 1.6). Logging generally results in the death of the tree, but also includes cases in which it may not, such as coppicing. Logging occurs in forests that may be classified as primary, naturally regenerating, planted, and plantation (see below “other definitions”). This assessment does not address logging from plantation forests (except as it has bearing on the practice in the other forest types). Harvest of non-woody parts of trees (e.g., leaves, propagules and bark) are here defined as gathering.

- **Terrestrial animal harvesting.** Terrestrial animal harvesting is defined as the removal from their habitat of animals (vertebrates and invertebrates) that spend some or all of their life cycle in terrestrial environments. As with fishing, terrestrial animal harvesting often results in the death of the animal, but it may not in some cases. To reflect both situations, terrestrial animal harvesting has been sub-divided into a lethal and “non-lethal” category. Hunting is defined as terrestrial animal harvesting that leads to the killing of the animal, such as in trophy hunting or subsistence hunting (Figure 1.6). “Non-lethal” terrestrial animal harvesting is defined as the temporary or permanent capture of live animals from their habitat without intended mortality, such as for the pet trade, falconry, or green hunting (Figure 1.6). Non-lethal harvest of animals also includes removal of parts or products of animals that do not lead to the mortality of the host, such as vicuña fibre or wild honey. Unintended mortality may however occur in this category and the term “non-lethal” is therefore put in quotes.

- **Non-extractive practices.** Non-extractive practices are defined as practices based on the observation of wild species in a way that does not involve the harvest or removal of any part of the organism (Figure 1.6). Observation can include some interaction with the wild species, such as the activities of wildlife and whale watching or no interaction with the wild species, such as remote photography.

Each of these practices and uses take place at multiple spatial and temporal scales, from the very large (hundreds to thousands of hectares) to the very small (single organisms) and from the long-term (over centuries) to the very short-term (days or weeks). They may involve technologies ranging from heavy machinery to manual tools or no tools. Likewise, they take place in economic contexts from supplying global commodity markets to satisfying household subsistence needs (see below).

The uses panel

For the purposes of this assessment, the uses of wild species have been divided into eight categories, which are not mutually exclusive:

- **Ceremony and ritual expression** are defined as the uses of wild species in collective or individual spiritual observances, including those that may be valued for their role in maintaining cultural identity.
- **Decorative and aesthetic** are defined as the uses of wild species in order to produce handicrafts and objects of adornment, beauty, and/or entertainment.

- **Energy** is defined as the use of wild species to provide energy for heat, cooking, water sterilization, etc.
- **Food and feed** are defined as the uses of wild species to provide food for humans and domestic animals.
- **Learning and education** are defined as uses of wild species in which the production of knowledge is a primary value.
- **Materials and construction** are defined as the uses of wild species to create shelter for humans or animals and to produce objects such as cordage.
- **Medicine and hygiene** are defined as the uses of wild species to heal illnesses or promote health and well-being of humans and domestic animals.
- **Recreation** is defined as the uses of wild species in which enjoyment is considered a primary value.
- **Other** is defined as the uses of wild species that are not encompassed by the categories above, such as companionship (i.e., pets).

Other definitions related to scale in fishing and logging

While the main components outlined in the scoping document have been defined in the previous sub-sections, it is also important to define key components of some practices (e.g., small-scale fisheries) as they are used in this assessment.

Small-scale versus industrial fisheries. Following the definition from the FAO (2001), the assessment considers that a fishery is a unit determined by an authority or other entity that is engaged in raising and/or harvesting fish. This unit is defined in terms of the people involved, species or type of fish, area of water or seabed, method of fishing, class of boats and purpose of the activities (see Glossary). International bodies often refer to specific fisheries categories, especially to small-scale fisheries. However, this category remains an unresolved (often fuzzy) category, which still generates a large debate within the scientific community, as well as within international bodies.

In its report of the Second Session of the Working Party on Small-scale Fisheries (2004), the Advisory Committee on Fisheries Research of the FAO concluded that there

Table 1 2 **Matrix table used for the characterization of fisheries based on multiple attributes along gradients between small-scale (lower scores) to large-scale (higher scores).**

(from Basurto *et al.*, 2017) m= meters, km = kilometers, GT = Gigaton, hp = horse power

Score	0	1	2	3
Size of fishing vessel (or equivalent range for fixed gears)	No vessel	< 12 m, < 10 GT	< 24 m, <50 GT	> 24 m, > 50 GT
Motorization	No engine	Outboard engine	Inboard engine < 400hp	Inboard > 400hp
Mechanization	No mechanization	Small power winch/ hauler powered off engine	Independently powered gear deployment/ hauling	Fully mechanized gear deployment and hauling
Refrigeration/ storage on board	No storage	Ice box	Ice hold	Refrigerated hold
Labor/crew	Individual and/ or family members	Cooperative group	< 2 paid crew	> 2 paid crew
Fishing unit/ ownership	Owner/ operator	Leased arrangement	Owner	Corporate business
Time commitment	Part-time/ occasional	Full-time, but seasonal	Part-time all year	Full-time
Day trip/ multiday	< 6 hours	Day trip	< 4 days	> 4 days
Fishing grounds/ zone/ distance from shore	< 100 m from shoreline	< 3 km from shoreline	< 20 km	> 20 km from shoreline
Disposal of catch	Household consumption/ barter	Local direct sale	Sale to traders	Onboard processing and/ or delivery to processors
Utilization of catch, value added/ preservation	For direct human consumption	Chilled	Frozen	Frozen/ chilled for factory processing (for human consumption or fishmeal)
Integration into economy and/ or management system	Informal, not integrated (no fees)	Integrated (registered, untaxed)	Formal, integrated (licensed, landing fees)	Formal, integrated (licensed, taxed)

was no globally agreed definition of small-scale fisheries and its Small Scale Fisheries Guidelines did not prescribe a standard definition of small-scale fisheries, but underlined the need to ascertain which activities and operators are considered small-scale.

The report of the FAO on “Improving our knowledge on small-scale fisheries: data needs and methodologies” (Basurto *et al.*, 2017) proposed a matrix approach for the characterization of diverse small-scale fisheries. This matrix (see **Table 1.2**) allows a value to be assigned to each characteristic which can then be aggregated into an overall score, allowing for clearer disaggregation between large-scale fisheries and small-scale fisheries, which is based on the following characteristics:

The World Ocean Assessment (see Ferreira *et al.*, 2016) gives the following definition: “Capture fisheries and aquaculture operate at many geographical scales, and vary in how they use marine resources for food production. Here, “small-scale” refers to operations that are generally low capital investment but high labour activities, relatively low production, and often family or community-based with a part of the catch being consumed by the producers (Béné *et al.*, 2007; Garcia *et al.*, 2008). Large-scale operations require significantly more capital equipment and expenditure, are more highly mechanized and their businesses are more vertically integrated, with generally global market access rather than focused on local consumption. These descriptions are at the ends of a spectrum continuum of scales with enormous variation in between.”

The IPBES Global Assessment provides a definition for small scale fisheries only, based on the portal of the FAO (2018a), as follows: “Small-scale or non-industrial fisheries: Traditional fishing performed by family units rather than commercial units, using a relatively small amount of capital and energy, and carrying out short fishing trips close to coasts and mainly for local consumption”.

According to the above reports and the fact that the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species needs common guidelines on the different types of fisheries to ensure consistency across chapters, it is acknowledged that capture fisheries operate at many geographical scales and vary in how they use marine resources for food production. The main fisheries categories are further distinguished as:

➤ **Small-scale fisheries** generally present (some of) the following characteristics: (i) low capital investment, (ii) high labour activities often family or community-based, (iii) no vessel or small size vessel (< 12m and < 10 GT), (iv) relatively low production, which is household consumed or locally and directly sold and (v) operating close to the shoreline on a single day basis.

➤ **Industrial fisheries** generally present (some of) the following characteristics: (i) high capital equipment and expenditure, (ii) high level of mechanization, motorization and onboard processing, (iii) large vessel size (> 24 m and > 50 GT), (iv) based on a more vertically integrated business, with generally global market access, (v) operating offshore on a multi-day basis.

Organization and scale of logging. The organization of logging can be understood through the intersection of forest types, forest management objectives and forest ownership, including governance structures and institutions. Logging occurs in forests that may be characterized along a continuum of intensities of human intervention anchored at the one end by primary forests and at the other by plantation forests. Following the terms and definitions laid out in the Global Forest Resource Assessment 2020 by the FAO, the sustainable use assessment understands primary forests to be “naturally regenerated forest of native tree species, where there are no clearly visible indications of human activities and the ecological processes are not significantly disturbed” (FAO, 2020a), while plantation forests consist of areas in which the trees are deliberately planted (whether native or introduced species) often with the intent to produce wood, fiber or energy on a short rotation interval and do not resemble naturally regenerating forests at maturity (FAO, 2020a). Although boundaries between them can be fuzzy, intermediate levels of human manipulation of forests include naturally regenerating forests (i.e., composed in their majority, but not necessarily exclusively, of native and/or introduced tree species) and planted forests, which are dominated by trees that have been deliberately planted as saplings and/or seeds (FAO, 2020a). Broadly speaking, levels of labor and/or capital investment required to establish these forest types correspond with the intensity of human intervention. That is, such investments are lowest for primary forests and greatest for plantation forests.

Logging occurs in forests that are managed for one primary objective or for multiple uses, with the volume of biomass removal ranging from coppice forestry, in which living trees remain on the landscape (Fabbio, 2016; Unrau *et al.*, 2018), to even-aged management systems (i.e., clear cutting), with all trees removed from an area (Savilaakso *et al.*, 2021). Timber is most obviously harvested to obtain wood and fiber for use as energy and construction materials (FAO & UNEP, 2020), but also is used in the production of decorative, aesthetic and ceremonial or ritual objects (Diamond & Emery, 2011; Frey *et al.*, 2019; Johnson *et al.*, 2021). Some logging also may occur on forest lands for which the primary management objective is protection of soil and water, conservation of biodiversity or provision of social benefits such as education and recreation (FAO, 2020a).

Forest ownership is the right to “use, control, transfer, or otherwise benefit from...the trees growing on land

classified as forest” (FAO, 2020a) and may be separate from ownership of the land on which those trees are growing. Forest ownership types include: (i) local, tribal and indigenous communities, (ii) private and (iii) public entities (FAO, 2020a). Group ownership and management for group benefit are a shared characteristics of local, tribal and indigenous community forests. However, there is great variation in the governance structures and institutions through which they are established and managed. Private forest ownerships include individuals, businesses, and institutions with profit or non-profit aims. Approximately 22% of global forest area is in private forest ownership (FAO, 2020a), which may range in size from a few hectares to 2,000 or more hectares. An estimated 73% of global forest area is owned by public entities (e.g., the State, administrative arms of the State and parastatal entities) (FAO, 2020a) but logging on these lands may be carried out by local, tribal and indigenous communities or private entities through forest concessions (see, for example, FAO & EFI, 2018).

As with fishing, there is no easy crosswalk between forest type, management objective and ownership in which logging occurs. This assessment examines them as distinct and interacting aspects that influence the sustainability of this practice.

1.3.5 Use of indicators

Indicators that measure various elements of sustainable use are widely employed by a range of organizations and agencies from the local to the international level. As such, indicators illustrate and account for particular criteria of sustainable use that may be relevant to individual sectors (e.g., forestry or fisheries), habitats (e.g., particular marine or boreal ecosystems), or socio-environmental contexts (e.g., indigenous peoples and local communities’ uses of wild species). Indicators may be quantitative, semi quantitative or qualitative. They are fundamental to monitoring the status of a wild species use at a particular place and time and they may be relevant to and allow comparison across a range of temporal and spatial scales. As such, indicators are key components to the operationalization of sustainable use concepts as well as of broader principles of sustainable use, inclusive of concerns for equity and social justice (see section 1.3.2). Finally, insofar as the enactment of sustainable use is closely related to the implementation and institutionalization of indicators, indicators also have the potential to powerfully format environmental as well as equity and justice outcomes.

Chapter 2 traces the development of the sustainable use concept relative to wild species and how it came to be flexible and context-specific in its application. It also reviews the operationalization of sustainable use in various wild species cases and the role of methods and

metrics in implementation. In these cases, assessment and measurement rely on the use of indicators that align with case- and context-specific criteria which, themselves, are meant to reflect broader sustainable use concepts and principles. While the chain of translation from sustainable use principle to case-specific indicator will vary from one practice and context to the next, the use of often standardized and replicable indicators opens the door to meaningful comparisons over time within and across contexts (e.g., change in wild species population or habitat area), and it has the potential to foreground key drivers of change relevant across cases (e.g., demand or substitutable products). Finally, because indicators work well to capture change over time in sustainable use elements, they effectively support this assessment’s contention that sustainable use be understood more as a process and direction than a particular stage or state.

The detailed review of the relationship between indicators, criteria, and key elements of sustainable use undertaken in Chapter 2 points to how indicators are useful not only to gauge the status or trajectory of sustainable use but also to make clear what elements of sustainable use are most valued (or not) in any particular context or sector assessment. Conversely, indicator choice has the potential to shape sustainable use concepts themselves as they become institutionalized through investments in particular survey protocols, standardized data streams, and hegemonic analytical methods. In addition to influencing sustainable use concepts, indicators have the potential to affect policy development. For example, the review in Chapter 2 makes clear that more weight is given to environmental factors than socio-economic factors in the development of indicator methodologies, thereby creating the conditions for policy development that does not (and cannot) effectively incorporate socio-economic concerns relative to the sustainable use of wild species.

1.3.6 Confidence framework

A qualitative method of communicating the level of uncertainty and confidence in a key finding or statement using accessible and agreed upon terms and language has been essential to communicate assessment findings to decision-makers. The evaluation of confidence of assessment findings in the sustainable use assessment is based on the experience of previous IPBES assessments, which in turn benefited from other international and intergovernmental assessment processes, such as the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment and those of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

The sustainable use assessment followed the schematics and criteria presented in **Figure 1.7** to guide authors in the process of assessing and communicating the degree

of uncertainty, or confidence, related to key findings. This four-box confidence framework developed for IPBES assessments and their key findings are based on level of agreement of experts using their judgment (y-axis) in combination with the quantity and quality of evidence assessed (x-axis). The evidence includes publications, data, theory, models and information. Further details of the approach are documented in Section 2.2.6 of the IPBES guide on the production of assessments. The core version of the guide is available at: https://ipbes.net/sites/default/files/180719_ipbes_assessment_guide_report_hi-res.pdf.

The synthetic terms used to describe the evidence are:

- **Well established:** comprehensive meta-analysis or other synthesis or multiple independent studies that agree;
- **Established but incomplete:** general agreement although only a limited number of studies exist; no comprehensive synthesis and/or the studies that exist address the question imprecisely;
- **Unresolved:** multiple independent studies exist but conclusions do not agree;
- **Inconclusive:** limited evidence, recognizing major knowledge gaps.

Following other IPBES assessments, the sustainable use assessment does not use a likelihood scale or probabilistic certainty scale.

The synthesis of this large volume of evidence is challenging and complex and relies strongly on authors' expertise and joint deliberations, including authors from multiple disciplinary backgrounds and knowledgeable of issues related to other knowledge systems, particularly indigenous peoples and local communities. These confidence terms inform and communicate to decision-makers what the assessment author teams have high confidence in as well as what requires further investigation to allow decision makers to make informed decisions.

One of this assessment's findings is that sustainable use is highly complex to measure (see discussion in Section 1.3.1 above) and that it can only be defined with clarity *ex post*, as suggested in Cooney (2007). The findings of Chapters 3 to 6 highlight which patterns could lead to sustainable use of wild species in all the known cases that were documented and assessed as part of this work, and under which conditions sustainable use as an outcome could vary. Any *well established* or *established but incomplete* finding would need to be thought through when it leads to action on the ground. This assessment provides tools to do such measures, and model possible outcomes in terms of environmental and social benefits and provides a wide range of criteria to take into account, depending on the biome, species or type of practice or of use to be evaluated at the local or national level. Any conclusion of the sustainability of a specific use (see Chapter 3) would need to be regularly reassessed in light of the changing conditions affecting each driver (see Chapters 4 and 5), including how well policy and management are responsive to those changes (see Chapter 6).

1.4 INCORPORATING MULTIPLE KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS: A SYSTEMATIC AND MULTI-FACETED APPROACH

Incorporating multiple knowledge systems provides a more complete picture of the characteristics of sustainable uses of wild species than would be achieved through any single source. In particular, this assessment takes a systematic and multifaceted approach to integrate knowledge grounded in science and indigenous and local knowledge systems. Science is produced and interpreted through the preferred lenses and methods of diverse biophysical and social science disciplines. Among the strengths of a multidisciplinary approach such as that employed here is that it provides policy-relevant information at scales from the genetic to the landscape, the individual and household to the national and multilateral. Science, however, is not exhaustive: many of the thousands of wild species in use have yet to be the subject of detailed scientific inquiry. The same is true for the multifarious contexts of those uses (see Chapter 3).

The term “western science” is in wide use in scholarly work on diverse knowledge systems (Díaz *et al.*, 2015a), especially those that focus on indigenous and local knowledge. In this context, this assessment understands “western science” as defined in Díaz *et al.* (2015a, p.14); “as a broad term to refer to knowledge typically generated in universities, research institutions and private firms following paradigms and methods typically associated with the ‘scientific method’ consolidated in Post-Renaissance Europe on the basis of wider and more ancient roots. It is typically transmitted through scientific journals and scholarly books. Some of its central tenets are observer independence, replicable findings, systematic skepticism, and transparent research methodologies with standard units and categories.” While recognizing and embracing the importance of understanding the context within which all knowledge is produced, the assessment of the sustainable use of wild species refers to scientific knowledge without qualifying it.

The use of wild species is central to the livelihoods and identities of many indigenous peoples and local communities. Many indigenous peoples and local communities have extensive knowledge of the wild species they use, as well as the ecosystems in which these occur. Often referred to as indigenous and local knowledge, it both results from and informs a long experience in managing the social and ecological aspects of the use of wild species for long-term sustainability. Indeed, a strong case can be made that much of the biodiversity people

value, including the abundance and distribution of many species regarded as wild, are the result of indigenous peoples and local communities’ practices interacting with other-than-human nature over time periods extending from millennia to centuries (Ellis *et al.*, 2021; Garnett *et al.*, 2018; Levis *et al.*, 2017). There are, however, examples in which indigenous peoples and local communities’ uses of wild species have proven unsustainable over time and increasing pressures on indigenous peoples and local communities’ lands, livelihoods, and cultures place indigenous and local knowledge and associated practices at risk (IPBES, 2019a, 2019b and sections 4.2.1, 4.2.3, 4.2.5 in Chapter 4). Thus, incorporation of indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities’ perspectives and experience is essential to achieving both the social and ecological goals of sustainable use of wild species. In the context of the implementation of the IPBES approach to recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge, those perspectives are integrated throughout the assessment in support of national and international laws and principles, as well as important sources of knowledge and approaches to sustainable uses of wild species for all peoples, while endeavoring to respect the principle of free, prior and informed consent (FAO, 2016).

The sustainable use assessment has taken a multi-faceted approach to integrate indigenous and local knowledge throughout, following methodological guidance for recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge in IPBES (IPBES, 2020a). It included work with indigenous peoples and local communities’ organizations and international bodies representing or working closely with indigenous peoples and local communities. Direct input to the assessment by indigenous and local knowledge holders and experts was invited through a call for contributions distributed to indigenous peoples and local communities’ organizations throughout the world, as well as three dialogue workshops held at key moments in the assessment process. The call for contributions (distributed in June 2020) invited indigenous peoples and local communities and academics who work with indigenous peoples and local communities to submit community reports, academic papers, case studies, videos, songs and artworks related to the use of wild species by indigenous peoples and local communities, as well as recommendations of individuals, communities, organizations and networks that could collaborate in the development of the assessment. Workshops brought together indigenous peoples and local communities and experts of the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species for two days of engagement with assessment content, with results captured in publicly available reports (IPBES, 2019b, 2019a, 2021b). The first two workshops were conducted in person in the second and fourth quarters of 2019. As a result of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, the final workshop was realized through a series of online sessions in May 2021.

The remainder of this section develops core definitions and conceptualizations of indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities in relationship to the use of wild species. While recognizing their rich global diversity, indigenous peoples and local communities' uses of wild species and the indigenous and local knowledge that arises from and supports them share many characteristics. This assessment emphasizes approaches to safeguard continued capacity of indigenous peoples and local communities to engage in sustainable use of wild species and how active, respectful engagement with indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities will enhance national and international policy on sustainable use of wild species at large. Supporting sustainable use and management of wild species by indigenous peoples and local communities and applying lessons from them more broadly are complementary goals. Realizing them will require understanding the common characteristics of indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities' sustainable uses of wild species across the globe, as well as the nature and significance of their expression in particular places, times, and cultures.

1.4.1 Defining and conceptualizing indigenous peoples and local communities and indigenous and local knowledge in relationship to use of wild species

Methodological guidance for recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge in IPBES (IPBES, 2021a) provides foundational definitions for inclusion of indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities' perspectives and experiences in the assessment.

Indigenous and local knowledge

The term "indigenous and local knowledge" is understood to connote:

"dynamic bodies of integrated, holistic, social and ecological knowledge, practices and beliefs pertaining to the relationship of living beings, including people, with one another and with their environments" (IPBES, 2020a).

Indigenous and local knowledge systems are grounded in specific places, worldviews, beliefs, daily practices, and social relations that arise from and inform formal and informal indigenous and local governance, spiritual, and educational institutions. As a consequence, there is no singular body of indigenous and local knowledge. Rather,

multiple knowledge have grown out of diverse global ancestries, territories, and cultures. This is not unlike the diverse knowledge bases of scientific disciplines. Likewise, knowledge is not homogeneously distributed across members of a given culture and may be differentiated based on social characteristics such as specialization, kinship, gender, and age.

Importantly for this assessment, indigenous and local knowledge is dynamic. It "continuously evolves through the interaction between experiences, innovations, languages, and non-local knowledge" and, in many cases, is "empirically tested, applied, contested and validated" (IPBES, 2020a). Depth of understanding and adaptation to specific locations is a central strength of indigenous and local knowledge. This highlights both opportunities and challenges for a global assessment such as the present assessment by providing examples of how knowledge and management systems can be adapted to support sustainable use of wild species in particular places, while underscoring the need for careful attention to both the contexts within which knowledge is developed and how it translates into other locations (see section 1.4.3).

Indigenous peoples and local communities

The term "indigenous peoples and local communities" is widely used by international organizations and conventions to refer to individuals and groups who self-identify as indigenous or as members of distinct local communities. The IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species adopts this terminology, with particular emphasis on those who "maintain an inter-generational historical connection to place and nature through livelihoods, cultural identity, languages, worldviews, institutions, and ecological knowledge" (IPBES, 2020a). It notes that "recognition of an individual or group as indigenous is not necessarily synonymous with the group or individual holding indigenous knowledge about the environment" (IPBES, 2020a). That is, indigenous identity does not necessarily confer indigenous and local knowledge. Indeed, factors such as loss of indigenous and local language speakers imperils indigenous and local knowledge. Efforts to revitalize language and culture, including aspects related to sustainable use of wild species, have been initiated by indigenous peoples and local communities worldwide (McCarty *et al.*, 2019).

This assessment uses the term "local communities" to refer to non-indigenous communities with historical linkages to places and "livelihoods characterized by long-term relationships with the natural environment, often over generations" (IPBES, 2020). Such communities are characterized by distinctive approaches to management of the wild species they use. This management is grounded in place-based and hybrid environmental knowledge,

often governed by both customary and formal institutions. Many local communities also have perceptions of the relationships between humans, wild species, and the environment that are grounded in traditional values and beliefs that differ from those of the dominant culture. As is evident from this definition, local communities frequently have characteristics similar to those of indigenous peoples and some groups may self-identify as indigenous but are not formally recognized as such by their national governments. Further, such local communities often rely on informal tenure arrangements to access the lands, waters, and species on which they rely. Lack of formal rights and recognition mean that their continued ability to engage in customary use of wild species can be precarious and that their local knowledge is often discounted or ignored in policy processes (IPBES, 2019b; Mattalia *et al.*, 2018, 2020).

Indigenous peoples and local communities' definitions of wild species

As noted in section 1.3.2, definitions of wild tend to be 'purpose built'. Among the purposes of definitions of wild encoded in indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities' practices are the current and long-term viability of tightly interwoven cultures, identities, and livelihoods. Indeed, some wild species are so central to the well-being of indigenous peoples and local communities that they have been termed "cultural keystone species" (Garibaldi & Turner, 2004, see **Box 1.2**). Definitions of wild may also be said to reflect fundamental understandings of the differences and relationships between humans and other entities that inhabit the world (see section 2.2.4).

There are remarkable commonalities, as well as divergences, in understandings of wild species by indigenous peoples

Box 1.2 Cultural keystone species: wild rice.

Wild rice (*Zizania palustris*) is a cultural keystone species, providing physical, spiritual and cultural sustenance for many indigenous peoples in the Great Lakes region of North America (Matson *et al.*, 2021). Remarkable for its high protein and micronutrient profile, when processed correctly this aquatic grain can be stored for long periods of time (GLIFWC, n.d.), especially important properties in a region characterized by severe winters and short growing seasons. The significance of wild rice to the identities of indigenous peoples in the region

can be seen in nomenclatures and traditions. The name of the Menominee Indian Tribe of Wisconsin (United States) means "wild rice people" (Whyte *et al.*, 2018). When the Anishinaabe peoples migrated from the Atlantic Coast and northeast of North America, oral tradition instructed that they should move westward until they arrived at "the place where food grows on water". Wild rice remains a healthy staple in the diets of indigenous peoples in the Great Lakes region and is an important part of many feasts and ceremonies (GLIFWC, n.d.).

Harvesting wild rice, a cultural keystone species for indigenous peoples in the Great Lakes region of North America.

Photo credit: CO Rasmussen/GLIFWC

and local communities around the world (see section 2.2.4; IPBES, 2019a, 2019b). Among some indigenous peoples and local communities, to differentiate between wild animals, fungi, and plants and domesticates would be to imply a separation between humans and the natural world; an understanding; that carries with it potentially problematic implications such as failure to recognize human beings' responsibilities and capacity to be good stewards and citizens of the natural world. Other indigenous peoples and local communities do recognize a distinction between wild and domesticated species. Although the way this difference is described differs from group to group, common aspects include notions that wild species do not need human help, do not belong to people, are gifts, and/or come directly from or belong to deities or other entities, specific to each cosmology.

Identification, rather than separation, between humans and wild species is a focal point of nearly all indigenous peoples and local communities' understandings. Wild species and humans are relatives in many indigenous belief systems. This relationship is literal, not figurative, with all the responsibilities and possibilities for mutual care and support this entails (IPBES, 2019c). Further, far from being antithetical to the definition of wild, a responsibility to steward or care for species and places is regarded by many, if not most, indigenous peoples and local communities as fundamental to the existence and well-being of humans and other-than-humans (see **Box 1.3**).

Indigenous and local knowledge, indigenous peoples and local communities and sustainable use of wild species

As the definition of indigenous and local knowledge above suggests, indigenous peoples and local communities' ways of knowing wild species include careful observation over time, often including intergenerational transmission of these observations, material practices (i.e., fishing, gathering, hunting, and logging), and spiritual practices, including ceremony and ritual (Emery *et al.*, 2014; Kimmerer, 2000). Much of indigenous peoples and local communities' knowledge of species and how to use them respectfully and sustainably are recorded in myths, stories, songs,

and rituals (see section 2.2.4; IPBES, 2019a). Languages also encode information about the characteristics of wild species and human relationships with them (Terralingua, 2014). The knowledge systems indigenous peoples and local communities draw on to guide their uses of wild species may incorporate both scientific data and indigenous and local knowledge as complementary sources of information (see **Box 1.4**). As with scientific knowledge, indigenous and local knowledge and hybrid knowledge are dynamic, incorporating and adapting to new information as it becomes available. Indigenous and local knowledge often includes strategies for monitoring the status of wild species and their habitats as a means to adapt practices to changing conditions and ensure ongoing sustainable use (see Chapters 2 and 4).

Box 1.4 Communities around Mafungautsi State Forest embarked on a joint resource monitoring exercise with the Forest Commission of Zimbabwe, an arm of government responsible for managing all forest resources in the country. The communities took the lead in monitoring aspects of the forests that were of interest to them such as broom grass, honey and timber. Subsequent to the monitoring initiative, there was more sustainable use of the resources under observation, more equitable sharing of the resources and improved incomes and revenue to the resource harvesters and the state respectively (Mutimukuru *et al.*, 2007).

For indigenous peoples and local communities, a key measure of the sustainability of the use of wild species is whether it contributes to the long-term health and good quality of life of people, the species being used, and, in many cases, creation (or nature) as a whole. Often, this is expressed in terms of maintaining good relationships or living in balance and harmony with nature. Sustainable use and relationships between people and nature are often mediated by customary rules and norms, which have some broad similarities across many communities (IPBES, 2019b). Respect is often a guiding principle. For example, hunters should try not to cause non-lethal injuries to animals in order to minimize suffering and avoid waste of the life being taken (Reo & Whyte, 2012). Destroying mushrooms or plants 'just for fun' is unacceptable. Some form of reciprocity is

Box 1.3 Conceptualization of the sustainable use of wild species by Andean cultures.

Andean culture emphasizes the unity of nature, including humans, deities, wild and domesticated animals and plants, and land. The appropriate relationship between all these elements of nature is one of mutual love, respect, and responsibility. What could be translated as wild (*salqa*) are strongly associated with spiritual beings, which protect and control them, as well as higher, colder places where agriculture is not practiced. However,

humans and deities, wild and domesticated species all exist in relationships of mutual care, nurturing, and communication. Humans tend wild species and land when these are understood to request or need it, following the appropriate rituals and petitions to deities. This is understood to be necessary to the well-being of all elements of nature.

Box 1.4 Communities around Mafungautsi State Forest.

Communities around Mafungautsi State Forest embarked on a joint resource monitoring exercise with the Forest Commission of Zimbabwe, an arm of government responsible for managing all forest resources in the country. The communities took the lead in monitoring aspects of the forests that were of interest

to them such as broom grass, honey and timber. Subsequent to the monitoring initiative, there was more sustainable use of the resources under observation, more equitable sharing of the resources and improved incomes and revenue to the resource harvesters and the state respectively (Mutimukuru *et al.*, 2007).

frequently prescribed. Specifically, when people take a wild animal, mushroom, or plant they should acknowledge it as a gift. Some indigenous peoples and local communities' norms require that something be offered in return, such as a bit of a special plant, song, and/or prayer. Common norms prescribing when and how much of a wild species may be taken include limiting amounts to what is needed for immediate use by family or community, without any waste. Sharing is regarded as essential, assuring that enough is left for other people, as well as other species. Active tending or care for individual organisms, populations, and landscapes is also a strong norm for many indigenous peoples and local communities globally (Anderson, 2013; Peacock & Turner, 2000).

A suite of strategies is commonly employed to teach, regulate, and enforce these norms (see **Box 1.5**).

Challenges and opportunities for indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples and local communities' sustainable use practices

Indigenous peoples and local communities face many challenges to retaining indigenous and local knowledge and maintaining the practices that have provided for sustainable

use of wild species over time. These include both social and environmental forces (see Chapter 4; **Figure 1.8**). At the same time, a global surge of interest in cultural revival, emphasis on rights-based approaches to conservation, including community-based natural resources management (see section 6.4.4), and emerging national and international efforts to maintain and revitalize indigenous and local cultures offer hope for the continuity of indigenous and local knowledge and ongoing sustainability of the use of wild species by indigenous peoples and local communities.

The COVID-19 pandemic illustrates the forces that can threaten indigenous peoples and local communities' capacity to engage in sustainable use of wild species. At the same time, it demonstrates the value of those practices and the knowledge on which it is based for survival in the face of crisis, as well as the potential value of dialogue between indigenous and local knowledge and other sources of knowledge for imagining a better way forward for all. Specifically, emerging evidence on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on indigenous peoples and local communities and the role of the use of wild species in their responses to it indicate that those communities with robust indigenous and local knowledge have been remarkably resilient in the face of the crisis, especially where customary

Box 1.5 Common indigenous peoples and local communities' strategies for teaching, regulating, and enforcing local norms of sustainable use.

(This list is not exhaustive and not all indigenous peoples and local communities make use these approaches). Source: (IPBES, 2019b)

- **Calendars:** Calendars or schedules may indicate times to take and not take wild species, as well as where these activities may take place. Calendars may be based on religious rules, moon cycles, or patterns and indicators in the environment.
- **Monitoring:** Ongoing observation and monitoring of habitats, land and seascapes, and wild species populations and health.
- **Spiritual practices:** Ceremonies, including songs and dances, help teach and reinforce the actions necessary to maintain sustainable use and good relations with nature. They may be done, for example, before cutting a tree, picking medicines, hunting, fishing, or consuming animals.
- **Prohibitions and rest periods:** Permanent prohibitions against the use of a species (i.e., taboos) and temporary rest periods frequently are important aspects of customary rules and norms governing the use of wild species. Prohibitions may apply to individual species, groups of species, ecosystem types, or specific places.
- **Sanctions or punishments:** Sanctions for violating customary norms and rules may be enforced by the human community or be considered to come from the spiritual realm in the form of bad fortune for the individual who has transgressed and/or their family.

Figure 1.8 **Indigenous peoples and local communities’ (IPLC’s) sustainable use of wild species: enabling and inhibiting forces.**

Labels on the turtle’s legs and tail represent aspects of culture and practice that participants in the second indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop identified as central to sustainable use of wild species by indigenous peoples and local communities (IPBES, 2019b). The currents in the water around the turtle represent external forces or conditions identified as supporting or impeding sustainable use of wild species by indigenous peoples and local communities.

norms and institutions remain vigorous. Often located far from national centers of power, many communities have been largely on their own to manage the impacts of the pandemic, which include disruptions to government services, supply chains and markets, as well as the return of community members who had migrated to urban centers. For indigenous peoples and local communities who have retained access to healthy lands, waters, and wild species populations, fishing, hunting, and gathering have provided essential food and allowed them to care for vulnerable individuals (i.e., elders, children, and those with disabilities) (Forest Peoples Program, 2021a, 2021b; UN General Assembly, 2020; Walters *et al.*, 2021). Traditional medicinal systems make extensive use of wild animals, fungi and plants (see Chapter 3). These have been widely used for immune system support and treatment of symptoms of COVID-19. However, many other communities have seen their capacity to turn to the use of wild species erode as illegal expansion of agricultural frontiers, encroachment by criminal actors, and land grabs and displacement of indigenous peoples and

local communities from their lands by extractive industries have increased. Enforcement of indigenous peoples and local communities’ territorial rights and measure to assure the safety of their leaders could help to redress these trends and the loss of food and health security that attend them (Forest Peoples Program, 2021a, 2021b; UN General Assembly, 2020; Walters *et al.*, 2021). These examples of resilience and loss provide models for understanding and governing sustainable uses of wild species that can inform discussions of a ‘green recovery’ from the pandemic.

1.4.2 Scaling up the analysis of indigenous peoples and local communities’ contributions to sustainable use of wild species

The actual strategies developed by indigenous peoples and local communities to enhance sustainable use of wild

species have been developed through context-dependent learning, adaptation to changing environments and, often, sustained negotiations to resolve conflicts among individual users, sectors or communities. As a result, the ontological foundations and epistemological modes of indigenous peoples and local communities often diverge from those of research-based science and the management systems it informs. Indeed, the specific rules and approaches to sustainable use that have been developed by indigenous peoples and local communities are embedded in complex knowledge systems and socio-cultural milieux that differ not only from hegemonic institutions but also from one local context to the next. The identification of effective sustainable use strategies for the purpose of transposing such strategies benefits significantly from being attentive to the contexts from which they emerge, to the local knowledge and existing practices and rules that make such strategies effective. Nevertheless, the essential elements of successful strategies and the processes involved, as well as the concepts and principles with which they align, may find purchase beyond the local context and come to inform practices of sustainable use in other locations and at other scales.

Successful strategies developed within specific indigenous peoples and local communities' contexts to be useful in other locations and across larger scales will require some degree of assessment and translation by institutions intent on transposition. While institutions and organizations (e.g., state sponsored agencies, international regulatory bodies, non-governmental organizations) charged with developing approaches for sustainable use often document and amplify successful indigenous peoples and local communities' strategies for sustainable use, they could also engage in the explication of specific strategies (as well as concepts and principles) that are potentially translatable and transposable. To do so, such institutions and organizations may modify and recalibrate their own systems of sustainable use observation, measurement, and analysis in order to "see" and learn from indigenous peoples and local communities' sustainable use systems built upon other ontological and epistemological foundations. In this case, those translated and transposable strategies that emerge from engagements with indigenous peoples and local communities can best be understood as co-productions (by indigenous peoples and local communities and "larger" institutions) with capacities that are more likely to resonate beyond the local context from which they were derived.

While a range of indigenous peoples and local communities' strategies, concepts, and principles suitable for regulating specific types of resource uses may be identified, translated, and proposed as relevant elsewhere, their effective transposition will depend on how they are implemented. It is essential to have institutions and processes in place to facilitate discussion among stakeholders and indigenous

and local rights holders on implementation details adapted to each particular context (Carter & Currie-Alder, 2006). There is also a need to uncover and understand customary rules and institutions that may be operating effectively but could be easily destabilized when formal rules are introduced. Two examples in Chile illustrate ways that formal rules can clash with traditional fisheries systems: (i) regulatory requirements of the Chilean system of territorial use rights in fisheries disrupt the traditional system of rotating kelp harvesting practices (Gelcich *et al.*, 2006); (ii) recommendations for closing areas disrupt a tightly woven system of tenure of lobster fishing spots evolved over decades in the Chilean Juan Fernández archipelago (Ernst *et al.*, 2013).

Just as context matters in terms of learning about successful strategies from indigenous peoples and local communities, so too will context matter when proposing that such strategies be adopted elsewhere. The re-location and/or re-scaling of successful indigenous peoples and local communities' practices benefits significantly from recognizing their dynamic, experimental, and outcomes-based nature. In this case, it is recommended that institutions and formal management systems incorporate such practices into explicitly adaptive management approaches with the flexibility to include a range of concerns (e.g., socio-cultural) and avoid the inflexible institutionalization of particular regulations or rights (e.g., permanent property rights, see Cinner & Aswani, 2007). The success of indigenous peoples and local communities' systems of sustainable use is, in part, due to their ability to allow for and adapt to changing natural and social conditions (e.g., Berkes *et al.*, 2000). Successful practices and mistakes-to-avoid need to be documented to leverage local learning and scale-up successes. There is a strong potential to create, encourage and support communities of practice (Wenger, 1998) to share knowledge and learn from past mistakes and achievements.

1.5 THE IPBES ASSESSMENT OF THE SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES IN THE CONTEXT OF OTHER ASSESSMENTS

There have been very few international assessments targeting the sustainable use of wild species and those past reports focused only on a few species and/or case studies (see e.g., Prescott-Allen & Prescott-Allen, 1996). Nonetheless, previous biodiversity and sectoral assessments offer valuable insights into uses of wild species, their contributions to human well-being, and factors contributing to long-term prospects for their sustainable use. The sustainable use assessment builds on global assessments produced by IPBES, organizations of the United Nations and other global organizations. It also considers one national assessment dedicated to non-timber forest products, since the practice of gathering (1.3.3) was not thoroughly reflected in the other global assessments. All these assessments address human uses of wild species and factors contributing to their sustainability (or lack thereof) as a primary or secondary focus.

Collectively, the assessments document widespread global dependence on wild species for food, medicine, and other purposes (FAO, 2018c, 2018b, 2019, 2020b, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; IPBES, 2018a; Vira, *et al.*, 2015; WHO & CBD, 2015). Contributions of use of wild species to good quality of life include direct provisioning, sources of income, and energy, the latter especially for cooking and sanitizing water (FAO, 2018c, 2018b, 2020b, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; IPBES, 2016, 2018a, 2018b; Vira, *et al.*, 2015). For many indigenous peoples and local communities, the use of wild species is also essential to identity and culture (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2018; IPBES, 2016). These contributions of use of wild species to human well-being are continuous and quotidian, as well as episodic and exceptional.

The International Union of Forest Research Organizations estimates that nearly 20% of the global population directly depend on forests, tree-based systems, and the wild species in them (Vira, *et al.*, 2015), while the FAO estimates that fisheries and aquaculture support the livelihoods of 12% of people around the world and provide 17% of the global population's intake of animal proteins (FAO, 2018c, 2020b). In addition to serving as primary sources of subsistence resources, income, and identity, uses of wild species also serve as safety nets enabling survival during seasonal shortfalls and crises provoked by anthropogenic (e.g., armed conflicts) and non-anthropogenic (e.g., slow and rapid onset natural disasters) forces (see Chapter 4; FAO, 2015, 2018b, 2019, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; Vira, *et al.*, 2015; WHO & CBD, 2015). The use of wild species also

contributes to the global economy. In the European Union alone, international legal trade of wild species is estimated at 100 billion euros (TRAFFIC, 2020).

These various contexts mean there are intra- and interannual variations in the frequency and intensity of the use of wild species throughout and across years, and these variations may impact the sustainability of use. Whether quotidian or exceptional, nearly all assessments note that human uses of wild species are particularly important to individuals and groups in vulnerable situations, including women, marginalized peoples, indigenous peoples, and forest-dependent communities (note that these may be overlapping rather than mutually exclusive categories; FAO, 2015, 2018b, 2019, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; Vira, *et al.*, 2015; WHO & CBD, 2015).

Multiple assessments document the particularly important contributions of use of wild species to food security and nutrition (FAO, 2015, 2019; HLPE, 2017; Vira *et al.*, 2015; WHO & CBD, 2015). Consumption of wild animals, fungi, and plants contributes directly to human health and well-being through dietary quality and diversity, in rural and urban areas, in developed and developing countries (WHO & CBD, 2015). Reports to FAO from 91 countries included a total of over 2,800 distinct wild species used for human food across the world, the largest share of wild species used for food coming from aquatic and forest production systems, with capture fisheries likely the largest use of wild food by volume, for human consumption or feeding aquaculture species (FAO, 2019, 2020b). A majority of wild fungi, insects, plants and, to a lesser extent, mammals and birds are obtained from forested ecosystems (FAO, 2018b, 2019). Consumption of wild food also enables greater dietary choice (i.e., food sovereignty) and is often used as a complement to a limited set of cultivated crops (FAO, 2019; WHO & CBD, 2015). It has demonstrated benefits in terms of reducing metabolic diseases such as obesity and diabetes, which are epidemic in some parts of the world (Vira, *et al.*, 2015). In Madagascar, it was found that risk of anemia in children from poor households was lowered by nearly 30% when the household consumed wild meat, even in small quantities (Golden *et al.* 2011 in WHO & CBD, 2015). Some assessments note that wild species are an important or primary source of protein (IPBES, 2018a) and provide important micronutrients. Examples show that, in many instances, wild species contain higher levels of micronutrients, vitamins and proteins than similar domesticated crops or livestock (FAO, 2019; WHO & CBD, 2015). Beyond addressing primary needs, wild species may also be preferred to domestic species even when the latter are available through markets. Preference for wild species comes from traditional food preferences (e.g., for people moving from rural to urban areas) or "from a revival of interest in wild foods", often associated with cultural, recreational or nutritional values (FAO, 2019). However,

use of wild species may include risks to human health through the transmission of diseases. Hunting, butchering, transportation and storage of live wild animals or their meat in unsafe conditions particularly presents risk of zoonotic diseases (IPBES, 2020; WHO & CBD, 2015).

The reliance of biomedical processes and traditional medicine alike on wild species, and more specifically on wild plants is widely documented (WHO & CBD, 2015). Many biomedical innovations rely on wild species, but their development at an industrial production scale may threaten the preservation of the very resources underpinning traditional medicine. The Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization aims, among other things, to acknowledge communities' traditional knowledge such as use of plants or animal parts for medicine, in order to protect their rights to those resources, which may include support for conservation and sustainable use on the ground or financial compensation for use of the resources by third parties. Wild species also contribute to mental health and wellbeing, including through extractive and non-extractive practices related to ceremonial and ritual, decorative and aesthetic, recreational and learning and educational uses (FAO, 2019; WHO & CBD, 2015).

Several assessments observe that in addition to land use/land cover change, unsustainable agriculture and forestry, pollution, and climate change, unsustainable uses of wild species are a primary driver of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2018a, 2018d, 2018b, 2018c, 2018e).

Intensification of uses that had been sustainable in the past may lead them to become unsustainable if practices do not adapt to the new drivers (see Chapter 4, IPBES, 2019a). Such drivers may influence:

- Wild species populations (e.g., a disease affecting the wild species, or climate change leading to a shift in wild species range (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2018; FAO, 2019, 2020b);
- The practices (e.g., technological change leading to more intensive or extensive harvesting, industrialization of a wild species use or commercial or demographic drivers leading to increased demand for a wild species, often entailing expansion from local to regional or global markets (FAO, 2019, 2020b);
- The uses (e.g., new applications found for wild species, or shifts from subsistence to commercial uses (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2018; FAO, 2019).

For extractive practices, all those drivers may lead to an increased share of the biomass being removed from nature, disturbing the social-ecological system's equilibrium.

However, some assessments also note that much biodiversity is underpinned by the long-term results of indigenous and local knowledge and indigenous peoples' and local communities' customary practices associated with uses of wild species (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2018; FAO, 2018b, 2020a; Forest Peoples Program *et al.*, 2020; IPBES, 2016, 2019a). Further, erosion of indigenous and local knowledge, in concert with indigenous peoples and local communities' loss of access and tenure rights to traditional territories and resources appears to be a driver of unsustainable uses of wild species and biodiversity loss (Chamberlain *et al.*, 2018; FAO, 2018b, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; IPBES, 2016, 2019a). All assessments in this review identify governance as an important factor in support of sustainable uses of wild species. Several document positive ecological and social outcomes from decentralized, multi-sectoral approaches in which decision-making and management authorities do not rest solely at the level of the nation state (Forest Peoples Program *et al.*, 2020; IPBES, 2016, 2018a, 2018b; Vira, *et al.*, 2015). Rather, they recommend approaches that bring together the public and private sectors, non-governmental organizations, and local communities and integrate multi-sectoral actors from resource management, health, education, and others (Vira, *et al.*, 2015). Acknowledgement of and support for indigenous and local knowledge, tenure, and access to resources, including genetic resources, are identified as a key step toward the sustainable use of wild species (Forest Peoples Program *et al.*, 2020; HLPE, 2017; IPBES, 2016, 2018e; Vira, *et al.*, 2015). Likewise, the importance of a rights-based approach with particular importance given to complying with international human rights laws and standards in all governance instruments and processes is noted as fundamental to governing the use of wild species (Forest Peoples Program *et al.*, 2020; HLPE, 2017).

No assessment on non-extractive practices was identified, but some activities associated with nature-based tourism have been the focus of global reports (INTOSAI WGEA, 2013; Tapper, 2006). A study conducted in the early 2000s found that 20% to 40% of all international tourists included some form of wildlife watching in their trip. Tourism focusing on wild species sustains the whole tourism sector in some countries, and provides income and employment to people such as guides and drivers, as well as employees in the hotel and food services industries. Wildlife watching tourism "ranked as one of the top three export sectors for more than three-quarters of all developing countries in 2000, and was the principle export in a third of these countries" (Tapper, 2006). Globally, "wildlife tourism" was estimated to represent 9% of gross domestic product in 2011 (INTOSAI WGEA, 2013). Because protected areas are often wildlife watching destinations it also can support biodiversity conservation. It is therefore in the interest of national or local governments, but also of the tourism businesses, to support conservation of those areas (INTOSAI WGEA, 2013; Tapper, 2006).

In the early 2000s, Tapper (2006), noted that little was known about the actual income generated by wildlife watching or the impacts of tourism activities on the targeted species. Audits of the activities around wildlife watching, to assess their ecological and social impacts, were still scarce (INTOSAI WGEA, 2013). Another report by Tonazzini *et al.* (2019), focusing on coastal and marine tourism concluded that tourist density should be constrained to avoid negative impacts. When nature-based tourism is over developed, it can have negative impacts on wild species through increased disturbance, and on the local communities who risk being excluded from the benefits with the arrival of bigger, external players investing in tourism activities or through the commodification of people's cultures. The emphasis on economic returns may also contribute to an increase in local conflicts between people and wild species (INTOSAI WGEA, 2013). Further, if it becomes a main or single source of income, households and communities are vulnerable to variations in tourist flows within and across the years.

The picture of the relationship between human uses of wild species and biodiversity that emerges from this review of previous assessments is far from simple. Opportunities for and outcomes of human uses of wild species are mediated by complex, interacting factors including environmental, economic, social, and cultural contexts (HLPE, 2017). There are clearly documented instances in which the relationship between biodiversity and nature's contributions to people through the use of wild species is reciprocal; nature's contributions to people depend on biodiversity and much biodiversity is maintained through indigenous and local knowledge and practices related to the use of wild species. Equally, there are well-documented cases in which the use of wild species results in biodiversity losses. There are both rich sources of information on these processes and significant gaps in data and synthesis of existing knowledge from diverse sources. These gaps impede understanding of the processes and of the pathways to greater social and ecological sustainability of the use of wild species.

Contributions of the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species

The IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species is the first international endeavor to be fully comprehensive of all practices and uses associated with the sustainable uses of wild species. While many previous assessments focus on drivers of unsustainable uses of wild species and their consequences for biodiversity, the mandate of the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species is to identify solutions that enhance their sustainable uses. To do so, this assessment uses a groundbreaking conceptualization that enables analysis of any type of use of any species (see the organizing structure in section 1.3.4) and supports analyses across

scales and comparison of successes and failures of interventions across practices. The focus on sustainable use of wild species is also a novel aspect of this assessment. Building on assessments that have come before, the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species approaches the task through systematic review of the scientific literature and addressing and working with indigenous and local knowledge to fill gaps in knowledge and identify pathways to enhanced sustainability of the use of wild species that contribute to conservation and development.

Regarding fishing and logging, the sustainable use assessment draws from the work of the FAO and especially the State of the World's Forests and the State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture, which focus on resources (respectively, timber and non-timber forest products, and fish and shellfish), in order to present the various uses associated with these species and where, how and why those uses are sustainable. Regarding terrestrial animal harvesting, gathering and non-extractive uses, the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species similarly draws the bigger picture related to those practices, while also collating for the first time global data and evidence on those species' uses. This assessment also gives a clear picture of where gaps are in data and synthesis of existing knowledge around the sustainable use of wild species (see supplementary material S1.1). As those gaps are filled, understanding of pathways to greater social-ecological sustainability of the use of wild species will improve.

1.6 MAPPING SUSTAINABLE USE OF WILD SPECIES CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

While this assessment focuses on sustainable use and not on sustainable development (1.3.2), it is important to stress the multiple contributions that sustainable use of wild species can make to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. That contribution is overlooked for many Goals, with the phrasing of their targets or indicators making no link to the sustainable use of wild species. This section aims to highlight, in particular for policymakers, the role that sustainable use of wild species can play if taken into account in strategies for sustainable development. As noted below, the sustainable use of wild species can support better quality of life for people of the world in the most vulnerable situations, but is also an essential component of good quality of life for all. For many people, especially indigenous peoples and local communities, uses of wild species are

understood as characteristic of abundance and wealth. As highlighted in **Table 1.3** and throughout this assessment, the sustainable use of wild species offers potential synergies to realize almost all Sustainable Development Goals, and could be incorporated as a central or complementary strategy for many of them. When the use of wild species is sustainable, there are few drawbacks. Such drawbacks may include potential adverse human health and climate implications of some uses of wild biomass for energy and misidentification or unsafe handling of wild foods (see section 1.5).

It should be acknowledged that since all Sustainable Development Goals are interdependent and indivisible, achieving them will also create favorable conditions for the sustainable use of wild species, through for example better recognition of access and tenure rights, implementation of the rule of law, better distribution of benefits or opening up of more options e.g., for food, income generation etc. The analysis for each Sustainable Development Goal is presented in **Table 1.3** below and further discussed in the rest of the section. It covers only “outcome targets”, leaving aside targets on the means of implementation which fall beyond the scope of this assessment.

Table 1.3 Meeting Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) via socially & ecologically – actual & potential – sustainable uses of wild species.

SDGs	Potential contributions of the use of wild species to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (Numbers in brackets refer to sections in the chapters that provide underlying evidence)
SDG1 No poverty	Sustainable uses of wild species reduce poverty (i.e., lack of the resources necessary for subsistence) by providing food, medicine, and materials for personal use, as well as sources of income. The role of fishing, gathering, terrestrial animal harvesting and logging in poverty reduction is particularly important for many of the world’s poorest individuals and households. Globally, the proportion of household income from extractive and non-extractive uses of wild species ranges from 17% to 98%, depending on location, social identity, and types of products harvested (3.2.4, 3.3.1, 3.3.3, 3.3.4, 4.2.3.4).
SDG 2 Zero hunger	Wild foods are central to food security and nutrition for millions of people residing in rural and urban settings worldwide, providing essential energy, as well as macro- and micro-nutrients. Thousands of species of wild animals, fungi, and plants are used as food on a regular basis or provide safety nets in times of shortage. For example, gathering provides food, income, and nutritional diversity for an estimated one in five people around the world, in particular women, children, landless farmers and others in vulnerable situations. Wild fish and wild meat are the primary or sole source of protein in some households’ diets, where they can reduce the risk of anemia and provide important nutrients including calcium, zinc, and iron (1.5, 3.3.1.5.1, 3.3.2.3.4, 3.3.3.2.3, 4.2.4.2.2). In addition to subsistence consumption, wild foods are traded in formal and informal markets at scales from the local to the global. In some cases, competition between commercial and subsistence harvesting may jeopardize the food security of local communities (4.2.4.2.2). Indigenous and local knowledge can play a role in reducing global hunger through conservation of wild crop relatives and insights into uses of abundant but uncommonly used food sources such as insects (3.3.2.3.4).
SDG 3 Good health and well-being	Harvest and use of wild species, especially plants, are central to the traditional health systems and primary healthcare of people throughout the world, including for COVID-19 treatments. Access to and uses of wild species have particular importance for the health and well-being of indigenous peoples and local communities (1.4.1, 1.5, 3.3.2.3.5, 3.3.2.4, 4.2.3.5.1). In addition, wild food consumption has demonstrated benefits in reduced incidence of metabolic diseases such as obesity and diabetes, which are epidemic in much of the world (1.5). Wild plant materials and genetic resources also are important components of industrially-produced medicines. An estimated 60-90% of the medicinal and aromatic plants traded globally are gathered in the wild (1.1). Evidence suggests that connections to nature through non-extractive practices (e.g., forest bathing, bird watching) can benefit psychological health and improve well-being through effects such as reduced stress and increased mental abilities (3.3.5.2.2). Evidence also exists for physiological and psychological welfare derived from fishing or hunting (3.3.1.5.3, 3.3.3.2.1). However, unsanitary handling and consumption of wild animals can increase the risk of zoonotic diseases (3.3.3.1).

Table 1 3

SDGs	Potential contributions of the use of wild species to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (Numbers in brackets refer to sections in the chapters that provide underlying evidence)
SDG 4 Quality education	<p>Income generated through harvest and trade of wild species can be an important source of cash to support children's educational costs (3.3.2).</p> <p>Non-extractive practices (e.g., wildlife watching) may provide valuable educational experiences, enhancing understanding of nature and motivations to protect it (3.3.5.2.4).</p> <p>Global trends toward standardization of education are resulting in decreasing attention to, and understanding of, local biodiversity and a decline in community resilience. Many local and indigenous groups are calling for systemic changes in educational systems to respect the traditions, knowledge, languages, values, history, and identities of their cultures. Formal recognition by national educational systems of cross-generational knowledge transmission and a wider range of approaches to learning (e.g., supporting and restoring indigenous and local knowledge, led by indigenous peoples and local communities) would support local stewardship and sustainable use of wild species (4.2.6.4.2, 4.2.6.4.6).</p>
SDG 5 Gender equality	<p>Many uses of wild species are strongly gendered (3.3.2.2.3, 3.3.4.4.2, 4.2.3.6). Sustainable uses of wild species empower women throughout the world. Women's uses of wild animals, fungi, and plants support their health, provide the means for women to support themselves and their families, confer financial independence, and give them recognition within their communities and beyond. For example, globally women occupy half the jobs in the seafood industry and small-scale fisheries activities. Despite this, women often lack clear rights of tenure and are excluded from meaningful participation in management discussions. Securing women's participation in decision-making can be seen as an outcome as well as a condition for sustainable use (3.3.2.2.3, 4.2.2.6, 4.2.3.6).</p>
SDG 6 Clean water and sanitation	<p>Best management practices in logging can protect water quality, reduce soil erosion and maintain riparian habitat (4.3.2.4).</p>
SDG 7 Affordable and clean energy	<p>2.8 billion people, or 38% of the global population, rely on biomass for energy. Logging for energy accounts for 50% of all wood consumed globally, and accounts for 90% of timber harvested in Africa (3.3.4.4.2).</p> <p>While often affordable, in many cases wood energy is not clean because of the technologies used for cooking and/or heating. However, the demand for wood fuel is increasing due to renewable energy targets (3.3.4.4.2).</p>
SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth	<p>Sustainable uses of wild species provide work for millions of people worldwide and contribute to economic growth and stability at local, national, and regional scales (3.3). Mixed economies and diverse livelihood strategies that include subsistence uses of wild species and/or their trade in informal markets allow households and communities to respond to changes in the wage economy and variation in the availability of wild species (4.2.4.2.1).</p> <p>A majority of jobs and income from sustainable uses of wild species likely involve local trade in the informal economy. Conversion from small-scale enterprises to more intensive commodification for a larger market often jeopardizes the social and ecological sustainability of subsistence activities and small-scale trade (3.3.1, 3.3.2, 4.2.4.3, 4.2.4.4).</p> <p>Nevertheless, there is substantial global trade in wild species. For example, in 2009, TRAFFIC estimated legal international trade, including timber and fisheries products, at US\$323 billion. Germany alone imported US\$ 250 million of medicinal and aromatic plants in 2015. Nevertheless, caution is in order, as the direction of global trade in wild species typically flows from developing to developed nations (4.2.4.3) and often, the individuals and communities that harvest wild species for global commodity markets are not the primary economic beneficiaries of such trade (4.2.4.3.1).</p> <p>When sustainably managed, naturally regenerating forests can provide diverse work and opportunities for economic return from each of the extractive and non-extractive practices considered in this assessment (3.3.4.3.1, 3.3.5.2).</p> <p>Non-extractive practices (e.g., wildlife watching) can provide work for local communities and national economic growth. However, that income is vulnerable to shocks such as global recessions or pandemics and the distribution of benefits depends on factors including tax policy, infrastructure, and supply chains for goods and services (3.3.5.3, 4.2.4.3.3).</p>
SDG 9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure	<p>Wild species are primary raw materials for numerous industrial sectors, <i>inter alia</i> apparel, construction, cosmetics, energy, food, and pharmaceuticals and traditional medicine formulations. These industries are national to global in extent, with annual values in the millions to billions of US dollars (3.3.1.5, 3.3.2.3.2, 3.3.2.3, 3.3.3.2.3, 3.3.3.3.1, 3.3.4.4).</p> <p>Industries that initially use wild species as primary raw materials often shift to substitution of alternative materials, cultivation, or synthesis for reasons that include declines in commercially viable populations of the target wild species, interannual variability in the abundance of the wild species, and other efficiencies or cost cutting measures (3.3.2.3.4, 3.3.4.2, 3.4.3, 4.2.1.5.3, 4.2.6.2.4).</p> <p>While indigenous peoples and local communities often derive important income from trade in wild species, conversion of subsistence and small-scale commerce to industrial scales can threaten the social and ecological sustainability of these practices (3.2.4).</p>
SDG 10 Reduced inequalities	<p>Sustainable use of wild species can create new opportunities and upward social and economic mobility for some. Conversely, when species previously used for subsistence or small-scale trade enter larger-scale markets, supply chains often are taken over by more powerful individuals or organizations, reducing or eliminating benefits to people who do not enjoy institutional or political favor (3.3.3.2.4, 3.3.5.2.3, 3.4.5.2). Indigenous and local people can make critical contributions to enhance the way people understand the natural world and the ways people conduct meaningful research and resource management (2.2.4, 4.2.5, 6.6).</p> <p>For many rural families, the sale of wild species is the main source of cash income and provides access to modern services and basic necessities such as medicines, energy and education (3.3.3.2.3).</p> <p>When well governed, nature-based tourism can support poverty alleviation and provide local employment. However, such benefits require that nature-based tourism enterprises provide direct employment for local people and source goods and services locally (3.3.5.2.3).</p>

SDGs	Potential contributions of the use of wild species to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (Numbers in brackets refer to sections in the chapters that provide underlying evidence)
SDG 11 Sustainable cities and communities	<p>Sustainable uses of wild species can and do occur in and around cities. Many urban residents consume wild meats, cook with wood fuels, and use medicinal plants. Some hunting, fishing, and gathering also occurs in urban and peri-urban environments. Urban residents' motivations for using wild species may include perceptions that consuming wild foods is more ecologically and ethically sound than conventional agricultural products, preference, tradition, status, and recreation. Demand for game meat or wood fuel in fast-growing cities can lead to unsustainable use of wild species in nearby areas. Approaches combining rural and urban planning, such as peri-urban agroforestry, can contribute to sustainable use.</p> <p>Time spent in urban greenspaces to engage in wild species-based activities such as wildlife watching and gathering has been shown to support physical and emotional well-being (3.3.3.2.3, 3.3.3.2.6, 3.3.4.3.3, 3.3.5.2.2, 4.2.3, 4.2.5).</p> <p>SDG 11 also includes a target related to the protection of the world's cultural and natural heritage. In many instances, uses of wild species are directly or indirectly linked with cultural and natural heritage, and the erosion of one (either wild species or cultural and natural heritage) leads in many cases to the decline of the other. In some instances, urban greenspaces also support cultural and religious identity in a manner similar to that of rural sacred spaces (3.2.1.5, 3.3.1.4, 3.3.2.3.2, 3.3.2.3.4, 3.3.5.2, 4.2.2.5, 4.2.5.2.2, 4.2.5.2.6, 4.2.5.2.7, 4.2.5.2.10).</p>
SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production	<p>Socially and ecologically sustainable use of wild species has a role to play in responsible production and consumption. A large proportion of wild species production and consumption is for personal use (i.e., subsistence) or trade that occurs in informal markets. For the use of wild species that take place through large-scale commercial trade, multilateral organizations, environmental nongovernmental organizations, and industry associations have developed programs to incentivize sustainable production and motivate consumers to make sustainable choices (e.g., the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development BioTrade program and certification schemes such as the Marine Stewardship Council and the Forest Stewardship Council). While there is some evidence of success in these endeavors, findings are mixed as to whether they have delivered hoped for outcomes including uptake of voluntary programs, equitable distribution of benefits from production systems, transparent supply chains, and changing consumer behavior. Factors contributing to responsible production and consumption of recreational benefits through non-extractive uses of wild species such as wildlife watching include respect for local community rights and customary practices, use of locally sourced material and labor, capacity building for providers, and environmental education programming for consumers (3.2.4; 3.3.4.3.3, 3.3.5.2.3, 4.2.2, 4.2.3.5, 4.2.4).</p>
SDG 13 Climate action	<p>For millennia, the use of wild species has provided safety nets in times of abrupt and cyclical shortages due to meteorological events (1.5, 4.2.1.2, 4.3.3). Education, awareness-raising and capacity building, including maintenance of indigenous and local knowledge and capacity building for indigenous peoples and local communities, can enable future contributions of use of wild species to climate change adaptation and impact reduction strategies (6.5.2.1). Policies for climate action, such as those for the reduction of emissions from deforestation and forest degradation, can build on the sustainable use of wild species, e.g., through decreasing logging and improving gathering practices (4.2.1.2.5, 6.4.1).</p>
SDG 14 Life below water	<p>The status of fish stocks in the temperate north, which provide half of the world's catch, show positive trends in good part due to monitoring of fish stocks and regulation of catches. The status of the other half of world's catch, largely from South-East Asia, is unknown. Industrial fishing now occurs in over 55% of the global oceans, and several countries have established arrangements to guarantee access to those resources by local communities. Granting user rights to communities has usually had positive impacts for the sustainability of fisheries. Although informal and largely unreported, small-scale fisheries sustain local based economies and provide for the food security of people living in conditions of poverty all over the world. Illegal, unreported and unregulated fisheries do not necessarily mean that those fisheries are unsustainable, but in most known cases they are or are very likely to become so. There is some evidence for unsustainable use in regulated fisheries although robust fisheries management generally leads to more sustainable use. Very successful management measures adopted by large-scale and small-scale fishing systems (e.g., in Europe) have been able to promote better fishing practices, including the recovery of many over exploited fishing stocks, the readoption of old technologies and gears, and even the recovery of lost jobs and economic viability. This can include, among other effective regulation measures, the creation of marine protected areas to regulate fishing, which are more successful when local fishers are engaged. It is <i>well established</i> that co-management practices are very effective in the adoption and promotion of good fishing practices, with very positive effects in almost all places it is implemented. Potential revenues from non-lethal or non-extractive practices (e.g., catch-and-release, diving) can be also substantial (3.3.1, 3.3.5, 4.2.1, 4.2.2, 4.2.4.2, 4.2.4.3.3).</p>
SDG 15 Life on land	<p>Often local livelihoods are believed to be in conflict with conservation and are restricted by rules and regulation that impede local economic development and effectively criminalize customary activities. Where conservation actions are co-designed and co-managed with local communities, they can support recovery of species and further sustainable use. Nature-based tourism as a complementary activity that substitutes completely, or partially, unsustainable use of wild species requires a fundamental re-organization of a community's economic and social structure. Local communities who participate in nature-based tourism and receive tangible benefits from it tend to become cautious in their use of natural resources and more likely to support conservation (3.2.1, 3.3.3.4.1, 3.3.4.3.2, 3.3.5.2.3).</p> <p>There is increasing recognition that cultural diversity plays a pivotal role in sustainable use of wild species. A growing body of work indicates that multi-use systems and de-centralized, small-scale community and household economies adapt more readily to variability and shocks in the availability of wild species. They also have benefits for social equity and community well-being. Tenure arrangements that secure local rights over land and resource use and trade, management systems co-designed with indigenous peoples and local communities, clear incentives and equitable sharing of benefits can lead to sustainable use, diversification of livelihoods, and biodiversity conservation. There is evidence that centralized management has failed to ensure sustainable use in several instances (4.2.2, 4.2.4.2, 4.2.5.1).</p> <p>The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora is an international treaty to prevent species from becoming endangered or extinct because of international trade. Trade bans were important in the recovery of many species but depending on the resource and the circumstances they may have unintended consequences. Indiscriminate/blanket trade bans create the risk of undermining the potential for sustainable use to provide critically-needed revenue and incentives for conservation. Mediating factors such as the scale of trade, species characteristics, governance, trade relationship, local incentives for conservation, supply chains and market demand are important in determining the sustainability outcomes of a particular trade. Empowering local people to capture legal benefits from trade in wild species can be an important step in reducing excessive illegal harvests, when efforts to provide alternative livelihoods are unsuccessful. It can further lead to species conservation efforts, by creating an incentive to mitigate other threats to biodiversity, such as habitat loss through land conversion (4.2.4.3.1).</p>

Table 1 3

SDGs	Potential contributions of the use of wild species to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (Numbers in brackets refer to sections in the chapters that provide underlying evidence)
SDG 16 Peace, justice and strong institutions	Effective governance of wild species can contribute to peace, justice and strong institutions, especially where indigenous peoples and local communities are dependent on these resources for food, medicine, and other purposes. Investments in strong, transparent institutions, distribution of information through clear communication, and a focus on rights and equity support more sustainable, just outcomes. Illegal and unsustainable use of wild species is often linked to international criminal organizations (3.3.1.4, 3.3.3.2.4, 3.3.4.2, 4.2.2, 4.2.4.3.2, 4.2.2.6).
SDG 17 Partnerships for the Goals	Many systems for sustainable use of wild species currently involve partnerships that contribute to achieving one or more sustainable development goals (see, especially, 14 and 15) and provide an arena in which cross sectoral and multi-lateral cooperation can be further strengthened. For example, scientific reports on fisheries and forests produced by the FAO are important mechanisms for developing and transferring scientific information, which could be enhanced by additional attention to how effective governance of practices such as gathering can strengthen progress toward goals 1, 2, 3, and 5. Likewise, the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues can raise awareness and disseminate information about indigenous rights, as well as strategies to support indigenous and local knowledge and build capacity among indigenous peoples and local communities. Global commercial trade in wild species is worth billions of US dollars, with goods flowing mostly from developing to developed countries. Many existing governance and institutional frameworks for the sustainable use of wild species include provisions to ensure equitable distribution of benefits. However, implementation is often flawed, with adverse consequences for social and ecological sustainability. Evidence shows that where benefits are equitably shared with the communities who are custodians or primary users of wild species, this can lead to overall progress towards all Sustainable Development Goals (1.5, 3.2.4, 3.3.1.4.4, 3.3.2.3.2, 3.3.4.4.1, 3.3.4.4.3, 3.5, 4.2.2, 4.2.3.4, 4.2.4.2).

While this assessment and previous ones (1.5) highlight the critical role that sustainable use of wild species can play in eradicating poverty (Goal 1) and reducing inequalities (Goal 10), only one target (1.4) of Goal 1 explicitly mentions natural resources and implies that control of those can contribute to eradicating poverty. Evidence shows that sustainable use of wild species is central to the livelihoods and resilience of billions of people. While not captured in formal statistics, personal consumption of wild species and trade in informal markets are particularly important to the capacity of people in vulnerable situations to meet their basic needs (see Chapter 3). The sustainable use of wild species is also central to long term strategies for financial stability and employment, especially in rural communities, where personal consumption can free up monetary resources for other purposes, and trade in formal and informal markets can generate income in the same order of magnitude as some national employment sectors. In particular, sustainable use of wild species is critical for many women’s financial independence and contributes to giving them a role in decision-making. At the State level, many sustainable uses of wild species occur in developing countries, including non-extractive practices, with many exported globally as a national asset. However, one cannot expect to fully eradicate global poverty or inequalities, solely on the basis of sustainable use of wild species. Indeed, evidence demonstrates that to remain sustainable, uses must respect ecological boundaries and social contexts, which can be exceeded or disrupted when subjected to intensification. Good governance frameworks are critical to ensure that use remains sustainable while benefiting people in the most vulnerable situations, who are in most cases the custodians and harvesters of the species (see Chapter

3 and Chapter 4). This is linked with the opportunities that sustainable use of wild species offer for providing decent work and economic growth, which are at the core of Goal 8 (see below).

Three out of the five outcome targets of Goal 2 relating to ending hunger focus on agriculture. This emphasis overlooks the critical contributions that wild foods make to the nutrition of many people, including those in the most vulnerable situations (see Chapter 3). Recognizing the contributions of wild species in food policies could enhance nutritional outcomes, provided long-term availability of these resources is prioritized. Doing so would also help to avoid undermining current contributions of use of wild species to ending hunger, noting the need for attention to both near-term and long-term outcomes. For example, agricultural expansion may produce short-term improvements in development status while reducing long-term access to wild species as safety nets in times of individual or collective crisis, with especially adverse consequences for the most vulnerable peoples. Sustainability of a use will depend on the relationship between commercial and subsistence harvesting, and whether local communities receive equitable sharing of the benefits from harvests (see Chapter 4).

Targets of Goal 3 on achieving good health and well-being do not provide much insight into the contributions that wild species can make to this goal. However, through use in many traditional medical systems and the pharmaceutical industry, as well as their contributions to sound and nutritious food (see above), sustainable use of wild species plays a role in reducing child mortality, healing vector-borne

diseases and preventing non-communicable diseases. Extractive and non-extractive practices can play a central role to achieve Target 3.4 aiming at promoting mental health and well-being. The use of wild species also carries health risks, however, as when zoonotic diseases are transmitted to humans through unsanitary handling or consumption of wild meat (see Chapter 3).

Goal 4 relates to giving access to quality education to all people, from small children to adults. Sustainable use of wild species indirectly contributes through the generation of income that in many instances is used to pay for education, especially among the poorest (see Chapters 3 and 4). More directly, practices associated with sustainable use contribute to target 4.4 on providing people with technical and vocational skills to have decent jobs and develop entrepreneurship (see details below related to Goals 5 and 12, among others). The knowledge necessary to support sustainable use of wild species can greatly contribute to target 4.7 on acquiring knowledge and skills for sustainable development. In particular, inclusion of indigenous and local knowledge about sustainable use of wild species in school curricula and other programs can support culturally appropriate education for indigenous peoples and local communities, as well as broader understanding of sustainable lifestyles and an appreciation of cultural diversity for all. This also contributes to the social inclusion of people who are often marginalized (see Chapter 4).

In many local cases, sustainable use of wild species contributes to gender equality (Goal 5). Women participate heavily in the practices examined in this assessment, either as the head of the household in charge of providing food for their family through subsistence uses (see Goal 1 above) or through commercial sales of the species (see Goal 8). Examples identified in this IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species demonstrate particularly key roles for women in fishing and gathering. Nevertheless, the literature shows that conditions supporting the sustainable use of wild species by women often are precarious, with most lacking rights over the natural resources they use. Further, when commercial uses of wild species enter large-scale markets women's practices frequently are taken over by men. Targets on gender equality and sustainable use of wild species influence each other mutually: efforts to increase the contributions of use of wild species to eradicate poverty and provide jobs could include measures that reduce inequality, in general, and contribute to gender equality, in particular (Goals 10 and 5, respectively).

As a primary tool for forest management, sustainable logging can play an important role in ensuring availability and sustainable management of water (Goal 6). The role of forest functions in the health of surface and ground water is widely recognized. Where logging is sustainable and contributes to the maintenance or restoration of healthy forests, it also

can play a role in addressing water scarcity and improving water quality.

Sustainable logging also is a potential contributor to Goal 7, although views on its potential in this regard are mixed. Wood fuel and charcoal provide affordable energy for millions of people worldwide (Goal 7). However, the technologies used to burn wood fuel and charcoal often are not clean or safe and can create health risks (thus undermining Goal 3). Biomass energy from timber is increasingly common in Europe and North America, as is the development of combustion technologies that are clean and efficient. There is lack of consensus, however, on the net effect of forest management for the production of woody biomass energy on carbon budgets (Schlesinger, 2018; Serman *et al.*, 2018), which could undermine progress towards Goal 13 on climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Goal 8 is closely related to other Sustainable Development Goals, especially Goals 1 and 5 to which the contribution of the sustainable use of wild species is discussed above. Wildlife watching and other non-extractive practices can be important components of the service industry, contributing to economic growth at local and national scales. Likewise, observations of wild species have triggered innovations, to increase harvesting ease and efficiency. Such innovations may enhance the sustainability of a use (e.g., design of fishing gear to reduce bycatch) or they may decrease sustainability (e.g., through bigger fishing vessels and fleets with onboard processing that make it possible to increase catch volumes in waters farther from shore; see Chapter 4). More generally, resource efficiency is critical for the sustainability of many uses of wild species and is well reflected in this Goal. The sustainable use of wild species can thus bring much in terms of economic and social development, especially through high-added value uses, when all environmental and social safeguards are implemented. However, the sustainable use assessment also raises cautionary flags about the potential for efforts aimed only at economic growth, noting the need for attention to both near-term and long-term sustainability outcomes. For example, unregulated recreation and tourism development may produce short-term improvements in development status while reducing long-term access to wild species as safety nets in times of individual or collective crisis, with especially adverse consequences for peoples in the most vulnerable situations (see in 1.5 above: FAO, 2018b, 2020a; HLPE, 2017; IPBES, 2018b, 2018a; Vira, *et al.*, 2015).

The contribution of wild species to Goal 9 is a double-edged sword. The sustainable use of wild species inspires and is central to several big industries such as the construction, food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic and fashion industries. Many local users of wild species also rely on them as

the basis for small-scale industries. The production scale will greatly impact the sustainability of the use. When the demand from industry for a species is too high to be sustained from the wild, the species can be cultivated or bred (e.g., plantation of forests for timber) (see **Box 1.1**), in the field or in laboratories. Such alternatives can jeopardize the sustainability of local uses of the species, whose sales to the industry provide income to the local communities. For example, small-scale fisheries are threatened by industrial fishing, in many cases placing the viability of small-scale fisheries communities at risk (see Chapter 3). They can also lead to other environmental concerns when it comes to the production of feedstock, such as land use conversion for cultivation or depletion of wild populations to supply raw materials for the synthesis of pharmaceuticals (see Chapter 4).

With regard to sustainable use of wild species, Goal 9 is closely linked with Goal 12, which focuses on sustainable production and consumption. The IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species notes that private companies often do not divulge the origin of the products they process, and that the assessment of the social dimension of sustainability is often neglected in current sustainability assessments of supply chains. Improving those would contribute to target 12.6 under the Sustainable Development Goals and enable individuals to make more informed decisions about the sustainability of their consumption practices (target 12.8). This IPBES assessment also identifies key elements, enabling conditions and criteria for sustainable use of wild species to inform industries and companies that have wild species in their supply chains or work in areas that provide habitat for such species. Business schemes for the sustainable use of wild species (e.g., certifications and labels) can contribute to Goal 12, but need to be implemented with care. Indeed, research indicates that some of them create inequalities, and thus undermine progress towards other Sustainable Development Goals, such as Goal 5 or Goal 10.

As noted above, sustainable use of wild species can play an important role in reducing poverty, especially among people in vulnerable situations. As such, it can help reduce inequality within countries (Goal 10) by supporting food security, health and well-being, access to education, gender equality, and incomes (see Goal 1-5 and 8). These functions of sustainable use of wild species, as well as their contributions to maintaining cultural identity, can be especially important to indigenous peoples and local communities. Establishment of laws and policies that support indigenous peoples and local communities' rights of access to land, waters, and wild species for sustainable use will reduce inequality within and among countries.

Sustainable cities and communities are at the core of Goal 11 and impact the sustainable use of wild species in two

different ways. While Goal 11 only mentions green spaces (target 11.7) that may be a relevant contribution of wild species, the other contributions that the sustainable use of wild species can make to increase the sustainability of cities need to be highlighted. City-dwellers gather fungi and wild plants in urban environment and benefit from non-extractive practices such as bird watching and forest bathing (see Chapter 3). In that sense, target 11.7 which aims to provide universal access to green spaces reflects well the potential contributions of wild species. City-dwellers also use wild species coming from peri-urban or rural areas, with attendant effects on the sustainable use of wild species outside. Awareness of such practices is increasing in Europe and North America, where the use of wild species may be seen as more sustainable than alternative resources (e.g., game meat instead of ranched cattle, wood fuel instead of fossil-fuel energy). Recent rural migrants to cities also bring knowledge and practices with them, which they may continue to draw on in urban and peri-urban environments. The IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species notes (see e.g., Chapter 4) that high urban demand for wild species imported from rural areas may lead to their overexploitation, especially in the cases of wood for cooking and heating or game meat for food. Aiming for the sustainable use of wild species in urban contexts could contribute to several targets of Goal 11, especially target 11.6 about reducing the environmental impact of cities and target 11.A on the economic, social and environmental link between urban, peri-urban and rural areas. Another component of Goal 11 appearing in target 11.4 relates to the protection of the world's cultural and natural heritage, which are both closely interlinked as this assessment demonstrates: many cultures around the world are built around their relationship with nature, and their use of it. Likewise, many features of the world's natural heritage are influenced by people's use of nature (Brondizio *et al.*, 2021; Ellis *et al.*, 2021).

The sustainable use of wild species is at the very core of Goal 14 for marine resources and of Goal 15 for terrestrial and aquatic species. Sustainable use of wild species will contribute to and benefit from the sustainable management of ecosystems (see Chapter 2). More generally, it will contribute to biodiversity conservation efforts. Efforts towards conservation and sustainable use of wild species and against drivers of unsustainable use are directly mentioned in 13 out of the 16 targets assessed. Nine of those targets were to be met by 2020, as they reflected the Aichi Biodiversity Targets adopted as part of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020. As highlighted by the IPBES global assessment and the 5th edition of the Global Biodiversity Outlook (CBD, 2020), those targets were not met. There is therefore a great need for reinforcing the sustainable use of wild species across the globe, so that it can deliver its potential for biodiversity conservation. All relevant targets for sustainable use in Goal 14 and 15 are

addressed by the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species, including through its analysis of non-extractive uses. For example, target 14.7 includes sea-based tourism as a development pathway, especially for Small Islands Developing States. While sustainable use of wild species will necessarily contribute to the targets related to sustainable management, conservation of biodiversity and phasing out of subsidies leading to overexploitation (mentioned only in target 14.6 for fishing), it should be noted that illegal, unreported and unregulated uses targeted in 14.4 and 15.7 are not in all cases unsustainable (although they often reflect a lack of efficient governance which often leads to unsustainable use), just as legal uses are not in all cases sustainable (see Chapter 4). Progress towards Goals 14 and 15 could therefore take into account local practices, including which species are targeted, which ones are incidentally captured, how much is taken from the wild etc. to better inform regulations around uses. Species management will likely have to evolve under the influence of multiple drivers, such as climate change (see Chapter 5).

There is no target of Goal 16 on peace, justice and strong institutions that points to the sustainable use of wild species as a way forward. Impacts of armed conflicts on sustainable use are diverse and varied across contexts and through different direct and indirect pathways. Much evidence shows that illegal harvest of wild species has been used as a financial means by organized crime and armed conflict operations, while sustainable use practices offer more desirable alternatives to the populations. The end of armed conflicts and return of peace often provide opportunities for local and rural communities, however unregulated uses due to lack of governmental control in previously inaccessible regions pose significant risks to sustainable use. Inclusion of local communities in the management of natural resources in post-conflict areas improves governmental control and promotes the sustainable use of resources (see Chapter 4). As further evidenced by this assessment, sustainable use can also support better decision-making, by giving a voice and weight to communities that are otherwise missing from decision-making processes.

Target 17.14 of the Sustainable Development Goal on partnerships for the Goals is on enhancing policy coherence for sustainable development. As evidenced throughout this analysis of the actual and potential contributions of sustainable use of wild species to the Sustainable Development Goals, sustainable use of wild species can be an entry point for many policies related to sustainable development, both in developed and developing countries. Since it relates to so many Sustainable Development Goals, a successful policy for sustainable use of wild species would increase overall policy coherence. Indicators for the sustainable use of wild species are still lacking for many social dimensions (see Chapter 2). Working on those could contribute to target 17.19 on measuring progress

toward sustainable development. Those two points are the main contributions that sustainable use of wild species can make to Goal 17, but other targets related to international cooperation on and access to science (17.6), the development and transfer of environmentally sound technologies (17.7), the increase of the contribution of developing countries to global trade (17.11) and the creation of public, public-private and civil society partnerships (17.17) would benefit from it as well.

REFERENCES

- Abensperg-Traun, M. (2009). CITES, sustainable use of wild species and incentive-driven conservation in developing countries, with an emphasis on southern Africa. *Biological Conservation*, 142(5), 948–963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.12.034>
- Allan, J. D., Abell, R., Hogan, Z., Revenga, C., Taylor, B. W., Welcomme, R. L., & Winemiller, K. (2005). Overfishing of Inland Waters. *BioScience*, 55(12), 1041–1051. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2005\)055\[1041:OOIW\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2005)055[1041:OOIW]2.0.CO;2)
- Allen, C. M., & Edwards, S. R. (1995). The sustainable-use debate: Observations from IUCN. *Oryx*, 29(2), 92–98. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605300020950>
- Anderson, M. K. (2013). *Tending the wild: Native American knowledge and the management of California's natural resources*. University of California Press.
- Anthony, B. P., & Bellinger, E. G. (2007). Importance value of landscapes, flora and fauna to Tsongo communities in the rural areas of Limpopo province, South Africa. *South African Journal of Science*, 103, 148–154.
- Banerjee, A., Doxey, A. C., Mossman, K., & Irving, A. T. (2021). Unraveling the Zoonotic Origin and Transmission of SARS-CoV-2. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 36(3), 180–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2020.12.002>
- Barthel, S., Svedin, U., & Crumley, C. (2013). Bio-cultural refugia—Safeguarding diversity of practices for food security and biodiversity. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(5), 1142–1152. <https://doi.org/10.17615/P389-W730>
- Basurto, X., Franz, N., Mills, D. J., Virdin, J., Westlund, L., & Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Eds.). (2017). *Improving our knowledge on small-scale fisheries: Data needs and methodologies : workshop proceedings, 27-29 June 2017, FAO, Rome, Italy* (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations).
- Bazeley, M. L. (1921). The Extent of the English Forest in the Thirteenth Century. *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, 4, 140–159. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3678331>
- Bell, J. D., Bartley, D. M., Lorenzen, K., & Loneragan, N. R. (2006). Restocking and stock enhancement of coastal fisheries: Potential, problems and progress. *Fisheries Research*, 80(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2006.03.008>
- Béné, C., Macfadyen, G., & Allison, E. H. (2007). *Increasing the contribution of small-scale fisheries to poverty alleviation and food security*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Berkes, F. (2011). Restoring Unity: The Concept of Marine Social-Ecological Systems. In R. E. Ommen, R. I. Perry, K. Cochrane, & P. Cury (Eds.), *World Fisheries* (pp. 9–28). Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444392241.ch2>
- Berkes, F. (2018). *Sacred Ecology* (Fourth). Routledge.
- Berkes, F., Colding, J., & Folke, C. (2000). Rediscovery of Traditional Ecological Knowledge as Adaptive Management. *Ecological Applications*, 10(5), 1251–1262. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(2000\)010\[1251:ROTEKA\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(2000)010[1251:ROTEKA]2.0.CO;2)
- Berkes, Fikret., & Folke, Carl. (1998). *Linking social and ecological systems: Management practices and social mechanisms for building resilience*. Cambridge University Press. <https://www.cambridge.org/de/academic/subjects/life-sciences/ecology-and-conservation/linking-social-and-ecological-systems-management-practices-and-social-mechanisms-building-resilience?format=PB>
- Bhattacharyya, J., & Larson, B. M. H. (2014). The Need for Indigenous Voices in Discourse about Introduced Species: Insights from a Controversy over Wild Horses. *Environmental Values*, 23(6), 663–684. <https://doi.org/10.3197/096327114x13947900181031>
- Bouchard, O. (2020). *Protection de la nature et diversité ontologique chez Philippe Descola: Quelques enjeux et une possibilité de dépassement avec le contextualisme de Mark Hunyadi* [Université du Québec à Rimouski]. https://semaphore.uqar.ca/id/eprint/1828/1/Olivier_Bouchard_juillet2020.pdf
- Brashares, J. S., & Gaynor, K. M. (2017). Eating ecosystems, wildlife harvest and depletion compromise socioecological stability. *Science*, 356(6334), 136–137. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan0499>
- Brondízio, E. S., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bates, P., Carino, J., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Ferrari, M. F., Galvin, K., Reyes-García, V., McElwee, P., & Molnar, Z. (2021). Locally Based, Regionally Manifested, and Globally Relevant: Indigenous and Local Knowledge, Values, and Practices for Nature. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 46, 481–509.
- Carruthers, J. (2008). “Wilding the farm or farming the wild”? The evolution of scientific game ranching in South Africa from the 1960s to the present. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*, 63(2), 160–181.
- Carter, S. E., & Currie-Alder, B. (2006). Scaling-up natural resource management: Insights from research in Latin America. *Development in Practice*, 16(2), 128–140.
- Casini, M., Blenckner, T., Mollmann, C., Gardmark, A., Lindegren, M., Llope, M., Kornilovs, G., Plikshs, M., & Stenseth, N. C. (2012). Predator transitory spillover induces trophic cascades in ecological sinks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(21), 8185–8189. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1113286109>
- Catarino, S., Duarte, M., Costa, E., Carrero, P., & Romeiras, M. M. (2019). Conservation and sustainable use of the medicinal Leguminosae plants from Angola. *PeerJ*, 7, e6736. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6736>
- CBD. (2008). *Biodiversity Glossary*. <https://www.cbd.int/cepa/toolkit/2008/doc/CBD-Toolkit-Glossaries.pdf>
- CBD. (2020). *Global Biodiversity Outlook 5* (p. 211). <https://www.cbd.int/gbo/gbo5/publication/gbo-5-en.pdf>
- Chamberlain, J. L., Emery, Marla. R., & Patel-Weynard, Toral. (2018). *Assessment of Nontimber Forest Products in the United States Under Changing Conditions. A report for the United States Department of Agriculture. General Technical Report SRS-232. June*, 267. <https://doi.org/10.2737/SRS-GTR-232>
- Chapin, F. S., Kofinas, G. P., & Folke, C. (Eds.). (2009). *Principles of ecosystem stewardship: Resilience-based natural resource management in a changing world* (1st ed). Springer.

- Child, M. F., Roxburgh, L., Do Linh San, E., Raimondo, D., & Davies-Mostert, H. T. (Eds.). (2016). *The 2016 Red List of Mammals of South Africa, Swaziland and Lesotho*. South African National Biodiversity Institute and Endangered Wildlife Trust, South Africa. <https://www.ewt.org.za/resources/resources-mammal-red-list/>
- Child, M. F., Selier, S. J., Radloff, F. G., Taylor, W. A., Hoffmann, M., Nel, L., Power, J., Birss, C., Okes, N. C., & Peel, M. J. (2019). A framework to measure the wildness of managed large vertebrate populations. *Conservation Biology*.
- Cinner, J. E., & Aswani, S. (2007). Integrating customary management into marine conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 140(3–4), 201–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.08.008>
- Coad, L., Fa, J., Abernethy, K., van Vliet, N., Santamaria, C., Wilkie, D., El Bizri, H., Ingram, D., Cawthorn, D., & Nasi, R. (2019). *Towards a sustainable, participatory and inclusive wild meat sector*. CIFOR. <https://doi.org/10.17528/cifor/007046>
- Comberti, C., Thornton, T. F., Wyllie de Echeverria, V., & Patterson, T. (2015). Ecosystem services or services to ecosystems? *Global Environmental Change*, 34, 247–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.07.007>
- Cookson, L. J. (2011). A Definition for Wildness. *Ecopsychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2011.0028>
- Cooney, R. (2007). *Sustainable Use: Concepts, Ambiguities, Challenges* (p. 76). IUCN Species Survival Commission's Sustainable Use Specialist Group. <https://www.iucn.org/sites/dev/files/whiteoakmtgfinalbackgroundjuly07.pdf>
- Craigie, I. D., Baillie, J. E. M., Balmford, A., Carbone, C., Collen, B., Green, R. E., & Hutton, J. M. (2010). Large mammal population declines in Africa's protected areas. *Biological Conservation*, 143(9), 2221–2228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.06.007>
- Cromsigt, J. P., te Beest, M., Kerley, G. I., Landman, M., le Roux, E., & Smith, F. A. (2018). Trophic rewilding as a climate change mitigation strategy? *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 373(1761), 20170440.
- Cronon, W. (1996). The Trouble with Wilderness: Or, Getting Back to the Wrong Nature. *Environmental History*, 1(1), 7. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3985059>
- Cruzten, P. J., & Stoermer, E. F. (2000). The "Anthropocene." *Global Change Newsletter*, 41, 17–17.
- Cruz-Garcia. (2017). Management and motivations to manage "wild" food plants. A case study in a Mestizo village in the Amazon deforestation frontier. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 5, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2017.00127>
- Darwin, C. (1859). *On the origin of species by means of natural selection, or the preservation of favoured races in the struggle for life*. John Murray.
- Daskalov, G. M., Grishin, A. N., Rodionov, S., & Mihneva, V. (2007). Trophic cascades triggered by overfishing reveal possible mechanisms of ecosystem regime shifts. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(25), 10518–10523. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0701100104>
- Descartes, R. (1637). *Discours de la méthode*. Flammarion.
- Deur, D., & Turner, N. J. (2005). *Keeping It Living: Traditions of Plant Use and Cultivation on the Northwest Coast of North America*. University of Washington press.
- Diamond, A. K., & Emery, M. R. (2011). Black Ash (*Fraxinus nigra* Marsh.): Local Ecological Knowledge of Site Characteristics and Morphology Associated with Basket—Grade Specimens in New England (USA). *Economic Botany*, 65(4), 422–426.
- Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Carabias, J., Joly, C., Lonsdale, M., Ash, N., Larigauderie, A., Adhikari, J. R., Arico, S., Báldi, A., Bartuska, A., Baste, I. A., Bilgin, A., Brondizio, E., Chan, K. M., Figueiroa, V. E., Duraipappah, A., Fischer, M., Hill, R., ... Zlatanova, D. (2015a). The IPBES Conceptual Framework—Connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 14, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2014.11.002>
- Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Joly, C., Lonsdale, W. M., & Larigauderie, A. (2015b). A Rosetta Stone for nature's benefits to people. *PLoS Biology*, 13(1), e1002040. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002040>
- Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martín-López, B., Watson, R. T., Molnár, Z., Hill, R., Chan, K. M. A., Baste, I. A., Brauman, K. A., Polasky, S., Church, A., Lonsdale, M., Larigauderie, A., Leadley, P. W., van Oudenhoven, A. P. E., van der Plaats, F., Schröter, M., Lavorel, S., ... Shirayama, Y. (2018). Assessing nature's contributions to people. *Science*, 359(6373), 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>
- Ellis, E., Gauthier, N., Goldewijk, K., Bird, R., Boivin, N., Diaz, S., Fuller, D., Gill, J., Kaplan, J., Kingston, N., Locke, H., McMichael, C., Ranco, D., Rick, T., Shaw, M., Stephens, L., Svenning, J., & Watson, J. (2021). People have shaped most of terrestrial nature for at least 12,000 years. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118(17). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2023483118>
- Emery, M. R., Wrobel, A., Hansen, M. H., Dockry, M., Moser, W. K., Stark, K. J., & Gilbert, J. H. (2014). Using traditional ecological knowledge as a basis for targeted forest inventories: Paper birch (*Betula papyrifera*) in the US Great Lakes region. *Journal of Forestry*, 112(2), 207–214.
- Ernst, B., Chamorro, J., Manríquez, P., Orensanz, J. L., Parma, A. M., Porobic, J., & Román, C. (2013). Sustainability of the Juan Fernández lobster fishery (Chile) and the perils of generic science-based prescriptions. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(6), 1381–1392.
- Fa, J. E., Seymour, S., Dupain, J., Amin, R., Albrechtsen, L., & Macdonald, D. (2006). Getting to grips with the magnitude of exploitation: Bushmeat in the Cross–Sanaga rivers region, Nigeria and Cameroon. *Biological Conservation*, 129(4), 497–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2005.11.031>
- Fabbio, G. (2016). Coppice forests, or the changeable aspect of things, a review. *Annals of Silvicultural Research*, 40(2). <https://doi.org/10.12899/asr-1286>
- FAO. (1995). *Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO. (2001). *Fisheries Glossary*. Retrieved January 24, 2019, from <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/collection/fisheries/en/>.
- FAO. (2004). *Report of the Second session of the Working Party on Small-Scale Fisheries: Bangkok, Thailand, 18 - 21 November 2003*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Advisory Committee on Fisheries Research.
- FAO. (2015). *Voluntary guidelines for securing sustainable small-scale fisheries in the context of food security and poverty eradication*. FAO. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i4356en.pdf>

- FAO. (2016). *Free, prior and informed consent: An Indigenous peoples' right and a good practice for local communities: Manual for project practitioners* (p. 52). United Nations Food & Agriculture Organization. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i6190e.pdf>
- FAO. (2018a). *FAO Term Portal*. Retrieved November 28, 2018, from <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>.
- FAO. (2018b). *The State of the world's forests 2018—Forests pathways to sustainable development*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO. (2018c). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2018—Meeting the sustainable development goals*. FAO Rome, Italy. <http://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/19540EN/>
- FAO. (2019). *The state of the world's biodiversity for food and agriculture* (p. 572). Commission on Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. <http://www.fao.org/3/CA3129EN/CA3129EN.pdf>
- FAO. (2020a). *Global Forest Resources Assessment (FRA) 2020: Main report*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/ca8753en/>
- FAO. (2020b). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229enAlso> Available in: Chinese Spanish Arabic French Russian
- FAO, & EFI. (2018). *Making forest concessions in the tropics work to achieve the 2030 Agenda: Voluntary Guidelines* (No. 180; FAO Forestry Paper, p. 128). <https://www.fao.org/forestry/46348-01f3c79fdbca80c72eaf3f1ee5b6f83fb.pdf>
- FAO, & UNEP. (2020). *The State of the World's Forests 2020: Forests, Biodiversity and People*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca8642en>
- Ferreira, B., Rice, J., & Rosenberg, A. (2016). Chapter 10. The Oceans as a Source of Food. In *The First Global Integrated Marine Assessment. World Ocean Assessment I* (United Nations, p. 12). https://www.un.org/depts/los/global_reporting/WOA_RPROC/Chapter_10.pdf
- Fletcher, M.-S., Hamilton, R., Dressler, W., & Palmer, L. (2021). Indigenous knowledge and the shackles of wilderness. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(40), e2022218118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2022218118>
- Fluet-Chouinard, E., Funge-Smith, S., & McIntyre, P. B. (2018). Global hidden harvest of freshwater fish revealed by household surveys. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(29), 7623–7628. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1721097115>
- Ford, R. I. (1985). *Prehistoric food production in North America: Vol. No. 75*. The Regents of the University of Michigan.
- Forest Peoples Program. (2021a). *COVID-19 and indigenous and tribal peoples: The impacts and underlying inequalities* (p. 44). Forest Peoples Program.
- Forest Peoples Program. (2021b). *Rolling back social and environmental safeguards in the time of COVID-19: The dangers for indigenous peoples and for tropical forests* (p. 65) [Discussion Paper]. Forest Peoples Program.
- Forest Peoples Program, International Indigenous Forum on Biodiversity, Indigenous Women's Biodiversity Network, Centres of Distinction on Indigenous and Local Knowledge, & CBD. (2020). *Local Biodiversity Outlooks 2: The contributions of indigenous peoples and local communities to the implementation of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and to renewing nature and cultures. A complement to the fifth edition of Global Biodiversity Outlook*. Forest Peoples Programme. www.localbiodiversityoutlooks.net
- Frey, G. E., Cabbage, F. W., Holmes, T. P., Reyes-Retana, G., Davis, R. R., Megevard, C., Rodríguez-Paredes, D., Kraus-Elsin, Y., Hernández-Toro, B., & Chemor-Salas, D. N. (2019). Competitiveness, certification, and support of timber harvest by community forest enterprises in Mexico. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 107, 101923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.05.009>
- Fromentin, J.-M., Bonhommeau, S., Arrizabalaga, H., & Kell, L. T. (2014). The spectre of uncertainty in management of exploited fish stocks: The illustrative case of Atlantic bluefin tuna. *Marine Policy*, 47, 8–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.01.018>
- Garcia, S. M. (1996). The precautionary approach to fisheries and its implications for fishery research, technology and management: And updated review. In *Precautionary approach to fisheries. Part 2: Scientific papers. Prepared for the Technical Consultation on the Precautionary Approach to Capture Fisheries (Including Species Introductions)* (FAO, Vol. 2). <https://www.fao.org/3/W1238E/W1238E01.htm#ch1>
- Garcia, S. M., Allison, E., Andrew, N., Béné, C., Bianchi, G., de Graaf, G., Kalikoski, D., Mahon, R., & Orensanz, L. (2008). *Towards integrated assessment and advice in small-scale fisheries: Principles and processes*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Garibaldi, A., & Turner, N. (2004). Cultural keystone species: Implications for ecological conservation and restoration. *Ecology & Society*, 9(3), Article 1.
- Garnett, S. T., Burgess, N. D., Fa, J. E., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Molnár, Z., Robinson, C. J., Watson, J. E. M., Zander, K. K., Austin, B., Brondizio, E. S., Collier, N. F., Duncan, T., Ellis, E., Geyle, H., Jackson, M. V., Jonas, H., Malmer, P., McGowan, B., Sivongxay, A., & Leiper, I. (2018). A spatial overview of the global importance of Indigenous lands for conservation. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(7), 369–374. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0100-6>
- Gelcich, S., Edwards-Jones, G., Kaiser, M. J., & Castilla, J. C. (2006). Co-management Policy Can Reduce Resilience in Traditionally Managed Marine Ecosystems. *Ecosystems*, 9, 951–966. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-005-0007-8>
- Gentry, A., Clutton-Brock, J., & Groves, C. P. (2004). The naming of wild animal species and their domestic derivatives. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 31(5), 645–651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2003.10.006>
- Glacken, C. J. (1976). *Traces on the Rhodian shore*. University of California Press.
- GLIFWC. (n.d.). *Manoomin Wild Rice. The Good Berry*. Retrieved February 25, 2022, from https://glifwc.org/publications/pdf/Goodberry_Brochure.pdf
- Golden, C. D., Allison, E. H., Cheung, W. W. L., Dey, M. M., Halpern, B. S., McCauley, D. J., Smith, M., Vaitla, B., Zeller, D., & Myers, S. S. (2016). Nutrition: Fall in fish catch threatens human health. *Nature*, 534(7607), 317–320. <https://doi.org/10.1038/534317a>
- Gorenflo, L. J., Romaine, S., Mittermeier, R. A., & Walker-Painemilla, K. (2012). Co-occurrence of linguistic and biological diversity in biodiversity hotspots and high biodiversity wilderness areas. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(21), 8032–8037.

- Gulbrandsen, L. H., & Humphreys, D. (2006). *International Initiatives to address tropical timber logging and trade* (No. 4/2006; p. 67). Fridtjof Nansen Institute.
- Haraway, D. J. (2003). *The companion species manifesto: Dogs, people, and significant otherness* (Vol. 1). Prickly Paradigm Press Chicago.
- Hayward, M. W., Child, M. F., Kerley, G. I. H., Lindsey, P. A., Somers, M. J., & Burns, B. (2015). Ambiguity in guideline definitions introduces assessor bias and influences consistency in IUCN Red List status assessments. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2015.00087>
- Hilborn, R., Amoroso, R. O., Anderson, C. M., Baum, J. K., Branch, T. A., Costello, C., de Moor, C. L., Faraj, A., Hively, D., Jensen, O. P., Kurota, H., Little, L. R., Mace, P., McClanahan, T., Melnychuk, M. C., Minto, C., Osio, G. C., Parma, A. M., Pons, M., ... Ye, Y. (2020). Effective fisheries management instrumental in improving fish stock status. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(4), 2218–2224. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1909726116>
- Hilborn, R., & Hilborn, U. (2019). *Ocean Recovery: A sustainable future for global fisheries?* Oxford University Press.
- HLPE. (2017). *Sustainable forestry for food security and nutrition: A report by the High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security* (Report of the High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition HLPE Report 11; HLPE Report Series, p. 136). Food and Agriculture Organization. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i7395e.pdf>
- Hoffmann, B. D., & Courchamp, F. (2016). Biological invasions and natural colonisations: Are they that different? *NeoBiota*, 29, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.29.6959>
- Hoffmann, R. C. (2005). A brief history of aquatic resource use in medieval Europe. *Helgoland Marine Research*, 59(1), 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10152-004-0203-5>
- Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General. (2019). *Global Sustainable Development Report 2019: The Future is Now – Science for Achieving Sustainable Development* (p. 252). United Nations. https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/24797GSDR_report_2019.pdf
- INTOSAI WGEA. (2013). *Impact of Tourism on Wildlife Conservation* (p. 44). http://iced.cag.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/2013_wgea_Wild-Life_view.pdf
- IPBES. (2016). *Summary for policymakers of the assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services on pollinators, pollination and food production*. (S.G. Potts, V. L. Imperatriz-Fonseca, H. T. Ngo, J. C. Biesmeijer, T. D. Breeze, L. V. Dicks, L. A. Garibaldi, R. Hill, J. Settele, A. J. Vanbergen, M. A. Aizen, S. A. Cunningham, C. Eardley, B. M. Freitas, N. Gallai, P. G. Kevan, A. Kovács-Hostyánszki, P. K. Kwapong, J. Li, ... B. F. Viana, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. https://www.ipbes.net/sites/default/files/spm_deliverable_3a_pollination_20170222.pdf
- IPBES. (2018a). *Summary for policymakers of the regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Africa of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (E. Archer, L. E. Dziba, K. J. Mulongoy, M. A. Maela, M. Walters, R. Biggs, M.-C. Cormier-Salem, F. DeClerck, M. C. Diaw, A. E. Dunham, P. Failler, C. Gordon, K. A. Harhash, R. Kasisi, F. Kizito, W. D. Nyingi, N. Oguge, B. Osman-Elasha, L. C. Stringer, ... N. Sitas, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3236178>
- IPBES. (2018b). *Summary for policymakers of the regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Asia and the Pacific of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (M. Karki, S. Senaratna Sellamuttu, S. Okayasu, W. Suzuki, L. A. Acosta, Y. Alhafedh, J. A. Anticamara, A. G. Ausseil, K. Davies, A. Gasparatos, H. Gundimeda, I. Faridah-Hanum, R. Kohsaka, R. Kumar, S. Managi, N. Wu, A. Rajvanshi, G. S. Rawat, P. Riordan, ... Y. C. Youn, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237373>
- IPBES. (2018c). *Summary for policymakers of the regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Europe and Central Asia of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (N. E. Z. M. Fischer, M. Rounsevell, A. Torre-Marín Rando, A. Mader, A. Church, M. Elbakidze, V. Elias, T. Hahn, P.A. Harrison, J. Hauck, B. Martín-López, I. Ring, C. Sandström, I. Sousa Pinto, P. Visconti & M. Christie, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237428>
- IPBES. (2018d). *Summary for policymakers of the regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for the Americas of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (J. Rice, C.S. Seixas, M.E. Zaccagnini, M. Bedoya-Gaitán, N. Valderrama, C.B. Anderson, M.T.K. Arroyo, M. Bustamante, J. Cavender-Bares, A. Diaz-de-Leon, S. Fennessy, J. R. García Márquez, K. Garcia, E.H. Helmer, B. Herrera, B. Klatt, J.P. Omoto, V. Rodríguez Osuna, F.R. Scarano, ... J. S. Farinaci, Eds.). IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3236252>
- IPBES. (2018e). *The IPBES assessment report on Land Degradation and Restoration* (L. Montanarella, R. Scholes, & A. Brainich, Eds.). Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237392>
- IPBES. (2019a). *Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES Secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>
- IPBES. (2019b). *Report of the first ILK dialogue workshop for the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species, held in Paris, France, on 6-7 May 2019*. (p. 53). UNESCO.
- IPBES. (2019c). *Report of the ILK dialogue workshop for the first order draft of the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species, held in Montreal, Canada, on 8-9 October 2019*. (p. 40). UNESCO. https://ipbes.net/sites/default/files/inline-files/IPBES_SusUse_2ndILKDialogue_Report_final_forWeb_0.pdf
- IPBES. (2020). *Workshop Report on Biodiversity and Pandemics of the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)* (1.3). IPBES secretariat. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4147317>
- IPBES. (2021a). *DRAFT - Methodological guidance for recognizing and working with indigenous and local knowledge in IPBES*. IPBES. https://ipbes.net/sites/default/files/inline-files/IPBES_ILK_MethGuide.pdf
- IPBES. (2021b). *Report of the ILK dialogue workshop for the draft summary for policymakers and second order draft of the IPBES assessment of the sustainable use of wild species. Online, 17-21 May 2021*. UNESCO.

- IPCC. (2019a). Summary for Policymakers. In P. R. Shukla, J. Skea, E. Calvo Buendia, V. Masson-Delmotte, H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, P. Zhai, R. Slade, S. Connors, R. van Diemen, M. Ferrat, E. Haughey, S. Luz, S. Neogi, M. Pathak, J. Petzold, J. Portugal Pereira, P. Vyas, E. Huntley, ... J. Malley (Eds.), *Climate Change and Land: An IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems* (p. 36).
- IPCC. (2019b). Summary for Policymakers. In H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, M. Tignor, E. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Nicolai, A. Okem, J. Petzold, B. Rama, & N. M. Weyer (Eds.), *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* (p. 35).
- IUCN. (2021a). *IUCN Glossary of Definitions*. <https://www.iucn.org/resources/publications/publishing-iucn>
- IUCN. (2021b). *The IUCN Red List Data*. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. <https://www.iucnredlist.org/en>
- IUCN Standards and Petitions Committee. (2019). *Guidelines for Using the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria. Version 14*. IUCN Standards and Petitions Committee. <http://www.iucnredlist.org/documents/RedListGuidelines.pdf>
- IUFRO. (2018). *Glossary of wildlife management terms and definitions*. IUFRO. <https://www.iufro.org/fileadmin/material/science/spps/silvavoc/wildlife-glossary.pdf>
- Jenkins, M., Timoshyna, A., & Cornthwaite, M. (2018). *Wild at Home. Exploring the global harvest, trade and use of wild plant ingredients* (Traffic Report, p. 43). TRAFFIC International.
- Johnson, A., Clavijo, A. E., Hamar, G., Head, D.-A., Thoms, A., Price, W., Lapke, A., Crotteau, J., Cervený, L. K., Wilmer, H., Petershoare, L., Cook, A., & Reid, S. (2021). Wood Products for Cultural Uses: Sustaining Native Resilience and Vital Lifeways in Southeast Alaska, USA. *Forests*, 12(1), 90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12010090>
- Kimmerer, R. W. (2000). Native knowledge for native forests. *Journal of Forestry*, 98(8), 4–9.
- Kurien, J., & Willmann, R. (2009). Special Considerations for Small-Scale Fisheries Management in Developing Countries. In K. L. Cochrane & S. M. Garcia (Eds.), *A Fishery Manager's Guidebook* (pp. 404–424). Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444316315.ch15>
- Lam, V. Y. Y., & Sadovy de Mitcheson, Y. (2011). The sharks of South East Asia - unknown, unmonitored and unmanaged: Sharks of South East Asia. *Fish and Fisheries*, 12(1), 51–74. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2010.00383.x>
- Latour, B. (1993). *We Have Never Been Modern*. Harvard University Press.
- Latour, B. (2004). *Politics of Nature*. Harvard University Press.
- Leopold, A. (1949). *A Sand County Almanac And Sketches Here and There* (First). Oxford University Press.
- Lepofsky, D., & Caldwell, M. (2013). Indigenous marine resource management on the Northwest Coast of North America. *Ecological Processes*, 2(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-1709-2-12>
- Leslie, H. M., Basurto, X., Nenadovic, M., Sievanen, L., Cavanaugh, K. C., Cota-Nieto, J. J., Erisman, B. E., Finkbeiner, E., Hinojosa-Arango, G., Moreno-Báez, M., Nagavarapu, S., Reddy, S. M. W., Sánchez-Rodríguez, A., Siegel, K., Ulibarria-Valenzuela, J. J., Weaver, A. H., & Aburto-Oropeza, O. (2015). Operationalizing the social-ecological systems framework to assess sustainability. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(19), 5979–5984. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1414640112>
- Levis, C., Costa, F. R. C., Bongers, F., Pena-Claros, M., Clement, C. R., Junqueira, A. B., Neves, E. G., Tamanaha, E. K., Figueiredo, F. O. G., Salomao, R. P., Castilho, C. V., Magnusson, W. E., Phillips, O. L., Guevara, J. E., Sabatier, D., Molino, J.-F., Lopez, D. C., Mendoza, A. M., Pitman, N. C. A., ... ter Steege, H. (2017). Persistent effects of pre-Columbian plant domestication on Amazonian forest composition. In *Science* (Vol. 355, Issue 6328, p. 925+). Amer Assoc Advancement Science. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal0157>
- Lichtenstein, G., & Vilá, B. (2003). Vicuna Use by Andean Communities: An Overview. *Mountain Research and Development*, 23(2), 198–201. [https://doi.org/10.1659/0276-4741\(2003\)023\[0197:VU BACA\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1659/0276-4741(2003)023[0197:VU BACA]2.0.CO;2)
- Lorenzen, K., Amarasinghe, U. S., Bartley, D. M., Bell, J. D., Billo, M., de Silva, S. S., Garaway, C. J., Hartmann, W. D., Kapetsky, J. M., Laleye, P., Moreau, J., Sugunan, V., & Swar, D. B. (2000). Strategic Review of Enhancements and Culture-based Fisheries. In *Aquaculture in the Third Millennium. Technical Proceedings of the Conference on Aquaculture in the Third Millennium, Bangkok, Thailand*. (pp. 221–237).
- Lorimer, J. (2015). *Wildlife in the Anthropocene: Conservation after Nature*. University of Minnesota Press. <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/39521>
- Ma, T., Hu, Y., Wang, M., Yu, L., & Wei, F. (2021). Unity of Nature and Man: A new vision and conceptual framework for the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. *National Science Review*, 8(7), nwa265. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwaa265>
- Maffi, L. (2005). Linguistic, cultural, and biological diversity. *Annu. Rev. Anthropol.*, 34, 599–617.
- Mahapatra, A., & Mitchell, C. P. (1997). Sustainable development of non-timber forest products: Implication for forest management in India. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 94(1–3), 15–29. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(97\)00001-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(97)00001-7)
- Mahoney, S. P. (Ed.). (2019). *The North American model of wildlife conservation*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Mallon, D. P., & Stanley Price, M. R. (2013). The fall of the wild. *Oryx*, 47(4), 467–468. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S003060531300121X>
- Maris, V. (2018). *La part sauvage du monde: Penser la nature dans l'Anthropocène*. Éditions du Seuil.
- Mathews, D. L., & Turner, N. J. (2017). Ocean Cultures: Northwest Coast Ecosystems and Indigenous Management Systems. In *Conservation for the Anthropocene Ocean* (pp. 169–206). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805375-1.00009-X>
- Matson, L., Ng, G.-H. C., Dockry, M., Nyblade, M., King, H. J., Bellcourt, M., Bloomquist, J., Bunting, P., Chapman, E., Dalbotten, D., Davenport, M. A., Diver, K., Duquain, M., Graveen, W. (Joe), Hagsten, K., Hedin, K., Howard, S., Howes, T., Johnson, J., ... Waheed, A. (2021). Transforming research and relationships through collaborative tribal-university partnerships on Manoomin (wild rice). *Environmental Science & Policy*, 115, 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.10.010>

- Mattalia, G., Soukand, R., Corvo, P., & Pieroni, A. (2020). Wild Food Thistle Gathering and Pastoralism: An Inextricable Link in the Biocultural Landscape of Barbagia, Central Sardinia (Italy). *Sustainability*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12125105>
- Mattalia, G., Volpato, G., Corvo, P., & Pieroni, A. (2018). Interstitial but Resilient: Nomadic Shepherds in Piedmont (Northwest Italy) Amidst Spatial and Social Marginalization. *Human Ecology*, 46(5), 747–757. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-018-0024-9>
- McCarty, S., Nicholas, S. E., & Wigglesworth, G. (2019). *A world of Indigenous languages: Politics, pedagogies and prospects for language reclamation* (Vol. 17). Springer Nature Switzerland.
- McDermott, C. L., O'Carroll, A., & Wood, P. (2007). *International Forest Policy- the instruments, agreements and processes that shape it* (p. 131). Department of Economic and Social Affairs- United Nations Forum on Forests Secretariat.
- Millenium Ecosystem Assessment. (2005). *Ecosystems and Human Well-being: Policy Responses, Volume 3*. <https://www.millenniumassessment.org/documents/document.772.aspx.pdf>
- Minnis, P. E., & Elisens, W. J. (2000). *Biodiversity and Native America*. University of Oklahoma Press.
- Mkono, M. (2019). Neo-colonialism and greed: Africans' views on trophy hunting in social media. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 27(5), 689–704. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2019.1604719>
- Mueller-Dombois, D. (2007). The Hawaiian Ahupua'a Land Use System: Its Biological Resource Zones and the Challenge for Silvicultural Restoration. *Bishop Museum Bulletin in Cultural and Environmental Studies*, 3, 23–33.
- Mueller-Dombois, D., & Wirawan, N. (2005). The Kahana Valley Ahupua'a, a PABITRA Study Site on O'ahu, Hawaiian Islands. *Pacific Science*, 59(2), 293–314.
- Muir, G. F., Sorrenti, S., Vantomme, P., Vidale, E., & Masiero, M. (2020). Into the wild: Disentangling non-wood terms and definitions for improved forest statistics. *International Forestry Review*, 22(1), 101–119. <https://doi.org/10.1505/146554820828671553>
- Mutumukuru, T., Kozanayi, W., & Nyirenda, R. (2007). Initiating a dynamic process for monitoring in Mafungautsi State Forest, Zimbabwe. In *Negotiated learning: Collaborative monitoring in forest resource management*. Resources For the Future.
- Nadasdy, P. (2007). The gift in the animal: The ontology of hunting and human-animal sociality. *American Ethnologist*, 34(1), 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.2007.34.1.25>
- Nelson, M. P., & Callicott, J. B. (2008). *The Wilderness Debate Rages On: Continuing The Great New Wilderness Debate*. The University of Georgia Press.
- Neumann, R. P. (1998). *Imposing Wilderness: Struggles Over Livelihood and Nature Preservation in Africa*. University of California Press.
- Odum, E. P. (1953). *Fundamentals of ecology*. W. B. Saunders Company.
- Ostrom, E. (2009). A General Framework for Analyzing Sustainability of Social-Ecological Systems. *Science*, 325(5939), 419–422. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1172133>
- Pacoureaux, N., Rigby, C. L., Kyne, P. M., Sherley, R. B., Winker, H., Carlson, J. K., Fordham, S. V., Barreto, R., Fernando, D., Francis, M. P., Jabado, R. W., Herman, K. B., Liu, K.-M., Marshall, A. D., Pollom, R. A., Romanov, E. V., Simpfendorfer, C. A., Yin, J. S., Kindsvater, H. K., & Dulvy, N. K. (2021). Half a century of global decline in oceanic sharks and rays. *Nature*, 589(7843), 567–571. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-03173-9>
- Palkovacs, E. P., Moritsch, M. M., Contolini, G. M., & Pelletier, F. (2018). Ecology of harvest-driven trait changes and implications for ecosystem management. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 16(1), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1743>
- Palmer, C. (2011). *The Moral Relevance of the Distinction Between Domesticated and Wild Animals*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195371963.013.0026>
- Parma, A. M., Hilborn, R., & Orensanz, J. M. (2006). The good, the bad, and the ugly: Learning from experience to achieve sustainable fisheries. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 3(78), 411–427.
- Parsons, E. C. M., & Brown, D. M. (2017). Recent Advances in Whale-Watching Research: 2015–2016. *Tourism in Marine Environments*, 12(2), 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.3727/154427317X694728>
- Peace, A. (2010). The whaling war: Conflicting cultural perspectives. *Anthropology Today*, 26(3), 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8322.2010.00734.x>
- Peacock, S. L., & Turner, N. J. (2000). "Just Like A Garden:" Traditional Resource Management and Biodiversity Conservation on the Interior Plateau of British Columbia. In P. E. Minnis & W. J. Elisens (Eds.), *Biodiversity and Native America* (pp. 133–179). University of Oklahoma Press.
- Plumwood, V. (2002). *Environmental Culture: The Ecological Crisis of Reason*. Routledge.
- Polfus, J. L., Manseau, M., Simmons, D., Neyelle, M., Bayha, W., Andrew, F., Andrew, L., Klütsch, C. F. C., Rice, K., & Wilson, P. (2016). Łeghągots'eneṭę (learning together): The importance of indigenous perspectives in the identification of biological variation. *Ecology and Society*, 21(2), art18. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08284-210218>
- Prescott-Allen, R., & Prescott-Allen, C. (1996). *Assessing the sustainability of uses of wild species: Case studies and initial assessment procedure*. IUCN.
- Pretty, J., Adams, B., Berkes, F., de Athayde, S. F., Dudley, N., Hunn, E., Maffi, L., Milton, K., Rapport, D., Robbins, P., Sterling, E., Stolton, S., Tsing, A., Vintinner, E., & Pilgrim, S. (2009). The Intersections of Biological Diversity and Cultural Diversity: Towards Integration. *Conservation and Society*, 7(2), 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-4923.58642>
- Pullanikkatil, D., & Shackleton, C. (Eds.). (2019). *Poverty reduction through non-timber forest products: Personal stories* (Ed. Deepa Pullanikkatil, Charlie M. Shackleton editors). Springer.
- Purvis, B., Mao, Y., & Robinson, D. (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: In search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science*, 14(3), 681–695. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5>
- Redford, K. H., Amato, G., Baillie, J., Beldomenico, P., Bennett, E. L., Cium, N., Cook, R., Fonseca, G., Hedges, S., Launay, F., Lieberman, S., Mace, G. M., Murayama, A., Putnam, A., Robinson, J. G., Rosenbaum, H., Sanderson, E. W., Stuart, S. N., Thomas, P., & Thorbjarnarson, J. (2011). What Does It Mean to Successfully Conserve a (Vertebrate) Species? *BioScience*, 61(1), 39–48. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.1.9>
- Reo, N. J., & Whyte, K. P. (2012). Hunting and morality as elements of traditional ecological knowledge. *Human Ecology*, 40, 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-011-9448-1>

- Rice, J. (2014). Evolution of international commitments for fisheries sustainability. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 71(2), 157–165. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fst078>
- Richerson, P. J., Gavrillets, S., & de Waal, F. B. M. (2021). Modern theories of human evolution foreshadowed by Darwin's Descent of Man. *Science*, 372(6544), eaba3776. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba3776>
- Robinson, D. F., & Raven, M. (2019). Ethical Trade in Natural Products based on Traditional Knowledge. *Trade For Development News*. <https://trade4devnews.enhancedif.org/en/news/ethical-trade-natural-products-based-traditional-knowledge>
- Román-Palacios, C., & Wiens, J. J. (2020). Recent responses to climate change reveal the drivers of species extinction and survival. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(8), 4211–4217. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1913007117>
- Russell, R., Guerry, A. D., Balvanera, P., Gould, R. K., Basurto, X., Chan, K. M., Klain, S., Levine, J., & Tam, J. (2013). Humans and nature: How knowing and experiencing nature affect well-being. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 38, 473–502. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012312-110838>
- Sandifer, P. A., Sutton-Grier, A. E., & Ward, B. P. (2015). Exploring connections among nature, biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human health and well-being: Opportunities to enhance health and biodiversity conservation. *Ecosystem Services*, 12, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.12.007>
- Sangha, K. K., Le Brocque, A., Costanza, R., & Cadet-James, Y. (2015). Ecosystems and indigenous well-being: An integrated framework. *Global Ecology and Conservation*, 4, 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2015.06.008>
- Sasaoka, M., & Laumonier, Y. (2012). Suitability of Local Resource Management Practices Based on Supernatural Enforcement Mechanisms in the Local Social-cultural Context. *Ecology and Society*, 17(4), 10.
- Savilaakso, S., Johansson, A., Häkkinen, M., Uusitalo, A., Sandgren, T., Mönkkönen, M., & Puttonen, P. (2021). What are the effects of even-aged and uneven-aged forest management on boreal forest biodiversity in Fennoscandia and European Russia? A systematic review. *Environmental Evidence*, 10(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-020-00215-7>
- Schäfer, D., Siebert, M., & Sterckx, R. (2018). Knowing Animals in China's History: An Introduction. In *Animals through Chinese History* (1st ed., pp. 1–19). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108551571.002>
- Scheiner, S. M., & Mindell, D. P. (Eds.). (2020). *The theory of evolution: Principles, concepts, and assumptions*. The University of Chicago Press.
- Schlesinger, W. H. (2018). Are wood pellets a green fuel? *Science*, 359(6382), 1328–1329. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat2305>
- Singh, G. G., Harden-Davies, H., Allison, E. H., Cisneros-Montemayor, A. M., Swartz, W., Crosman, K. M., & Ota, Y. (2021). Will understanding the ocean lead to “the ocean we want”? *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(5), e2100205118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2100205118>
- Spinu, M., Spinu, O., & Degen, A. A. (1999). Haematological and immunological variables in a domesticated and wild subspecies of ostrich (*Struthio camelus*). *British Poultry Science*, 40(5), 613–618. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071669986981>
- Spooner, D., Hettterscheid, W., L. A., van den Berg, R., G., & Brandenburg, W. (2003). Plant Nomenclature and Taxonomy An Horticultural and Agronomic Perspective. *Horticultural Reviews*, 28, 1–60.
- Steffen, W., Persson, Å., Deutsch, L., Zalasiewicz, J., Williams, M., Richardson, K., Crumley, C., Crutzen, P., Folke, C., Gordon, L., Molina, M., Ramanathan, V., Rockström, J., Scheffer, M., Schellnhuber, H. J., & Svedin, U. (2011). The Anthropocene: From Global Change to Planetary Stewardship. *AMBIO*, 40(7), 739–761. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-011-0185-x>
- Steffen, W., Rockström, J., Richardson, K., Lenton, T. M., Folke, C., Liverman, D., Summerhayes, C. P., Barnosky, A. D., Cornell, S. E., Crucifix, M., Donges, J. F., Fetzer, I., Lade, S. J., Scheffer, M., Winkelmann, R., & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2018). Trajectories of the Earth System in the Anthropocene. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(33), 8252–8259. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1810141115>
- Sterling, E. J., Filardi, C., Toomey, A., Sigouin, A., Betley, E., Gazit, N., Newell, J., Albert, S., Alvira, D., Bergamini, N., Blair, M., Boseto, D., Burrows, K., Bynum, N., Caillon, S., Casselle, J. E., Claudet, J., Cullman, G., Dacks, R., ... Jupiter, S. D. (2017). Biocultural approaches to well-being and sustainability indicators across scales. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1, 1798–1806. <https://doi-org.ezproxy.uvm.edu/10.1038/s41559-017-0349-6>
- Sterman, J. D., Siegel, L., & Rooney-Varga, J. N. (2018). Does replacing coal with wood lower CO 2 emissions? Dynamic lifecycle analysis of wood bioenergy. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(1), 015007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaa512>
- Stokland, H. B. (2020). Conserving Wolves by Transforming Them? The Transformative Effects of Technologies of Government in Biodiversity Conservation. *Society & Animals*, 29(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685306-00001407>
- Tapper, R. (2006). *Wildlife Watching and Tourism: A study on the benefits and risks of a fast growing tourism activity and its impacts on species* (p. 68). UNEP/CMS Secretariat.
- Taylor, W. A., Lindsey, P. A., & Davies-Mostert, H. T. (2015). *An assessment of the economic, social and conservation value of the wildlife ranching industry and its potential to support the green economy in South Africa* (p. 160). Endangered Wildlife Trust.
- Tebboth, M. G. L., Few, R., Assen, M., & Degefu, M. A. (2020). Valuing local perspectives on invasive species management: Moving beyond the ecosystem service-disservice dichotomy. *Ecosystem Services*, 42, 101068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101068>
- Teletchea, F., & Fontaine, P. (2014). *Levels of domestication in fish: Implications for the sustainable future of aquaculture*. 181–195. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12006>
- Terralingua. (2014). *Biocultural Diversity Toolkit: Assessing the State of the World's Languages*. Terralingua. https://terralingua.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Biocultural-Diversity-Toolkit_vol-2.pdf
- Tonazzini, D., Fosse, J., Morales, E., González, A., Klarwein, S., Moukaddem, K., & Louveau, O. (2019). *Blue Tourism. Towards a sustainable coastal and maritime tourism in world marine regions*. (p. 145). eco-union.
- TRAFFIC. (2020). *Legal wildlife trade*. <https://www.traffic.org/about-us/legal-wildlife-trade/>

- Traill, L. W., Bradshaw, C. J. A., & Brook, B. W. (2007). Minimum viable population size: A meta-analysis of 30 years of published estimates. *Biological Conservation*, 139(1–2), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2007.06.011>
- Turner, N. J. (2014). *Ancient Pathways, Ancestral Knowledge*. McGill-Queens University Press.
- Turner, N. J., & Turner, K. L. (2008). “Where our women used to get the food”: Cumulative effects and loss of ethnobotanical knowledge and practice; case study from coastal British Columbia. *Botany*, 86(2), 103–115.
- Turner, N., Plotkin, M., & Kuhnlein, H. V. (2013). Global Environmental Challenges to the integrity of Indigenous Peoples’ Food Systems. In *Indigenous Peoples’ food systems & well-being: Interventions & policies for healthy communities* (pp. 23–38).
- Turpie, J., & Letley, G. (2018). *An initial investigation into the potential feasibility and design of a market-based certification scheme for the wildlife sector of South Africa* (Anchor Environmental Consultants Report No: AEC/1810; p. 102). United Nations Development Programme and Department of Environmental Affairs.
- UN General Assembly. (2020). *Impacts of the coronavirus disease on individual and collective rights of indigenous peoples* (Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, José Francisco Calí Tzay A/75/185; p. 27). United Nations General Assembly.
- United Nations (1982) *UN World Charter for Nature*. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/39295?ln=en>
- United Nations. (1972). *Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment*. <http://www.un-documents.net/unchedec.htm>
- Unrau, A., Becker, G., Spinelli, R., Lazdina, D., Magagnotti, N., Nicolescu, V.-N., Buckley, P., Bartlett, D., & Kofman, P. D. (Eds.). (2018). *Coppice Forests in Europe* (1. Auflage). Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg.
- Vigne, J.-D. (2011). The origins of animal domestication and husbandry: A major change in the history of humanity and the biosphere. *Comptes Rendus Biologies*, 334(3), 171–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crv.2010.12.009>
- Vignieri, S. (2014). Vanishing fauna. Introduction. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 345(6195), 392–395. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.345.6195.392>
- <https://www.iufro.org/science/gfep/forests-and-food-security-panel/report/>
- Vira, B., Wildburger, C., & Mansourian, S. (2015). *Forests, trees and landscapes for food security and nutrition: Contributing to the “Zero Hunger Challenge”* (Vol. 33). International Union of Forest Research Organizations. <https://www.iufro.org/fileadmin/material/publications/iufro-series/ws33/ws33.pdf>
- Walters, G., Pathak Broome, N., Cracco, M., Dash, T., Dudley, N., Elias, S., Hymas, O., Mangubhai, S., Mohan, V., Niederberger, T., Nkollo-Kema Kema, C. A., Oussou Lio, A., Raveloson, N., Rubis, J., Toviehou, S. A. R. M., & Van Vliet, N. (2021). COVID-19, indigenous peoples, local communities and natural resource governance. *Parks*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.20221.Parks-27-SIGW.en>
- Wanger, T. C., Traill, L. W., Cooney, R., Rhodes, J. R., & Tschardtke, T. (2017). Trophy hunting certification. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(12), 1791–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0387-0>
- Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning, and identity*. Cambridge University Press.
- WHO & CBD. (2015). *Connecting global priorities: Biodiversity and human health: a state of knowledge review*. http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/174012/1/9789241508537_eng.pdf?ua=1
- Whyte, K., Caldwell, C., & Schaefer, M. (2018). Indigenous Lessons about Sustainability Are Not Just for “All Humanity.” In *Sustainability* (pp. 149–179). NYU Press. <https://doi.org/10.18574/nyu/9781479894567.003.0007>
- Wiersum, K. F., Gole, T. W., Gatzweiler, F., Volkman, J., Bognetteau, E., & Wirtu, O. (2008). Certification of Wild Coffee in Ethiopia: Experiences and Challenges. *Forests, Trees and Livelihoods*, 18(1), 9–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14728028.2008.9752614>
- Worm, B., Hilborn, R., Baum, J. K., Branch, T. A., Collie, J. S., Costello, C., Fogarty, M. J., Fulton, E. A., Hutchings, J. A., Jennings, S., Jensen, O. P., Lotze, H. K., Mace, P. M., McClanahan, T. R., Minto, C., Palumbi, S. R., Parma, A. M., Ricard, D., Rosenberg, A. A., ... Zeller, D. (2009). Rebuilding Global Fisheries. *Science*, 325(5940), 578–585. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1173146>
- WWF. (2018). *Living Planet Report 2018: Aiming higher* (M. Gooten & R. E. A. Almond, Eds.). www.livingplanetindex.org
- Yi-Ming, L., Zenxiang, G., Xinhai, L., Sung, W., & Niemelä, J. (2000). Illegal Wildlife trade in the Himalaya Region of China. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 9(7), 901–918. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008905430813>
- Zalasiewicz, J. A., Waters, C. N., Williams, M., & Summerhayes, C. P. (Eds.). (2018). *The anthropocene as a geological time unit: A guide to the scientific evidence and current debate*. Cambridge University Press.
- Zeder, M. A. (2015). Core questions in domestication research. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(11), 3191–3198. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1501711112>

